

16th
E D I T I O N

CEPOS

AFTER COMMUNISM.
EAST AND WEST UNDER SCRUTINY

Book of Abstracts

International Academic Conference

20 – 21 March 2026

House of the University
Craiova, Romania

Organized by

Association Centre of Post-Communist Political Studies
Craiova, Romania

PHYSICAL & VIRTUAL ATTENDANCE

CENTER OF POST-COMMUNIST POLITICAL STUDIES (CEPOS)

Anca Parmena Olimid
Cătălina Maria Georgescu
Editors

AFTER COMMUNISM.

EAST AND WEST UNDER SCRUTINY

**Book of Abstracts of the
Sixteenth International Conference After Communism.
East and West Under Scrutiny,
20-21 March 2026, Craiova, Romania**

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CĂTĂLINA MARIA GEORGESCU**
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**AFTER COMMUNISM.
EAST AND WEST UNDER SCRUTINY**

**Book of Abstracts of the
*Sixteenth International Conference After Communism.
East and West Under Scrutiny,
20-21 March 2026, Craiova, Romania***

Editura Sitech
Craiova

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(POST-COLLECTION) is coordinated by
Anca Parmena Olimid and Cătălina Maria Georgescu.

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Post-Communist Political Studies Collection
(POST-COLLECTION) Scientific Committee
beginning with 2013:
Associate Professor Anca Parmena Olimid, Ph.D.
Lecturer Cătălina Maria Georgescu, Ph.D.
Associate Professor Cosmin Lucian Gherghe, Ph.D.

EDITORS' NOTE: The Authors are fully responsible for the entire content of their papers.

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**Welcoming Note from the *The Organizing and Scientific Committees*
16th CEPOS CONFERENCE 2026 *After Communism. East and
West under Scrutiny, 20-21 March 2026, Craiova***

Dear Friends,

On behalf of both *Organizing and Scientific Committees of the Annual CEPOS CONFERENCE After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny 20-21 March 2026 Craiova (Romania)*, we are honored and delighted to welcome you for its 16th edition. You are invited to attend a high-level conference that is designed to balance the ongoing challenges of the East and West by enabling the international/ European, the national, the local and regional paths to democracy, civic participation, freedoms and rights, transition reforms, transitional justice, security inputs and outputs, integration and development, political history and collective memory. We shall focus on the social changes, the recent political events, the media-communication-politics links, the transitional justice, the comparative policies, the reforms and the competitiveness sector. Our agenda is focused on answering to the current research thematic of the social and political sciences domain with panelists, chairs and invited key addresses, more than 140 scientific papers, book launches and via internet panels, research tutorials and student workshops. As always, CEPOS is honored and pleased to welcome its friends and special guests sharing the precious research contributions aimed to contribute to the international impact of the CEPOS Conference 2026.

We hope to welcome you again on 12-13 March 2027!

The Organizing and Scientific Committees of the
16th International Conference AFTER COMMUNISM.
EAST AND WEST UNDER SCRUTINY,
Craiova, 20-21 March 2026

Organizing Committee of the 16th International Conference AFTER COMMUNISM. EAST AND WEST UNDER SCRUTINY, Craiova, 20-21 March 2026

Board of Directors (provided by CEPOS staff):
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Rafał Jung, Ph.D. University of Łódź, Political Theory and Political Thought (Sports Policy Research Group, Faculty of International and Political Studies, Łódź, Poland)
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Professor Virgil Stoica, Ph.D. (“Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, Romania)
Professor Gabriela Rățulea, Ph.D. (Transylvania University of Brașov, Romania)
Professor Dan Claudiu Dănișor, Ph.D. (University of Craiova)
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Professor Andra Seceleanu, Ph.D. (Andrei Saguna University of Constanta, Romania)
Professor Luminița Șoproni, Ph.D. (University of Oradea, Romania)
Professor Claudiu Tufiș, Ph.D. (University of Bucharest, Romania)
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Professor Jonuz Abdullahi, Ph.D. (South East European University, Skopje, Republic of North Macedonia)
Professor Ali Pajaziti, Ph.D. (South East European University, Skopje, Republic of North Macedonia)
Professor Ali Musliu, Ph.D. (State University of Tetova, Law Faculty, Republic of North Macedonia)
Professor George Gîrleşteanu, Ph.D. Habil. (University of Craiova)
Associate Professor Adrian Basarabă, Ph. D. (West University of Timișoara, Romania)
Professor Simber Atay, Ph.D. (Dokuz Eylül University, Fine Arts Faculty, İzmir, Turkey)

General Information

E-mail:

cepos2013@gmail.com, cepos2023@gmail.com

Website: <http://cepos.eu/upcoming.html>

Facebook: CEPOS FACEBOOK

<http://ro-ro.facebook.com/pages/Center-of-Post-Communist-Political-Studies-CEPOS/485957361454074>

Political Sciences Specialization (University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences Romania)

SP Facebook

<https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100010712348257>

Important! Previous Publication of the Conference materials

Publication of the CEPOS Conference articles at previous editions (2012-2025) in Revista de Științe Politice. Revue des Sciences Politiques – around 500-1000 pages of conference materials published/ year (archive issues 2012-2025) assessed and indexed by the following international databases⁵ ERIH Plus, ProQuest, EBSCO, Gale Cengage Learning, Index Copernicus, CEEOL available at <http://cis01.central.ucv.ro/revistadestiintepolitice/acces.php>

CONTACT:REVISTA DE ȘTIINȚE POLITICE. REVUE DES SCIENCES POLITIQUES

University of Craiova, 13th A. I. Cuza Street, Craiova, 200585, Dolj, Romania. Phone /Fax: +40251418515, Email: cepos2023@gmail.com.

Website:<http://cis01.central.ucv.ro/revistadestiintepolitice>

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 Article Submission Deadlines – 2026 Update

 Revista de Științe Politice. Revue des Sciences Politiques

 The submission deadlines are:

- 25 March 2026 (Issue 89 / April)
- 25 April 2026 (Issue 90 / June)
- 1 August 2026 (Issue 91 / September)
- 1 November 2026 (Issue 92 / December)

CEPOS International Conferences 2014-2026: International Indexing and Abstracting

CEPOS Conference 2026

The **Sixteenth International Conference** After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 20-21 March 2026) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 11 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases

Indexation links

1. **ConferenceAlerts**
Conal Conference Alerts
<https://conferencealerts.com/country-listing?country=Romania>
2. **CEPOS (site oficial – secțiunea Upcoming 2026)**
<https://cepos.eu/upcoming2026>
3. **Conferencelists.org**
https://www.conferencelists.org/event/cepos-16th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny/?utm_source=chatgpt.com
4. **ConfFinder (Conferences in Romania)**
https://conffinder.com/pagesconference/ConferencesListing?country=Romania&utm_source=chatgpt.com
5. **Events notification**
<https://eventsnotification.com/event/61037>
6. **Conferencesked**
https://www.conferencesked.com/conference_details/15391/cepos-16th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny

7. 📌 **Conffinder**
<https://www.confinder.com/pagesconference/ConferencesListing?country=Romania>

8. 📌 **Sciencedz**
https://www.google.com/search?q=16th+cepos+international+confernece+2026&og=16th+cepos+international+confernece+2026&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOTIJCAEQIRgKKGKABMgkIAhAhGAoYoAHSAQkxMDMyOWowajSoAgGwAgE&client=ms-android-motorola-rvo3&sourceid=chrome-mobile&ie=UTF-8#ip=1

9. 📌 **Conference daily**
<https://conferencesdaily.com/european-studies-conferences>

10. 📌 **Scholarly meet**
https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&opi=89978449&url=https://scholarlymeet.com/country/fr&ved=2ahUKEwikirrDuqeSAxW7wAIHHfhgE2c4FBAWegQIKRAB&usg=AOvVaw3pIVukONrNS4lLm1n6vU_R

11. 📌 **Conferencealertz**
<https://www.conferencealertz.com/conferenceslist?country=Romania>

CEPOS Conference 2025

The **Fifteenth International Conference** After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 14-15 March 2025) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 14 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

Indexation links:

1. <https://academic.oup.com/jcs/article-abstract/67/1/csaf001/7997508?redirectedFrom=PDF>
<https://scholarlymeet.com/events/ca73318d-42a7-4b5e-bcca-635e0aa1c46b>
2. <https://conferences365.com/conferences-in-romania>

3. <https://conferencewiki.com/conference-listing/MzA4>
4. <https://www.conferencelists.org/event/cepos-15th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny/>
5. <https://www.sciencedz.net/en/conference/110381-cepos-15th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>
6. <https://conferencealerts.com/show-event?id=262202>
7. <https://conferencedaily.com/cities/craiova>
8. <https://cepos.org/upcoming/>
9. <https://10times.com/after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>
10. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/379144286_CENTER_OF_POST-COMMUNIST_POLITICAL_STUDIES_CEPOS_Book_of_abstracts_of_the_14th_International_Conference_After_Communism_East_and_West_under_Scrutiny_Craiova_Romania_15-16_March_2024
11. <https://conferencewiki.com/conference-detail/Cepos-15th-International-Conference-After-communism-East-and-West-under-scrutiny>
12. <https://www.conferencelists.org/romania/>
13. https://www.conferencesked.com/conference_details/10148/cepos-15th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny
14. <https://conffinder.com/pagesconference/ConferencesListing?country=Romania>

CEPOS Conference 2024

The **Fourteenth International Conference** After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 15-16 March 2024) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 11 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

Indexation links:

1. CEEOL <https://www.ceeol.com/search/article-detail?id=1195305>
2. ProQuest, Part of Clarivate <https://www.proquest.com/docview/2863220849/CC02F21AE4DB44F1PQ/1?accountid=50247&sourcetype=Scholarly%20Journals>
3. Oxford Academic (Oxford University Press)

<https://doi.org/10.1093/jcs/csad066>

Oxford Journal of Church and State-Oxford Academic (Oxford University Press) (Vol. 65, nr 4/2023) în secțiunea Calendar of Events JCS (publicare 28 Noiembrie 2023)

4. Conference Alerts

<https://conferencealerts.com/show-event?id=254313>

5. Science DZ

<https://www.sciencedz.net/.../100575-14th-international...>

6. 10 Times

<https://10times.com/after-communism-east-and-west-under...>

7. The Free Library

<https://www.thefreelibrary.com/CEPOS+NEW+CALL+FOR+PAPERS...>

8. Conference 365

<https://conferences365.com/.../14th-international...>

9. World University Directory

<https://worlduniversitydirectory.com/edu/event/...>

10. Conferences daily

<https://conferencesdaily.com/eventdetails.php?id=1625192>

11. Gale Cengage Learning USA

<https://go.gale.com/ps/i.do?id=GALE%7CA766112846...>

CEPOS Conference 2023

The **Thirteenth International Conference** After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 17-18 March 2023) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 6 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

- Oxford Church & State Journal: <https://academic.oup.com/jcs/article-abstract/65/1/168/7044222?redirectedFrom=fulltext>
- 10 Times: <https://10times.com/after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>
- Conferencesite.eu: <https://index.conferencesites.eu/conference/575/10/13th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny;>
- Schoolandcollegelistsings :<https://www.schoolandcollegelistsings.com/RO/Craiova/485957361454074/Center-of-Post-Communist-Political-Studies-CEPOS>

- Conferencealerts : <https://conferencealerts.com/show-event?id=247851>
- Sciencedz : <https://www.sciencedz.net/en/conference/93446-13th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

CEPOS Conference 2022

The **Twelfth International Conference** After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 18-19 March 2022) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 6 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

<https://www.conferenceflare.com/events/category/social-sciences-and-humanities/art-history/>

Vinculation International Diciembre 2021 newsletter n 99

https://issuu.com/fundacionargeninta5/docs/diciembre_2021_fundaci_n_argeninta-ai_ok?fr=sZjg2NjE5NTg3OTY

<https://www.schoolandcollegelistings.com/RO/Craiova/485957361454074/Center-of-Post-Communist-Political-Studies-CEPOS>

<https://10times.com/company/cepos>

<https://10times.com/after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

<https://conferencealerts.com/show-event?id=238529>

<https://www.sciencedz.net/conference/82995-cepos-international-conference-2022-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

CEPOS Conference 2021

The Eleventh International Conference After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 19-20 March 2021) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 5 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

[https://academic.oup.com/jcs/advance-article-](https://academic.oup.com/jcs/advance-article-abstract/doi/10.1093/jcs/csaa064/5941887?redirectedFrom=fulltext)

Abstract:[doi/10.1093/jcs/csaa064/5941887?redirectedFrom=fulltext](https://academic.oup.com/jcs/advance-article-abstract/doi/10.1093/jcs/csaa064/5941887?redirectedFrom=fulltext)

<https://conferencealerts.com/show-event?id=229654>

<https://www.sciencedz.net/en/conference/72628-1th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

<https://10times.com/after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

<https://worlduniversitydirectory.com/edu/event/?slib=1th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny-2>

CEPOS Conference 2020

The Tenth International Conference After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 27-28 March 2020) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 6 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

Scichemistry

<http://scichemistry.org/ConferenceInfosByConferenceTopicId?conferenceTopicId=57>

Oxford Journals

<https://academic.oup.com/jcs/advance-article-pdf/doi/10.1093/jcs/csz078/30096829/csz078.pdf>

Conference alerts

<https://conferencealerts.com/show-event?id=215370>

<https://www.sciencedz.net/en/conference/57625-10th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

Intraders

<https://www.intraders->

[org.cdn.ampproject.org/v/s/www.intraders.org/news/romania/10th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny/amp/?amp_js_v=a2&_gsa=1&usqp=mq331AQCKAE%3D#ao](https://www.intraders-)
[h=15737604302246&referrer=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.google.com&_t](https://www.intraders-)
[f=De%20pe%20%251%24s&share=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.intraders.o](https://www.intraders-)
[rg%2Fnews%2Fromania%2F10th-international-conference-after-](https://www.intraders-)
[communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny%2F](https://www.intraders-)

10 times

<https://10times.com/after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

The conference alerts

<https://theconferencealerts.com/event/46428/10th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

Scirea

<https://www.scirea.org/ConferenceInfosByConferenceCountryId?conferenceCountryId=75>

CEPOS Conference 2019

The Ninth International Conference After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 29-30 March 2019) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 6 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

Oxford Academic Journal of Church & State

[https://academic.oup.com/jcs/article-Abstract/60/4/784/5106417?redirectedFrom=PDF](https://academic.oup.com/jcs/article-abstract/60/4/784/5106417?redirectedFrom=PDF)

10 Times

<https://10times.com/after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

Conference Alerts

<https://conferencealerts.com/show-event?id=205682>

Researchgate

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327905733_CEPOS_9TH_INTERNATIONAL_CONFERENCE_AFTER_COMMUNISM_EAST_AND_WEST_UNDER_SCRUTINY_2019?_iepl%5BviewId%5D=sjcOJrVCO8PTLapcfVciZQsb&_iepl%5Bcontexts%5D%5B0%5D=publicationCreationEOT&_iepl%5BtargetEntityId%5D=PB%3A327905733&_iepl%5BinteractionType%5D=publicationCTA

The Free Library

<https://www.thefreelibrary.com/9th+INTERNATIONAL+CONFERENCE+AFTER+COMMUNISM.+EAST+AND+WEST+UNDER...-a0542803701>

Science Dz.net

<https://www.sciencedz.net/conference/42812-9th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

CEPOS Conference 2018

The Eighth International Conference After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 23–24 March 2018) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 15 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

Conference Alerts, <https://conferencealerts.com/show-event?id=186626>

Sciencesdz, <http://www.sciencedz.net/conference/29484-8th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

ManuscriptLink,

<https://manuscriptlink.com/cfp/detail?cfpId=AYAXKVAR46277063&type=event>

Maspolitiques, <http://www.maspolitiques.com/ar/index.php/en/1154-8th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

Aconf, https://www.aconf.org/conf_112399.html

Call4paper, <https://call4paper.com/listByCity?type=event&city=3025&count=count>

Eventegg, <https://eventegg.com/cepos/>

10 times, <https://10times.com/after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

Biblioteca de Sociologie, <http://bibliotecadesociologie.ro/cfp-cepos-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny-craiova-2018/>

Science Research Association

<http://www.scirea.org/topiclisting?conferenceTopicId=5>

ResearcherBook <http://researcherbook.com/country/Romania>

Conference Search Net, <http://conferencesearch.net/en/29484-8th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

SchoolandCollegeListings,

<https://www.schoolandcollegelistings.com/RO/Craiova/485957361454074/Center-of-Post-Communist-Political-Studies-CEPOS>

Vepub conference, <http://www.vepub.com/conferences-view/8th-International-Conference-After-Communism.-East-and-West-under-Scrutiny/bC9aUE5rcHN0ZmpkYU9nTHJzUkRmdz09/>

Geopolitika Hungary, <http://www.geopolitika.hu/event/8th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny/>

CEPOS Conference 2017

The Seventh International Conference After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 24–25 March 2017) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 10 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

Ethic & International Affairs (Carnegie Council), Cambridge University Press-<https://www.ethicsandinternationalaffairs.org/2016/upcoming-conferences-interest-2016-2017/>

ELSEVIER GLOBAL EVENTS

LIST <http://www.globaleventslist.elsevier.com/events/2017/03/7th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

CONFERENCE ALERTS-<http://www.conferencealerts.com/show-event?id=171792>

10TIMES.COM-<https://10times.com/after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

Hiway Conference Discovery System-

<http://www.hicds.cn/meeting/detail/45826124>

Geopolitika (Hungary)-<http://www.geopolitika.hu/event/7th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny/>

Academic.net-<http://www.academic.net/show-24-4103-1.html>

World University Directory-

<http://www.worlduniversitydirectory.com/conferencedetail.php?AgentID=2001769>

Science Research Association-

<http://www.scirea.org/conferenceinfo?conferenceId=35290>

Science Social Community-<https://www.science-community.org/ru/node/174892>

CEPOS Conference 2016

The Sixth International Conference After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 8-9 April 2016) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in the following international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

ELSEVIER GLOBAL EVENTS-

<http://www.globaleventslist.elsevier.com/events/2016/04/6th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny/>

Oxford Journals – Oxford Journal of Church & State-

<http://jcs.oxfordjournals.org/content/early/2016/02/06/jcs.csv121.extract>

Conference Alerts-<http://www.conferencealerts.com/country-listing?country=Romania>

Conferences-In - <http://conferences-in.com/conference/romania/2016/economics/6th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny/>

Socmag.net - <http://www.socmag.net/?p=1562>

African Journal of Political Sciences-

http://www.maspolitiques.com/mas/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=450:-securiteec-&catid=2:2010-12-09-22-47-00&Itemid=4#.VjUI5PnhCUk

Researchgate-

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283151988_Call_for_Papers_

6TH International Conference After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny 8-9 April 2016 Craiova Romania

World Conference Alerts-

<http://www.worldconferencealerts.com/ConferenceDetail.php?EVENT=WLD1442>

Edu events-<http://eduevents.eu/listings/6th-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny/>

Esocsci.org-<http://www.esocsci.org.nz/events/list/>

Sciencedz.net-

<http://www.sciencedz.net/index.php?topic=events&page=53>

Science-community.org-<http://www.science-community.org/ru/node/164404/?did=070216>

CEPOS Conference 2015

The Fifth International Conference After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny (Craiova, House of the University, 24-25 April 2015) was evaluated and accepted for indexing in 15 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases:

THE ATLANTIC COUNCIL OF CANADA, CANADA-

<http://natocouncil.ca/events/international-conferences/>

ELSEVIER GLOBAL EVENTS LIST-

<http://www.globaleventslist.elsevier.com/events/2015/04/fifth-international-conf>

GCONFERENCE.NET-

http://www.gconference.net/eng/conference_view.html?no=47485&catalog=1&cata=018&co_kind=&co_type=&pageno=1&conf_cata=01

CONFERENCE BIOXBIO-

<http://conference.bioxbio.com/location/romania>

10 TIMES-<http://10times.com/romania>

CONFERENCE ALERTS-<http://www.conferencealerts.com/country-listing?country=Romania>

<http://www.iem.ro/orizont2020/wp-content/uploads/2014/12/lista-3-conferinte-internationale.pdf>

<http://sdil.ac.ir/index.aspx?pid=99&articleid=62893>

NATIONAL SYMPOSIUM-

<http://www.nationalsymposium.com/communism.php>

SCIENCE DZ-<http://www.sciencedz.net/conference/6443-fifth-international-conference-after-communism-east-and-west-under-scrutiny>

scrutiny

ARCHIVE COM-http://archive-com.com/com/c/conferencealerts.com/2014-12-01_5014609_70/Rome_15th_International_Academic_Conference_The_ISES/

CONFERENCE WORLD-<http://conferencesworld.com/higher-education/>

KNOW A CONFERENCE KNOW A CONFERENCE-
<http://knowaconference.com/social-work/>

International Journal on New Trends in Education and Their Implications (IJONTE) Turkey <http://www.ijonte.org/?pnum=15&>

Journal of Research in Education and Teaching Turkey-
<http://www.jret.org/?pnum=13&pt=Kongre+ve+Sempozyum>

CEPOS CONFERENCE 2015 is part of a "consolidated list of all international and Canadian conferences taking place pertaining to international relations, politics, trade, energy and sustainable development". For more details see

<http://natocouncil.ca/events/international-conferences/>

CEPOS Conference 2014

The Fourth International Conference After Communism. East and West under Scrutiny, Craiova, 4-5 April 2014 was very well received by the national media and successfully indexed in more than 9 international databases, catalogues and NGO's databases such as:

American Political Science Association, USA-

<http://www.apsanet.org/conferences.cfm;>

Journal of Church and State, Oxford-

<http://jcs.oxfordjournals.org/content/early/2014/01/23/jcs.cst141.full.pdf+html;>

NATO Council of Canada (section events/ international conferences),

Canada, <http://atlantic-council.ca/events/international-conferences/>

International Society of Political Psychology, Columbus, USA-

http://www.ispp.org/uploads/attachments/April_2014.pdf

Academic Biographical Sketch,

<http://academicprofile.org/SeminarConference.aspx;>

Conference alerts, <http://www.conferencealerts.com/show-event?id=121380;>

Gesis Sowiport, Koln, Germany, [http://sowiport.gesis.org/;](http://sowiport.gesis.org/) Osteuropa-

Netzwerk, Universität Kassel, Germany, <http://its-vm508.its.uni->

kassel.de/mediawiki/index.php/After_communism_:_East_and_West_u
nder_scrutiny : Fourth International Conference
Ilustre Colegio Nacional de Doctores y Licenciados en Ciencias
Políticas y Sociología, futuro Consejo Nacional de Colegios
Profesionales, Madrid, <http://colpolsocmadrid.org/agenda/>.

Research Visibility and International Indexing of the CEPOS Book of Abstracts

The Book of Abstracts of CEPOS Annual Conference is internationally indexed on ResearchGate, with its own autonomous link that can be used for academic reporting and evaluation purposes.

©* Indexing of the CEPOS International Conference Book of Abstracts 2025:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/389899084_Book_of_Abstracts_of_the_Fifteenth_International_Conference_After_Communism_East_and_West_Under_Scrutiny_14-15_March_2025_Craiova_Romania

©* Indexing of the CEPOS International Conference Book of Abstracts 2024:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/389899084_Book_of_Abstracts_of_the_Fifteenth_International_Conference_After_Communism_East_and_West_Under_Scrutiny_14-15_March_2025_Craiova_Romania

©* Indexing of the CEPOS International Conference Book of Abstracts 2023:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/393775729_Book_of_abstracts_of_the_Thirteenth_International_Conference_After_Communism_East_and_West_under_Scrutiny_17-18_March_2023_Craiova_Romania

©* Indexing of the CEPOS International Conference Book of Abstracts 2022:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/393776033_Book_of_Abstracts_of_the_Twelfth_International_Conference_After_Communism_East_and_West_Under_Scrutiny_18-19_March_2022_Craiova_Romania

©* **Indexing of the CEPOS International Conference Book of Abstracts 2021:**

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/393776031_Book_of_Abstracts_of_the_Eleventh_International_Conference_After_Communism_East_and_West_Under_Scrutiny_19-20_March_2021_Craiova_Romania

©* **Indexing of the CEPOS International Conference Book of Abstracts 2020:**

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/393776117_Book_of_Abstracts_of_the_Tenth_International_Conference_AfterCommunism_East_and_West_Under_Scrutiny_27-28_March_2020_Craiova_Romania

Revista de Științe Politice. Revue des Sciences Politiques
International Indexing in International Databases, Library
Catalogues and Online Services (latest updates)

International Indexing & Abstracting
Databases – 2026

Revue des Sciences Politiques / Revista de Științe Politice

• • •

EBSCO

Political Science Complete (accessed March 16, 2026). Database Coverage List:

<https://about.ebsco.com/m/ee/Marketing/titleList/s/poh-coverage.xls> (position 2870)

Political Science Complete

Subject Social Sciences & Humanities/ Area Studies/ European Studies:

<https://www.ebsco.com/m/ee/Marketing/titleList/s/poh-subject.xls> (position 1690)

Central & Eastern European Academic Source (accessed March 16, 2026)

Database Coverage List:

<https://www.ebsco.com/m/ee/Marketing/titleList/s/e5h-coverage.htm>

ProQuest Database: Political Science Database

ProQuest Political Science Database Title list accurate as of March 16, 2026 (position 1200)

http://tls.search.proquest.com/titlelist/jsp/list/tlsSingle.jsp?productId=1005684&_ga=2.52655656.1051237904.1586630685-491238151.1586630685

INDEX COPERNICUS

ICI Journals Master list,

<https://journals.indexcopernicus.com/search/details?id=29570>

ICV 2024: 100.00; ICV 2023: 100.00; ICV 2022: 100.00; ICV 2021: 100.00; ICV 2020: 91.36; ICV 2019: 94.31; ICV 2018: 97.28; ICV 2017: 88.23; ICV 2016: 78.07; ICV 2015: 65.59; ICV 2014: 65.01 • Standardized Value: 6.55; ICV 2013: 5.04

ERIH PLUS

<https://kanalregister.hkdir.no/publiseringskanaler/erihplus/periodical/info.action?id=486286>

ERIH PLUS Interdisciplinary research in the disciplines: Political Sciences and Internatio

OECD Other Social Sciences. Political classifications:

CEEOL

Central and Eastern European Online Library

<http://www.ceeol.com/search/journal-detail?id=2102>

KVK Catalogue Karlsruhe Institut für Technologie

<https://kvk.bibliothek.kit.edu>,

Gale Cengage Learning - Academic OneFile

Report Generated 16/03//2026 (position 18266)

<https://support.gale.com/tlist/products/>

Google scholar

<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=geaFfgAAAAJ&hl=ro;>

2026: h-index: 21; i10-index: 67

2025: h-index: 19; i10-index: 57

2024: h-index: 15; i10-index: 40

2023: h-index: 12; i10-index: 25

2022: h-index: 11; i10-index: 14

JISC Library Hub Discover

<https://discover.libraryhub.jisc.ac.uk/search?&keyword=1584-224x>

TIB Leibniz Information Centre University Library

<https://www.tib.eu/en/search/id/TIBKAT%3A590280090/Revista-de-%C8%99tiin%C8%9Be-politice/>

Réseau Mir@bel. Mir@bel est piloté par Sciences Po Lyon, Sciences Po Grenoble, la MSH Dijon/RNMSH et l'ENTPE. <https://reseau-mirabel.info/revue/3046/Revista-de-Stiinte-Politice>

EP Library
CATALOGUE

European Parliament Library Catalogue

https://europarl.primo.exlibrisgroup.com/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma991001117790704886&context=L&vid=32EPA_INST:32EPA_V1&lang=en&search_scope=MyInst_and_CI&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine&tab=Everything&query=any,contains,1584-224x&offset=0

Polska Bibliografia Naukowa

<https://pbn.nauka.gov.pl/core/#/journal/view/5e715c9646e0fb0001cb2ef2/d5591413-f693-4a5f-b60e-f54b786edbc6>

ACNP Catalogo Italiano dei Periodici

<https://acnpsearch.unibo.it/journal/2601620>

Information Matrix for the Analysis of Journals

<https://miar.ub.edu/issn/1584-224X>

WorldCat

<https://www.worldcat.org/title/Revista-de-Stiinte-Politice-Revue-de-Sciences-Politiques/oclc/896853479>

Revista de Științe Politice. Revue des Sciences Politiques-Google Scholar

Evolution of bibliometric indicators

- 2026: h-index 21 | i10-index 67
- 2025: h-index 19 | i10-index 57
- 2024: h-index 15 | i10-index 40
- 2023: h-index 12 | i10-index 25
- 2022: h-index 11 | i10-index 1

Source:

https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=geaF_FgAAAAJ&hl=en&authuser=4

Google Academic

Revista de Stiinte Politice. Revue des Sciences Politiques

Afiere recunoscută
Adresă de e-mail confirmată pe central.ucv.ro - [Pagina de pornire](#)
Political Sciences Institutions Reform Administration Law

Citat de

	Toate	Din 2021
Referințe bibliografice	2654	1778
h-index	21	19
i10-index	67	45

AFIȘATELE PE TOATE

TITLU	CITAT DE	ANUL
Defining the new economics of labor migration theory boundaries: a sociological-level analysis of international migration A Popombica Revista de Științe Politice. Revue des Sciences Politiques, 55-64	74	2015
Emotional intelligence as a type of cognitive ability Al Buzai Revista de Științe Politice. Revue des Sciences Politiques, 204-215	67	2020
Teaching the digital natives CD Bărbuțeanu	48	2020

Revista de Științe Politice. Revue des Sciences Politiques-Google Scholar

Source:

https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=geaF_FgAAAAJ&hl=en&authuser=4

Revista de Științe Politice. Revue des Sciences Politiques-Google Scholar

Source:

https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=geaF_FgAAAAJ&hl=en&authuser=4

Revista de Științe Politice. Revue des Sciences Politiques. New indexing and Abstracting (Statistics 2025-2026)

Following our **March 2026 update on international listings**, we are pleased to announce **new indexations and catalogue entries from the United Kingdom recorded in March 2026**, further expanding the international visibility of our publications.

Data source:

<https://discover.libraryhub.jisc.ac.uk/search...>

Holding Libraries – United Kingdom

- Aberystwyth University Library – <https://www.aber.ac.uk/en/library/> – Aberystwyth, Wales, UK
- Anglia Ruskin University Library – <https://library.aru.ac.uk/> – Cambridge / Chelmsford, England, UK
- Bangor University Library – <https://www.bangor.ac.uk/library> – Bangor, Wales, UK
- University of Bath Library – <https://www.bath.ac.uk/campaigns/library/> – Bath, England, UK
- University of Birmingham Libraries – <https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/university/library> – Birmingham, England, UK
- Cardiff Metropolitan University Library – <https://www.cardiffmet.ac.uk/library/> – Cardiff, Wales, UK
- Cardiff University Libraries – <https://www.cardiff.ac.uk/libraries> – Cardiff, Wales, UK
- City St George's, University of London Library Services – <https://libraryservices.city.ac.uk/> – London, England, UK

- Coventry University Library – <https://libguides.coventry.ac.uk/> – Coventry, England, UK
- Durham University Library and Collections – <https://www.durham.ac.uk/departments/library/> – Durham, England, UK
- University of East Anglia Library – <https://www.uea.ac.uk/library> – Norwich, England, UK
- Edge Hill University Library – <https://www.edgehill.ac.uk/departments/support/library/> – Ormskirk, England, UK
- University of Edinburgh Libraries – <https://www.ed.ac.uk/information.../library-museum-gallery> – Edinburgh, Scotland, UK
- Edinburgh Napier University Library – <https://www.napier.ac.uk/library> – Edinburgh, Scotland, UK
- Glasgow Caledonian University Library – <https://www.gcu.ac.uk/library> – Glasgow, Scotland, UK
- University of Glasgow Library – <https://www.gla.ac.uk/myglasgow/library/> – Glasgow, Scotland, UK
- LSE Library – <https://www.lse.ac.uk/library> – London, England, UK
- Lancaster University Library – <https://www.lancaster.ac.uk/library/> – Lancaster, England

 Listings and updates in international databases, services, and library catalogues recorded in **March 2026**, coming from:

Denmark

 Universität Zürich Journal Database, Switzerland
Zurich Open Repository and Archive
<https://www.idb.uzh.ch/id/eprint/21535/>

 Royal Danish Library, Denmark
https://soeg.kb.dk/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma99123026492405763&context=L&vid=45KBDK_KGL:KGL&lang=en&search_scope=MyInst_and_CI&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine&tab=Everything&query=any,contains,1584-224x&offset=0

 SwissCovey, Swiss Library Service Platform (SLSP) Switzerland
https://swisscovery.slsp.ch/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma991170234587405501&context=L&vid=41SLSP_NETWORK:VU1_UNION&lang=de&search_scope=DN_and_CI&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine&tab=41SLSP_NETWORK&query=any,contains,1584-224x&offset=0

 Science On University Achievement Information System by University of Lodz, Poland
<https://son.uni.lodz.pl/.../ULbfee0e874c6a41c4a00d516e09.../>

 Le réseau vaudois Renouvaud Sciences et Patrimoines, Switzerland
https://renouvaud1.primo.exlibrisgroup.com/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma991021158885602852&context=L&vid=41BCULAUSA_LIB:VU2&lang=fr&search_scope=SP_libraries_and_CDI&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine&tab=Everything&query=any,contains,1584-224x&offset=0

 Rebiun Catálogo de la Red de Bibliotecas Universitarias y Científicas, Spain
<https://rebiun.baratz.es/.../b2FpOmNlbGVicmF0aW9uOmVzLmJh...>

KOBV Kooperativer Bibliotheksverbund Berlin Brandenburg, Germany
<https://portal.kobv.de/simpleSearch.do?index=internal&plv=2&sortCriteria=score&sortOrder=desc&hitsPerPage=&query=1584-224x&formsearch=%E2%9C%93#resultlistForm>

Katalog der Teilbibliothek Diakonie, Gesundheit und Soziales der Hochschule Hannover, Germany
<https://opac.tib.eu/DB=4.5/LNG=DU/SID=f438f44d-1/CMD...>

Revista de Științe Politice. Revue des Sciences Politiques. Other indexing and Abstracting (Statistics 2015-2026)

Kolibris Recherche Multibases

https://kolibris.univ-antilles.fr/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma991002037100405746&context=L&vid=33UAG_INST:33UAG_INST&lang=fr&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine

Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek Sachsen-Anhalt / Zentrale

<https://search.worldcat.org/libraries/18585>

Szeged University Library

<https://search.worldcat.org/libraries/104426>

Harriet Irving Library (UNB Libraries)

<https://search.worldcat.org/libraries/133054>

Thüringer Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek

<https://search.worldcat.org/libraries/18584>

Ibero-Amerikanisches Institut Preußischer Kulturbesitz, Bibliothek

<https://search.worldcat.org/libraries/100860>

Robert A Nicholson University Library

<https://search.worldcat.org/libraries/930>

Stellenbosch University Library

<https://search.worldcat.org/libraries/71498>

Universitätsbibliothek Leipzig

<https://search.worldcat.org/libraries/66103>

EP Library Catalogue – European Parliament Library Catalogue

https://europarl.primo.exlibrisgroup.com/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma991001117790704886&context=L&vid=32EPA_INST:32EPA_V1&lang=en&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine&tab=Everything&query=su b,exact,Europe%20de%20l%27Est%20--%20Politique%20et%20gouvernement,AND&mode=advanced&offset=0

Ghent University Library

<https://lib.ugent.be/en/catalog/ejn01:1000000000726583>

Universidad Carlos III de Madrid Research Portal

<https://researchportal.uc3m.es/display/rev184334>

J-Gate Social Science & Humanities Indexed Journal List

<https://www.kitsw.ac.in/Library/2022/JSSH%20Journal%20List.pdf>

<https://europub.co.uk/journals/revista-de-stiinte-politice-revue-des-sciences-politiques-J-11661>

Universiteits Bibliotheek Gent

<https://lib.ugent.be/catalog/ejn01:1000000000726583>

Publons

<https://publons.com/journal/540040/revista-de-stiinte-politice/>

Universidad Carlos III de Madrid

<https://researchportal.uc3m.es/display/rev184334>

Weill Cornell Medicine Qatar

[https://primo.qatar-](https://primo.qatar-weill.cornell.edu/discovery/fulldisplay?vid=974WCMCIQ_INST:VU1&docid=alma991000575074006691&lang=en&context=L&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine)

[weill.cornell.edu/discovery/fulldisplay?vid=974WCMCIQ_INST:VU1&docid=alma991000575074006691&lang=en&context=L&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine](https://primo.qatar-weill.cornell.edu/discovery/fulldisplay?vid=974WCMCIQ_INST:VU1&docid=alma991000575074006691&lang=en&context=L&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine)

Reseau Mirabel

<https://reseau-mirabel.info/revue/3046/Revista-de-Stiinte-Politice>

Bond Library University

https://librarysearch.bond.edu.au/discovery/fulldisplay?vid=61BOND_INST%3ABOND&docid=alma9930197890502381&lang=en&context=SP

Stanford University Libraries, Stanford, United States

<https://searchworks.stanford.edu/?q=469823489>

Cornell University Library, Ithaca, United States

https://newcatalog.library.cornell.edu/catalog?search_field=publisher+number%2Fother+identifier&q=469823489

University of Michigan Library,

<https://search.lib.umich.edu/catalog?&library=All+libraries&query=isbn%3A469823489>

Pepperdine Libraries, Malibu, United States

https://pepperdine.worldcat.org/search?qt=wc_org_pepperdine&q=no:469823489

University of Victoria Libraries , Victoria, Canada

<http://uvic.summon.serialssolutions.com/#!/search?ho=t&fvf=ContentType,Journal%20Article,f&l=en&q=1584-224X>

Academic Journals database

<http://journaldatabase.info/journal/issn1584-224X>

University of Zurich Database

<https://www.jdb.uzh.ch/id/eprint/21535/>

California Institute of Technology - Caltech Library

<https://www.library.caltech.edu/eds/detail?db=poh&an=98646324&isbn=1584224X>

Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin

http://kvk.bibliothek.kit.edu/view-title/index.php?katalog=STABI_BERLIN&url=http%3A%2F%2Fstabilitat.de%2FDB%3D1%2FCHARSET%3DISO-8859-1%2FIMPLAND%3DY%2FLNG%3DDU%2FSRT%3DYOP%2FTTL%3D1%2FSID%3D8dda05f3-1%2FSET%3D1%2FSHW%3FFRST%3D1&signature=eBtSKEx2BuW-HASpUsCT39FB3vQpIm6cGAajCH-kz44&showCoverImg=1

Union Catalogue of Belgian Libraries

http://kvk.bibliothek.kit.edu/view-title/index.php?katalog=VERBUND_BELGIEN&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.unicat.be%2Funicat%3Ffunc%3Dsearch%26query%3Dsysisid%3A7330250&signature=Dxc-cVFWjMO1W4HpEAWW_ERyKR4oiGWXLGFinWk8fNU&showCoverImg=1

The National Library of Israel

http://merhav.nli.org.il/primo-explore/fulldisplay?vid=ULI&docid=NNL-Journals003477656&context=L&lang=en_US

Verbundkatalog GBV

http://kvk.bibliothek.kit.edu/view-title/index.php?katalog=GBV&url=http%3A%2F%2Fgso.gbv.de%2FDB%3D2.1%2FCHARSET%3DUTF-8%2FIMPLAND%3DY%2FLNG%3DDU%2FSRT%3DYOP%2FTTL%3D1%2FCOOKIE%3DD2.1%2CE900d94f2-d%2CI0%2CB9000%2B%2B%2B%2B%2B%2B%2CSY%2CA%2CH6-11%2C%2C16-17%2C%2C21%2C%2C30%2C%2C50%2C%2C60-61%2C%2C73-75%2C%2C77%2C%2C88-90%2CNKVK%2BWEBZUGANG%2CR129.13.130.211%2CFN%2FSET%3D1%2FPPNSET%3FPPN%3D590280090&signature=Omwa_NLt wvdaOmmyeo7SUOCEYuDRGtoZqGXIK-vTY1o&showCoverImg=1

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<https://copac.jisc.ac.uk/search?&isn=1584-224x>

ACPN Catalogo Italiano dei Periodici, Università di Bologna

<https://acnpsearch.unibo.it/journal/2601620>

Bibliothèque Nationale de Luxembourg

https://a-z.lu/primo-explore/fulldisplay?vid=BIBNET&docid=SFX_LOCAL1000000000726583&context=L

National Library of Sweden

<http://libris.kb.se/bib/11702473>

Harold B. Lee Library, Brigham Young University

http://sfx.lib.byu.edu/sfxlcl3?url_ver=Z39.88-2004&url_ctx_fmt=info:ofi/fmt:kev:mtx:ctx&ctx_enc=info:ofi/enc:UTF-8&ctx_ver=Z39.88-2004&rft_id=info:sid/sfxit.com:azlist&sfx.ignore_date_threshold=1&rft.object_id=1000000000726583&rft.object_portfolio_id=&svc.holdings=yes&svc.fulltext=yes

Catalogue of Hamburg Libraries

https://beluga.sub.uni-hamburg.de/vufind/Search/Results?submit=Suchen&library=GBV_ILN22&lookfor=1584-224x

Edith Cowan Australia

<https://ecu.on.worldcat.org/search?databaseList=&queryString=1584-224X>

University College Cork, Ireland

<https://ucc.summon.serialssolutions.com/?q=1584-224X#!/search?ho=t&jt=Revista%20de%20Stiinte%20Politice&l=en-UK&q=>

York University Library, Toronto, Ontario, Canada

<https://www.library.yorku.ca/find/Record/muler82857>

The University of Chicago, USA

https://catalog.lib.uchicago.edu/vufind/Record/sfx_1000000000726583

The University of Kansas KUMC Libraries Catalogue

<http://voyagercatalog.kumc.edu/Search/Results?lookfor=1584-224X&type=AllFields>

Journal Seek

<http://journalseek.net/cgi-bin/journalseek/journalsearch.cgi?field=issn&query=1584-224X>

State Library New South Wales, Sidney, Australia,

<http://library.sl.nsw.gov.au/search~S1/?searchtype=i&searcharg=1584-224X&searchscope=1&SORT=D&extended=0&SUBMIT=Search&sea>

[rchlimits=&searchorigarg=i1583-9583](#)

Electronic Journal Library

https://opac.giga-hamburg.de/ezb/detail.phtml?bibid=GIGA&colors=7&lang=en&flavour=classic&jour_id=111736

Open University Malaysia

<http://library.oum.edu.my/oumlib/content/catalog/778733>

Wayne State University Libraries

<http://elibrary.wayne.edu/record=4203588>

Kun Shan University Library

http://muse.lib.ksu.edu.tw:8080/1cate/?rft_val_fmt=publisher&pubid=ucvpress

Western Theological Seminar

https://col-westernsem.primo.exlibrisgroup.com/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma991001225541104770&context=L&vid=01COL_WTS:WTS&lang=en&search_scope=MyInst_and_CI&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine&tab=Everything&query=any,contains,1584-224X&facet=rtype,include,journals&mode=Basic&offset=0

Swansea University Prifysgol Abertawe

http://whel-primo.hosted.exlibrisgroup.com/primo_library/libweb/action/search.do?vid=44WHELFW_SWA_VU1&reset_config=true#.VSU9SPmsVSk

Vanderbilt Library

https://catalog.library.vanderbilt.edu/discovery/fulldisplay?docid=alma991043322926803276&context=L&vid=01VAN_INST:vanui&lang=en&search_scope=MyInst_and_CI&adaptor=Local%20Search%20Engine&tab=Everything&query=any,contains,1584-224X&offset=0

Wissenschaftszentrum Berlin für Sozial

https://www.wzb.eu/en/literature-data/search-find/e-journals?page=searchres.phtml&bibid=WZB&lang=en&jq_type1=IS&j

q_term1=1584-
224X&jq bool2=AND&jq type2=KS&jq term2=&jq bool3=AND&jq
type3=PU&jq term3=&offset=-
1&hits_per_page=50&Notations%5B%5D=all&selected_colors%5B%5
D=1&selected_colors%5B%5D=2

Radboud University Nijmegen
<https://zaandam.hosting.ru.nl/oamarket-acc/score?OpenAccess=&InstitutionalDiscounts=&Title=&Issn=1584-224&Publisher=>

Elektronische Zeitschriftenbibliothek EZB (Electronic Journals Library)
http://rzblx1.uni-regensburg.de/ezeit/detail.phtml?bibid=AAAAA&colors=7&lang=de&jour_id=111736

The University of Hong Kong Libraries
https://julac.hosted.exlibrisgroup.com/primo-explore/search?query=any,contains,1584-224x&search_scope=My%20Institution&vid=HKU&facet=rtype,include,journals&mode=Basic&offset=0

Metropolitan University Prague, Czech Republic
<https://s-knihovna.mup.cz/katalog/eng/1.dll?h~=&DD=1&H1=&V1=o&P1=2&H2=&V2=o&P2=3&H3=&V3=z&P3=4&H4=1584-224x&V4=o&P4=33&H5=&V5=z&P5=25>

University of the West Library
<https://uwest.on.worldcat.org/search?queryString=1584-224x&clusterResults=off&stickyFacetsChecked=on#/oclc/875039367>

Elektronische Zeitschriften der Universität zu Köln
<https://www.ub.uni-koeln.de/IPS?SERVICE=METASEARCH&SUBSERVICE=INITSEARCH&VIEW=USB:Simple&LOCATION=USB&SID=IPS3:2d1c5acebc65a3cdc057a9d6c64ce76e&SETCOOKIE=TRUE&COUNT=15&GWT>

IMEOUT=30&HIGHLIGHTING=on&HISTORY=SESSION&START=1&STREAMING=on&URLENCODING=TRUE&QUERY alAL=1584-224x&SERVICEGROUP1.SERVICE.SEARCH_EDS=on&SERVICEGROUP1.SERVICE.SEARCH_KUGJSON=on&SERVICEGROUP1.SERVICE.SEARCH_KUGUSBWEB=on&SERVICEGROUP1.SERVICEGROUP.USB:Default=on

EKP Publications

<https://ckp-invenio.physik.uni-karlsruhe.de/search?ln=en&sc=1&p=1584-224X&f=&action=search&c=Experiments&c=Authorities>

Valley City State University

https://odin-primo.hosted.exlibrisgroup.com/primo-explore/search?query=any,contains,1584-224X&tab=tab1&search_scope=ndv_everything&sortby=rank&vid=ndv&lang=en_US&mode=advanced&offset=0displayMode%3Dfull&displayField=all&pcAvailabilityMode=true

Impact Factor Poland

<http://impactfactor.pl/czasopisma/21722-revista-de-stiinte-politice-revue-des-sciences-politiques>

Universite Laval

http://sfx.bibl.ulaval.ca:9003/sfx_local?url_ver=Z39.88-2004&url_ctx_fmt=info:ofi/fmt:kev:mtx:ctx&ctx_enc=info:ofi/enc:UTF-8&ctx_ver=Z39.88-2004&rft_id=info:sid/sfxit.com:azlist&sfx.ignore_date_threshold=1&rft.object_id=100000000726583&rft.object_portfolio_id=&svc.fulltext=yes

Universität Passau

<https://infoguide.ub.uni-passau.de/InfoGuideClient.upasis/start.do?Query=10%3d%22BV035261002%22>
BSB Bayerische Staatsbibliothek
<https://opacplus.bsb-muenchen.de/metaopac/search?View=default&oclcno=502495838>

Deutsches Museum

<https://opac.deutsches-museum.de/TouchPoint/start.do?Query=1035%3d%22BV035261002%22IN%5b2%5d&View=dmm&Language=de>

Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt

[https://opac.ku.de/TouchPoint/start.do?Branch=3&Language=de&View=thi&Query=35=%22502495838%22+IN+\[2\]](https://opac.ku.de/TouchPoint/start.do?Branch=3&Language=de&View=thi&Query=35=%22502495838%22+IN+[2])

Hochschule Augsburg, Bibliothek

<https://infoguide.hs-augsburg.de/InfoGuideClient.fhasis/start.do?Query=10%3d%22BV035261002%22>

Hochschule Weihenstephan-Triesdorf, Zentralbibliothek

Freising, Germany

<https://ffwtp20.bib-bvb.de/TouchPoint/start.do?Query=1035%3d%22BV035261002%22IN%5b2%5d&View=ffw&Language=de>

OTH- Ostbayerische Technische Hochschule Regensburg,

Hochschulbibliothek

OTHBR, Regensburg, Germany

<https://www.regensburger-katalog.de/TouchPoint/start.do?Query=1035%3d%22BV035261002%22IN%5b2%5d&View=ubr&Language=de>

Staatliche Bibliothek Neuburg/Donau , SBND,

Neuburg/Donau, Germany

<https://opac.swnd.de/InfoGuideClient.sndsis/start.do?Query=10%3d%22BV035261002%22>

Universitätsbibliothek Eichstätt-Ingolstadt, Eichstätt, Germany

[https://opac.ku.de/TouchPoint/start.do?Branch=0&Language=de&View=uei&Query=35=%22502495838%22+IN+\[2\]](https://opac.ku.de/TouchPoint/start.do?Branch=0&Language=de&View=uei&Query=35=%22502495838%22+IN+[2])

Bibliothek der Humboldt-Universität Berlin, Universitätsbibliothek der Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin

Berlin, Germany

https://hu-berlin.hosted.exlibrisgroup.com/prime-explore/search?institution=HUB_UB&vid=hub_ub&search_scope=default_scope&tab=default_tab&query=issn,exact,1584-224X

Hochschulbibliothek Ansbach, Ansbach, Germany

<https://fanoz3.bib-bvb.de/InfoGuideClient.fansis/start.do?Query=10%3d%22BV035261002%22>

Bibliothek der Europa-Universität Viadrina, Frankfurt (Oder)

Frankfurt/Oder, Germany

<https://opac.europa-uni.de/InfoGuideClient.euvsis/start.do?Query=10%3d%22BV035261002%22>

University of California Library Catalog

<https://catalog.library.ucla.edu/vwebv/search?searchCode1=GKEY&searchType=2&searchArg1=ucoclc469823489>

Glasgow Caledonian University

https://discover.gcu.ac.uk/discovery/openurl?institution=44GLCU_INST&vid=44GLCU_INST:44GLCU_VU2&?u.ignore_date_coverage=true&rft.mms_id=991002471123103836

Open University Library Malaysia

<http://library.oum.edu.my/oumlib/content/catalog/778733>

Academic Journals database

<http://journaldatabase.info/journal/issn1584-224X>

University of Zurich Database

<https://www.jdb.uzh.ch/id/eprint/21535/>

California Institute of Technology - Caltech Library

<https://www.library.caltech.edu/eds/detail?db=poh&an=98646324&isbn=1584224X>

Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin

http://kvk.bibliothek.kit.edu/view-title/index.php?katalog=STABI_BERLIN&url=http%3A%2F%2Fstabilitat.de%2FDB%3D1%2FCHARSET%3DISO-8859-1%2FIMPLAND%3DY%2FLNG%3DDU%2FSRT%3DYOP%2FTTL%3D1%2FSID%3D8dda05f3-1%2FSET%3D1%2FSHW%3FFRST%3D1&signature=eBtSKEx2BuW-HASpUsCT39FB3vQpIm6cGAajCH-kz44&showCoverImg=1

Zeitschriften Datenbank

<http://kvk.bibliothek.kit.edu/view-title/index.php?katalog=ZDB&url=https%3A%2F%2Fzdb-katalog.de%2Flist.xhtml%3Fkey%3DZDB%26t%3D2474973-4&signature=yssL7XoiGNdwpFbIOWTWkl7lz-Abc8CSz0Ddwnbr0Y&showCoverImg=1>

Union Catalogue of Belgian Libraries

http://kvk.bibliothek.kit.edu/view-title/index.php?katalog=VERBUND_BELGIEN&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.unicat.be%2FuniCat%3Ffunc%3Dsearch%26query%3Dsysid%3A7330250&signature=Dxe-cVFWjMO1W4HpEAWW_ERyKR4oiGWXLGFinWk8fNU&showCoverImg=1

The National Library of Israel

http://merhav.nli.org.il/primο-explore/fulldisplay?vid=ULI&docid=NNL-Journals003477656&context=L&lang=en_US

Verbundkatalog GBV

http://kvk.bibliothek.kit.edu/view-title/index.php?katalog=GBV&url=http%3A%2F%2Fgso.gbv.de%2FDB%3D2.1%2FCHARSET%3DUTF-8%2FIMPLAND%3DY%2FLNG%3DDU%2FSRT%3DYOP%2FTTL%3D1%2FCOOKIE%3DD2.1%2CE900d94f2-d%2CI0%2CB9000%2B%2B%2B%2B%2B%2B%2B%2CSY%2CA%2CH6-11%2C%2C16-17%2C%2C21%2C%2C30%2C%2C50%2C%2C60-61%2C%2C73-75%2C%2C77%2C%2C88-90%2CNKVK%2BWEBZUGANG%2CR129.13.130.211%2CFN%2FSET%3D1%2FPPNSET%3FPPN%3D590280090&signature=Omwa_NLtvvdaOmmyeo7SUOCEYuDRTGtoZqGXIK-vTY1o&showCoverImg=1

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<https://acnpsearch.unibo.it/journal/2601620>

Bibliothèque Nationale de Luxembourg

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[https://a-z.lu/primosexplore/fulldisplay?vid=BIBNET&docid=SFX_LOCAL1000000000726583](https://a-z.lu/primosexplore/fulldisplay?vid=BIBNET&docid=SFX_LOCAL1000000000726583&context=L)

National Library of Sweden

<http://libris.kb.se/bib/11702473>

16TH International Conference AFTER COMMUNISM. EAST AND WEST UNDER SCRUTINY, 20-21 March 2026, Craiova, Romania (Conference participation statistics)

- ✓ more than 140 applications accepted;
- ✓ more than 140 participants;
- ✓ senior researchers, academics, and professionals from 9 participating countries:
26 faculties, research centers, doctoral schools and institutes from 11 countries participate in the 16th CEPOS International Conference (March 2026)

Participating institutions include:

- University of Craiova, Romania
- Sorbonne Université – CEFRES, Paris, France
- Metropolitan University Prague, Prague, Czech Republic
- Faculty of Medicine, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic
- University of Bucharest – Doctoral School of Philosophy, Bucharest, Romania
- University of Bucharest – Faculty of Geography, Bucharest, Romania
- Faculty of Political Science, University of Bucharest, Romania
- Faculty of Journalism and Communication Studies, University of Bucharest, Romania
- Ovidius University of Constanța – Faculty of History and Political Science, Constanța, Romania
- “Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, Romania
- National University of Political Studies and Public Administration (SNSPA), Romania
- South East European University, North Macedonia

- 🇷🇴 West University of Timișoara, Romania
- 🇷🇴 Institute of Political Science and International Relations “Ion I. C. Brătianu”, Romanian Academy, Bucharest, Romania
- 🇷🇴 University of Petroșani, Romania
- 🇷🇴 Andrei Șaguna University of Constanța, Romania
- 🇷🇴 “C.S. Nicolăescu-Plopșor” Institute for Research in Social Studies and Humanities, Romanian Academy, Craiova, Romania
- 🇵🇱 University of Lodz, Poland
- 🇨🇷 University of Zadar, Croatia
- 🇷🇴 Black Sea House Constanța, Romania
- 🇹🇷 Dokuz Eylül University – Faculty of Fine Arts, Turkey
- 🇹🇷 Kütahya Dumlupınar University – Faculty of Fine Arts, Kütahya, Turkey
- 🇮🇳 Department of Commerce and Management, Purnea University, Purnea, Bihar, India
- 🇮🇳 Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India
- 🇮🇶 University of Thi-Qar – College of Law, Department of Private Law, Al-Nassiriyah, Iraq
- 🇮🇳 Department of Commerce, Darshan Sah College (Under Purnea University), India

- ✓ proposed researchers' panels and workshops: <https://cepos.eu/upcoming>. Last editions: <https://cepos.eu/past>
- ✓ Members of Organizing and Scientific Committees from 6 countries.
- ✓ Conference international indexing in 11 international databases and services

- ✓ **9 participating countries – in chronological order of application submission:**
 - **Romania**
 - **France**
 - **Czech Republic**
 - **Poland**
 - **Croatia**
 - **Turkey**
 - **North Macedonia**
 - **India**
 - **Iraq**

- ✓ 18 panel sessions and student workshop.

The poster features a background image of a cityscape with a prominent domed building. At the top, the text '16th EDITION' is displayed in a serif font, with 'EDITION' in red. To the right is the CEPOS logo, consisting of two overlapping shapes (one red, one orange) above the word 'CEPOS' in red. The main title 'CEPOS' is in a large, bold, blue serif font, followed by 'AFTER COMMUNISM. EAST AND WEST UNDER SCRUTINY' in red. Below this, the text 'International Academic Conference' is in a smaller, italicized font. The dates '20 – 21 March 2026' and the location 'House of the University Craiova, Romania' are centered. The organizers are listed as 'Association Centre of Post-Communist Political Studies Craiova, Romania' and 'University of Craiova • Faculty of Social Sciences'. Two QR codes are positioned at the bottom left and right. The bottom of the poster has a dark blue banner with the text 'Physical & Virtual Attendance' in white.

16th
EDITION

CEPOS

CEPOS
AFTER COMMUNISM.
EAST AND WEST UNDER SCRUTINY

International Academic Conference

20 – 21 March 2026
House of the University
Craiova, Romania

Organized by
Association Centre of Post-Communist Political Studies
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16th

E D I T I O N

CEPOS
AFTER COMMUNISM.
EAST AND WEST UNDER SCRUTINY

International Academic Conference

20 – 21 March 2026

House of the University

Craiova, Romania

Programme Overview

Organised by

Association Center of Post-Communist Political Studies Craiova, Romania

In collaboration with

University of Craiova • Faculty of Social Sciences

W E L C O M E

We are delighted to welcome you to the 16th edition of CEPOS, an international academic forum dedicated to the critical examination of post-communist societies in East and West. This two-day conference brings together scholars, researchers and practitioners to share findings, debate ideas, and foster scholarly exchange.

CEPOS Conference 2026 Event & Resources

VENUE	House of the University, Craiova
CEPOS 2027	Next CEPOS 17th Conference 12-13 March 2027! https://cepos.org/ , https://www.cepos.eu/
WEB	cepos.eu cepos2023@gmail.com
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/Center-of-Post-Communist-Political-Studies-CEPOS-485957361454074/
Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/center_cepos/
Twitter	Center CEPOS (@center_cepos): https://twitter.com/center_cepos
Linktr	https://linktr.ee/center_cepos
LANG	English (official conference language)
RSP	<i>Cite RSP! Citează RSP!</i> http://cis01.central.ucv.ro/revistadestiintepolitice/ <i>RSP Google Scholar Hindex available at</i> https://scholar.google.ro/citations?user=geaF_FgAAAAJ&hl=ro
CONTACTS	Other contact updates: Email: contact@cepos.org , cepos2023@gmail.com
CONFERENCE ZOOM LINK	CEPOS is inviting you to a scheduled Zoom meeting. Topic: CEPOS Conference 2026 Time: Mar 20, 2026 01:45 PM Bucharest Every day, 2 occurrences Please download and import the following iCalendar (.ics) files to your calendar system. Daily: https://us06web.zoom.us/meeting/tZUvcemspzwwHdyMj-cTt_gcHhH4g0WE2D7j/ics?icsToken=DEHOcM_1qTTHM6Pg5QAALA AAAOAeEmwROpgMdhG8051pu8V9s1YckazUSG2tSYbtenTeJZS7V9c4v355F6gu2tbsq1usFr7aTbslJD-XCzAwMDAwMQ&meetingMasterEventId=un4RKPcdTkezRDpCpaFM2g Join Zoom Meeting https://us06web.zoom.us/j/81260497478?pwd=sWolYplQkZBvmmMMBqmKfE7zYTnhWW.1 Meeting ID: 812 6049 7478 Passcode: 080787 Join instructions https://us06web.zoom.us/join/81260497478/invitations?signature=QWDbbvRq3oqbpQe36Rq3GxIB5OYXrMVd5L48LkH6Zko

DAY 1 — FRIDAY, 20 MARCH 2026

Opening Ceremony • Plenary Sessions • Panel Discussions

10:00 *Registration & Coffee*

**10:30 Opening Ceremony & Welcome Addresses
CEPOS Staff- Keynote Address**

Anca Parmena Olimid, Cătălina Maria Georgescu, Cosmin Lucian Gherge, New Frontiers in Political Science Research: Concepts, Methods and Global Contexts

■ **Parallel Sessions A (11:00 – 12:30)**

11:00 Panel A1: Democratic Transitions and Consolidation

Chair: Andrzej Dubicki, Stanislaw Kosmyнка, Rafał Jung
Hybrid Session

Andrzej Dubicki, Uniwersytet Łódzki/WSMiP, Łódź, Poland

The issue of teaching Polish in diaspora regarding the political and historical background

Stanislaw Kosmyнка, Faculty of International and Political Studies, University of Lodz, Poland

Emotions in Politics: The Anti-Immigrant Discourse of the Radical Right Vox Party in Spain

Rafał Jung, University of Łódź, Political Theory and Political Thought (Sports Policy Research Group), Faculty of International and Political Studies, Łódź, Poland

Olympic Peace Made in Russia: The Soviet Union and the Russian Federation in the Olympic Movement

Dumitru-Cătălin Vasile, National School of Political and Administrative Studies, Bucharest, Romania

The Impact of AI-Generated Content on Political Discourse in Post-Communist Societies

11:00 Panel A2: Visual Politics: An Interdisciplinary Approach

Chair: Marian Zidaru, Daniela Naidin
Hybrid Session

Marian Zidaru, Black Sea House Constanța, Romania

Stoica Lascu, Academy of Romanian Scientists, Romania

Data on SD Activity in Romania Resulting from the SOE Investigation of Jacob Lindermann

Daniela Naidin, University of Craiova, Faculty of Letters, Romania
Artificial Intelligence and the Reconfiguration of History Learning: An Interdisciplinary Analysis from the Perspective of Educational Sciences and Behavioral Anthropology

Tudora Crăciun, University of Bucharest/The Doctoral School of Philosophy, Bucharest, Romania
Art and Democracy. The Body in Post-Communist Art

Florin Nacu, Institute for Research in Social Sciences and Humanities, Craiova, Romania
Oltenia - the image of a post-communist evolution

Stoica Lascu, Academy of Romanian Scientists, Romania
Marian Zidaru, Black Sea House Constanța, Romania
The Cairo Negotiations in SOE. Documents from Spring and Summer 1944

12:30 Lunch Break Restaurant of the House of University - Ground Floor

■ **Parallel Sessions B (14:00 – 15:15)**

14:00 **Panel B1: Institutional Responsibility and Political Polarization**

Chair: Jan Bureš, Ladislav Cabada
Hybrid Session

Jan Bureš, Metropolitan University Prague, Prague, Czech Republic
The role of parliament in the communist coup in Czechoslovakia in 1948

Ladislav Cabada, Metropolitan University Prague, Prague, Czech Republic
(Dis)trust in Political Institutions and Long-term Polarising Trends in Europe

Tereza Bazgierová, Faculty of Medicine, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic
Responsibility as a Lost Value: Bioethical Consequences of Ideological Polarization

14:00 Panel B2: Governance, Democracy and Political Ideologies: Civic Engagement and Inclusion

Chair: **Tereza Bazgierová**, Marija Martinović, Barbara Węglarz

Hybrid Session

Marija Martinović, Sorbonne Université – CEFRES, Paris, France
Paradoxes of Socialist Ideology in Yugoslavia: Coca-Cola Socialism as a Diplomatic Strategy?

Barbara Węglarz, University of the National Education Commission in Krakow, Poland

Joanna Lampa

Andrzej Frycz, Modrzewski University in Krakow, Poland
Krakow's participatory school budget as an example of civic education

Kacso-Carstocea Matei, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration (SNSPA), Bucharest, Romania

Lucian Claudiu Anghel, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration (SNSPA), Bucharest, Romania
Post-Crisis Governance and Bank Risk-Taking in Europe

Diana-Maria Grosu, "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași, Romania

Digital governance in education: between the promise of inclusion and the risk of exclusion

14:00 Panel B3: Environmental Governance, Social Movements and International Law in the Digital Age

Chair: Daniel Ghiță, Adrian-Barbu Ilie, Livia Călin, Matei Diaconu, Simina Badea

Hybrid Session

Daniel Ghiță, Faculty of Law, University of Craiova, Romania

Defense strategies in civil proceedings

Adrian-Barbu Ilie, Faculty of Law, University of Craiova, Romania
Managerial Myopia and Sustainable Urban Governance: Legal Perspectives on Environmental Protection in Romanian Local Administration

Livia Călin, University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Romania

Between self-determination and terrorism: the legal qualification of the actions of national liberation movements in contemporary international law

Matei Diaconu, Faculty of Law, University of Craiova, Romania
The importance of the promise to sell in the context of the development of the real estate market in Romania

Diana-Maria Grosu, "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași, Romania
Global models of digital governance and their adaptation in Romania: International lessons and implementation pathways

Florentina-Cristina Merciu
University of Bucharest, Faculty of Geography, Bucharest, Romania

Bogdan Suditu
University of Bucharest, Faculty of Geography, Bucharest, Romania

George-Laurențiu Merciu
University of Bucharest, Faculty of Geography, Bucharest, Romania
Urban space and collective memory: the role of commemorative monuments built after 1990 in the Municipality of Bucharest

Laetitia Casangiu, Independent Researcher, Constanța, Romania
Food and Politics: State Food Controls in Totalitarian Regimes

Simina Badea, Faculty of Law, University of Craiova, Romania
Lexicalised or Dead Metaphor and Metonymy in the Specialised Language of Law

Diana-Maria Grosu, "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași, Romania

Ioan-Sebastian Buduroi, "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași, Romania

Victor Stoica, "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași, Romania
Digital governance in education: between the promise of inclusion and the risk of exclusion

14:00

Panel B4: Public Policies, Governance and Social Resilience: AI, Education, Professional Development and Sociological Perspectives

Chair: Gabriela Motoi, Alexandrina-Mihaela Popescu, Veronica Gheorghită, Viorel Ghenea

Hybrid Session

Gabriela Motoi, University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Alexandrina-Mihaela Popescu, University of Craiova, Department of Teacher Training, Romania

Gender Equality in Research: A Sociological Analysis of European Statistics and Public Policies

Emilia-Maria Sorescu, University of Craiova, Romania

Structural Violence, Occupational Stress, and Trauma-Informed Policy in Helping Professions

Alexandrina-Mihaela Popescu, University of Craiova, Department of Teacher Training, Romania

Gabriela Motoi, University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Understanding Continuous Professional Development Needs among Teachers in Vocational and Technical Education: Evidence from a Sociological Study

Valentina Marinescu, University of Bucharest, Romania

Teodor Dumitrache, University of Bucharest, Romania

From Spells to Code: Comparing Medical Authority in Medieval Romania and the Age of AI

Gabriela Motoi, University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Mihaela Alexandrina Popescu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Educational Vulnerabilities and School Participation among Vocational and Lower Secondary Students: A Sociological Needs Assessment in Dolj County, Romania

Roxana Pleșa, University of Petroșani, Petroșani, Romania
Artificial Intelligence vs. Human Factor in Applied Behavior Analysis: A Comparative Analysis for Future Integration in Behavioral Sciences

Valentina Marinescu, University of Bucharest, Romania
Teodor Dumitrache, University of Bucharest, Romania
Comprehension and Retention in Print, Digital, and AI-Mediated Reading: A Scoping Review

14:00 **Panel B5: Resilience, Youth Careers and Policy Strategies in the Information Age**

Chair: Andreea Mihaela Niță, Mihaela Pârvu, Emilia Sorescu
Hybrid Session

Mihaela-Cristina Pârvu, University of Craiova, Romania
Andreea-Mihaela Niță, University of Craiova, Romania
From Vulnerability to Resilience: Developing Emotional Resilience in Children at Risk

Cătălina Maria Georgescu, University of Craiova, Romania
Silviu Dorin Georgescu, Independent Researcher, Craiova, Romania
Rethinking Educational Policies to counteract Social Media Dependence: Grit and Self-Efficacy as Protective Factors for Youth

Andreea-Mihaela Niță, University of Craiova, Romania
Pârvu Mihaela-Cristina, University of Craiova, Romania
Navigating the AI Labour Market: Career Guidance Strategies for Romanian Youth

Otilia Maria Trașcă, University of Craiova, “Eugeniu Carada”
Doctoral School of Economics Sciences, Romania
The Always-On Culture: Expectations for Work Communication Beyond Working Hours

Cătălina Maria Georgescu, University of Craiova, Romania
Silviu Dorin Georgescu, Independent Researcher, Craiova, Romania
Comparative Analysis of National Security Strategies: Policy Formation, Institutional Actors, and Instruments of National Power

Irina Janina Boncea, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania
Pragmatic Aspects of Irrealis Tools in the Language of Information Technology

14:00

Panel B6: AI, Finances, banking & digital market

Chair: Ramona Pârnu, Ramona Birau

Hybrid Session

Saidalavi K, Department of Management and Commerce, MANUU, Hyderabad, Telangana, India

Rasheed K, Department of Management, Aliah University, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

Virgil Popescu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania,

Ramona Birau, University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania,

Roxana-Mihaela Nioata (Chireac), University of Craiova, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences "Eugeniu Carada", Craiova, Romania

Investigating the Impact of e-Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction by Examining the Trends in Consumer Behavior towards Quick Commerce (Q-commerce)

Ramona Costina Pîrvu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

Constantina Alina Ciurilă (Tapi), University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

Economic and Sociological Theories on the Impact of Technology on Labor: Toward an Institutional Task-Mediation Framework

Lucian-Florin Spulbăr, University of Craiova, Doctoral School of Economics Sciences „Eugeniu Carada”, Romania

The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on the Quality and Transparency of Corporate Reporting

Daniel-Marius Mitrache, University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Romania

Management challenges in the internationalization of Romanian SMEs

Lavinia-Adelina Mitrache, University of Craiova, Romania
The Impact of the War in Ukraine on Sustainable Development and Global Economic Resilience

Cezar-Cătălin Ene, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania
Assessing the Impact of Financial Risk on Organizations by Modelling the Unemployment Rate Using the Arima Model

Daniel-Marius Mitrache, University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Romania

The Impact of PropTech Technologies on Office Building Management Efficiency

14:00

Panel B7: Economic Resilience in Global Development: Trade Exchange and ESG Policies

Chair: Narcis Mitu, Cristian Stanciu

Hybrid Session

George Teodor Mitu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

Narcis Eduard Mitu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

Mihaela Zglavoci, University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

ESG and Economic Resilience in the EU: Evidence from Macro Indicators

Lucian-Florin Spulbăr, University of Craiova,

Doctoral School of Economics Sciences „Eugeniu Carada”, Romania

Reconfiguring Corporate Governance under the Impact of Hybrid and Conventional Wars

George Teodor Mitu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

Narcis Eduard Mitu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

Mihaela Zglavoci, University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

From PISA to Prosperity: How Education Quality Is Associated with Economic Development in the EU-27 (2018, 2022)

Andrei Cristian Spulbar

University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration Craiova, Romania

Cristian Valeriu Stanciu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration Craiova, Romania

FinTech and the integration of financial markets and institutions: mapping research frontiers and impact pathways

Andrei Cristian Spulbar

University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration Craiova, Romania

Cristian Valeriu Stanciu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration Craiova, Romania

FinTech and financial stability: risk channels, resilience, and regulatory trade-offs

Lavinia-Adelina Mitrache, University of Craiova, Romania

Quality education as a determinant of progress towards the Sustainable Development Goals

Eugen Stanciu, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, University of Craiova, Romania

Cristian Valeriu Stanciu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration Craiova, Romania

Blockchain Exchange Design and Trading Instruments: A Conceptual Framework for Centralized and Decentralized Markets

Daniela Iulia Maria Carbune, University of Craiova, Romania

Macroeconomic Determinants of Bank Profitability. Research Trends and Future Perspectives in the Era of Artificial Intelligence

Cristian Valeriu Stanciu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration Craiova, Romania

Eugen Stanciu, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, University of Craiova, Romania

The Digital Assets Landscape: A Bibliometric Analysis of Intra-Market Linkages

Andrei Smărăndescu, University of Craiova, Doctoral School of Economics Sciences "Eugeniu Carada"

The Evolution of ESG Integrated Lending: Implications for Credit Allocation and Underserved Populations

15:15

Coffee Break & Networking

■ **Parallel Sessions C (15:30 – 16:30)**

15:30 Panel C1: Law, constitutionalism and the rule of law in contemporary political systems

Chair: Dan Claudiu Dănișor, Mădălina Dănișor, George Gîrleşteanu, Mădălina Nica

Hybrid Session

Dan Claudiu Dănișor, University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Department of Public Law, Romania,

Mădălina Cristina Dănișor, University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Department of Public Law, Romania,

George Liviu Gîrleşteanu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Department of Public Law, Romania,

Elena Mădălina Nica, University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Department of Public Law, Romania,

Vertical separation of power – a means of guaranteeing freedom in states governed by the rule of law

George Liviu Gîrleşteanu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Department of Public Law, Romania

Rule of law standards

George Liviu Gîrleşteanu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Department of Public Law, Romania

Iohan-Andrei Ghibu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Department of Public Law, Romania

Emergency Powers and The Rule of Law: Theoretical Reflections and Legal Realities

Cosmin Lucian Gherghe, University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Craiova, Romania

A Comparative Analysis of the Legal Status of Political Parties in European Democracies

15:30 Panel C2: Governance and institutional transformation in democratic societies: public administration, accountability and policy frameworks

Chair: Oana Stăiculescu, Gabi-Daniela Găraïman, Cristina Stanciu, Roberta Ploscă, Armand Mihail Calotă

Hybrid Session

Cristina Stanciu, University of Craiova, Law Faculty, Romania
The shipping contract as a hybrid of commission and transport

Oana Stăiculescu, University of Craiova, Romania

Gabi-Daniela Găraïman, University of Craiova, Romania
Decision Rights and Accountability in Government AI

Roberta Ploscă, University of Craiova, Law Faculty, Craiova, Romania

The value of morality in the system of legal science and in the enhancement of social relations

Armand Mihail Calotă, University of Craiova, Romania

Legal perspectives on the regulation of artificial intelligence systems and the protection of the stability of employment relationships

Cristina Stanciu, Faculty of Law, University of Craiova, Romania
Legal protection in civil law and transport law

Oana Stăiculescu, University of Craiova, Romania

Veronica Gheorghită, University of Craiova, Romania
The Informational Ecology of Public Data in Romania

Armand Mihail Calotă, University of Craiova, Romania

The legal challenges of artificial intelligence in data and consumer law

Cosmin Lucian Gherghe, University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Assessing the Political and Legal Implications of the UN Security Council Resolutions in Supporting Justice Mechanisms in Conflict Zones

15:30 Panel C3: AI, Human Development and Societal Security: Policy, Health, and Law

Chair: Anca Parmena Olimid, Cătălina Maria Georgescu, Cosmin Gherghe

Hybrid Session

Anca Parmena Olimid, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Daniel Alin Olimid, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Digital Public Services and Human Development in the AI Era: A Citizen-Based Anticipatory Governance, Security Policy and Information Approach

Daniel Alin Olimid, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Anca Parmena Olimid, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Demographic Change, Social Cohesion and Human Development Sustainability and Security: Health Policy Innovation and Regulatory Sandboxes

Aman Shreevastava, P.G. Department of Commerce and Management, Purnea University, Purnea, Bihar, India-854301

Shahil Raza, Department of Commerce, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh 202001, India

Bharat Kumar Meher, P.G. Department of Commerce and Management, Purnea University, Purnea, Bihar, India-854301

Ramona Birau, Finance and Accounting Department, "Constantin Brâncuși" University of Târgu Jiu, Faculty of Economic Science, Tg-Jiu, Romania & University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

Virgil Popescu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

Ștefan Mărgăritescu, University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania, Email:

Md. Wahiduz Zama, Department of Commerce, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh 202001, India

The Superiority of Asymmetric Volatility Models: An Empirical Comparison of GARCH-Family Specifications for the Volatility of MSCI Mexico Index

Ramona Birău, University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Virgil Popescu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

Understanding colors in finance - The impact of Green, Blue and Black Finances on sustainable economic growth

Cătălina Maria Georgescu, *University of Craiova, Romania*

Anca Parmena Olimid, *University of Craiova, Romania*

Daniel Alin Olimid, *University of Craiova, Romania*

Silviu Dorin Georgescu, *Independent Researcher, Craiova, Romania*

Cosmin Lucian Gherghe, *University of Craiova, Romania*

Assessing the Correlations between Socioeconomic Development and Sustainable Policy Outcomes: A Multidimensional Analysis of Health, Education, Equality, Employment, Security and Climate Resilience

Maria-Mădălina Bulancia, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iași, Faculty of Philosophy and Social-political Sciences, Romania

Legitimizing the „peaceful rise” of the People's Republic of China. A Conceptual Analysis of Official Chinese Discourses and Trends in Academic Publication

Lucian Bălănuță, University Alexandru Ioan Cuza Iași – Faculty of Letters – specialization Journalism and Communications Sciences
Transactional Realism - recasting power as bargain. The diplomatic strategy of the United States in relation with the Russia-Ukraine war

16:30

Social & Cultural Programme

City Tour Craiova

Guided visit of the historic city centre

Craiova Pastry & Chocolate Tour

Visit to Mihai Viteazul Square and Prefecture Square

Walk through English Park and University area

Local culture and heritage presentation

Networking walk & informal discussions

■ **Parallel Sessions D (18:00 – 19:00)**

18:00

Panel D1: Political culture, values and language skills

Chair: Floriana Anca Păunescu, Ileana Mihaela Chirițescu, Laviniu Costinel Lăpădat, Maria-Magdalena Lăpădat, Elena Olivia Bălănescu

Hybrid Session

Ileana Mihaela Chirițescu, University of Craiova, Romania

Floriana Anca Păunescu, University of Craiova, Romania

Communication Mediated by Digital Means

Adrian-Florin Bușu, University of Craiova, Romania

Natural Language Processing as an Integrated Model of AI-Mediated Pedagogy

Floriana Anca Păunescu, University of Craiova, Romania

Ileana Mihaela Chirițescu, University of Craiova, Romania

Clarity, Coherence, and Communication: The Case for Standardized Administrative Language

LavinIU Costinel Lăpădat, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Energy Output and (De)industrialisation: Redefining the Socio-Economic and Cultural Fabric of the World's Three Major Blocs (EU, US and China)

Maria-Magdalena Lăpădat, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Specialized Vocabulary and Academic Communication Skills in English for Psychology: An ESP-Based Approach

Cristina-Gabriela Marin, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Loredana Ispas, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Biblical Idioms Used in Travel-Related Contexts

LavinIU Costinel Lăpădat, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Integrating Romanian Culture and Civilisation in Language Instruction for Foreign Students)

Diana Marcu, University of Craiova, Romania

The Integration of AI into the Lives of Engineering Students: A Case Study

Bălănescu Eleonora Olivia, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Reading Beyond the Text: The Role of Critical Literacy Skills in English Language Education

Laviniu Costinel Lăpădat, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Maria-Magdalena Lăpădat, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

The AI Revolution: Friend or Foe in Higher Education and the Subsequent Job Market Integration

Maria-Magdalena Lăpădat, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Classical Legacy vs. Modern Dissemination in Teaching English for Psychology Students: From Freud and Jung to Jordan Peterson

18:00

Panel D2: Media Writing, Language and AI-Driven Communication

Chair: Costina Denisa Bărbuceanu, Andreea Mihaela Stoian, Daniela Scorțan
Hybrid Session

Costina Denisa Bărbuceanu, University of Craiova, Romania

Active Learning Strategies for Increasing Student Engagement in English Language Teaching

Cristina-Eugenia Burtea-Cioroianu, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Using Artificial Intelligence in Teaching Romanian as a Foreign Language

Daniela Scorțan, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Immersive experience in teaching

Cristina Maria Andrei, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

The Relevance of Writing Practice

Viorel Ștefan Ghenea, University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Romania

Montaigne on Otherness: The Cannibal as Noble Savage

Andreea Mihaela Stoian, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

The importance of teachers in the educational system

Cristina-Gabriela Marin, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania
Abbreviations Used in Tourism Terminology

Alina Roxana Popa, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania
The Values of the “Succeeder” Psychographic Group as Discernible in The Sunday Times Newspaper Review of a Hotel

Costina Denisa Bărbuceanu, University of Craiova, Romania
From Chalkboard to Chatbots: Integrating AI Tools in the Modern ELT Classroom

Daniela Scorțan, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania
School dropout among students: how to prevent it

18:00

Panel D3: Roundtable Discussion: East–West Dialogue Thirty Years On & CEPOS Research Workshop and Tutorials Series: Security, Governance and Public Policy: Community Engagement and Social Dynamics

All Day-1 Participants — Paper Presentations & Moderated Discussion

Physical Attendance

Anca Parmena Olimid, University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Romania
Citizens-Focused Governance, Security and Digital Information Integrity: An Updated Review of the Evolving Topics and Emergent Metrics

Cătălina Maria Georgescu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Craiova, Romania
Investigating Institutional Image in Security Contexts: An Imagological Framework Combining Press Monitoring and Social Media Analysis

Cosmin Lucian Gherghe, University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Craiova, Romania
Analysing the Legal Framework of Information Security and the Fight Against Disinformation in Romania: The Interaction Between National Security, Cyber Infrastructure, and Democratic Processes

18:00

Panel D4:

STUDENT RESEARCH SESSION: Applied Intelligence Analysis (A2I) Panel & EU POLICIES AND SECURITY (CEPOS Student Project Research, Quiz, Facts, Press and Legal Monitoring, Social Analysis)

CEPOS & Political Sciences specialization, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova - CEPOS 15th international student symposium

Coordinating Professors: Parmena Olimid, Cătălina Georgescu, Cosmin Gherge. Date: launched on December 2025-March 2026

Daniel-Petruț Băsășteanu, MA Political Sciences, National and Euro-Atlantic Security, 1st year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova, Romania

EU cybersecurity strategy 2020–2025

Gabriela-Crina Ciupitu, BA Political Sciences, 2nd year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova, Romania

Countering Disinformation and Hybrid Threats in the European Space

Mirela Gheorghiu, MA Political Sciences, National and Euro-Atlantic Security, 1st year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova, Romania

Strengthening of the common security and defence policy (CSDP). Case study – the Strategic Compass for Security and Defence (2022)

Theodor Gheorghiu, MA Political Sciences, National and Euro-Atlantic Security, 1st year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova, Romania

Cybersecurity resilience: a shield against hybrid threats

Dumitru-Radu Guran, MA Political Sciences, National and Euro-Atlantic Security, 2nd year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova, Romania

The EU–NATO partnership in managing hybrid threats

Maria-Adela Lixandra, MA Political Sciences, National and Euro-Atlantic Security, 1st year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova, Romania

The EU cybersecurity strategy 2020–2025: a framework for digital security

Radu Nicolae Ruxanda, MA Political Sciences, National and Euro-Atlantic Security, 2nd year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova, Romania

EU Security Policy in the Eastern Neighborhood (Republic of Moldova, Ukraine, Georgia)

Alexandru Gabriel Savin, BA Political Sciences, 2nd year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova, Romania

European health security after COVID-19: the role of HERA and ECDC

Robert-Cristian Speriatu-Mirescu, MA Political Sciences, National and Euro-Atlantic Security, 2nd year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova, Romania

Migration and the EU asylum policy

Ana Maria Cornelia Sirbu, MA Political Sciences, National and Euro-Atlantic Security, 1st year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova, Romania

EU security policy in the Mediterranean and the Middle East

Silvestru-Șerban Pâslaru, MA Political Sciences, National and Euro-Atlantic Security, 1st year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova, Romania

EU migration and asylum policies

19: 00 **Gala Dinner & Networking Reception**

20:00 **End of Day 1 Sessions**

DAY 2 — SATURDAY, 21 MARCH 2026

Parallel Sessions • Keynote • Closing Ceremony

■ **Parallel Sessions E (10:00 – 11:00)**

10:00

Panel E1: Geopolitics and Security in Post-Communist Space

Chair: Parmena Olimid, Cătălina Georgescu, Cosmin Gherghe

Hybrid Session

Alexandra-Ștefania Dinulescu, Baku State University, Azerbaijan,

Observing Romania's Role in Regional Natural Gas Transport Systems

Radu Cupcea, Institute of Political Science and International Relations "Ion I. C. Brătianu" of the Romanian Academy

Presidential Advisers in post-communist Romania

Radu Pătrașcu, Faculty of Sociology and Social Work – University of Bucharest, Romania

Public opinion on Russia in Ukraine and Georgia. Comparative Analysis

Valentin Măngiurea, SNSPA - Doctoral School, Management, Bucharest, Romania

Lucian Claudiu Anghel, SNSPA - Bucharest, Romania

Who Controls the Decision? Artificial Intelligence, Algorithmic Control, and Consumer Trust in Banking

Luiza-Maria Filimon, Ovidius University of Constanța, Faculty of History and Political Science, Constanța, Romania

The Crisis of Euroscepticism and the Rise of the Illiberal Parties. A Comparative Analysis of Party Manifestoes from Romania, Poland and Hungary in the Context of National and European Elections

Karina Beatrice Crețu, Faculty of Political Science, University of Bucharest, Romania

Redefining American Conservatism after 2016: Transatlantic Illiberal Currents and the Crisis of Liberalism

Agim Sulejmani, South East European University, North Macedonia

Jonuz Abdullai, South East European University, North Macedonia
Multilateral Parliamentary Cooperation as a Tool for Accelerating Western Balkan Integration into the European Union

10:00 Panel E2: Art, Cultural Heritage and Politics in Contemporary Societies

Chair: Simber Atay, Selma Kozak, Antonia Matei, **Marijana Ražnjević Zdrilić**

Simber Atay, Dokuz Eylül University, Fine Arts Faculty, Photography Department, Izmir, Turkey
Florin Șerban's Cinematic Perspective

Antonia Matei, The Faculty of Journalism and Communication Studies, University of Bucharest, Romania
Reconfiguring Journalistic Roles in Romania: A Longitudinal Analysis Based on the Worlds of Journalism Study (2016 - 2023)

Selma Kozak, Kütahya Dumlupınar University Faculty of Fine Arts, Department of Visual Communication Design, Kütahya, Turkey
Rien ne pousse à l'ombre des grands arbres: Constantin Brâncuși and the Politics of Cultural Heritage

Ivana-Marija Vrsaljko, University of Zadar, Department of Applied Communication Studies, Zadar, Croatia

Marijana Ražnjević Zdrilić, University of Zadar, Department of Applied Communication Studies, Zadar, Croatia
Media and Culture in Croatia in the Post-War Period (1945-1946)

Leonard-Denis Păușan-Barna

West University of Timișoara, Timișoara, Romania
The Romanian Press During the Transition from the Communist to the Post-Communist Period. Case Study: Art, Culture, and Economy

■ **Parallel Sessions F (11:00 – 12:30)**

11:00 Panel F1: AI-Driven Markets and Democratization: Accuracy, Governance and Innovation

Chair: Parmena Ollimid
Hybrid Session

Shahil Raza, Department of Commerce Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh, India

Aman Shreevastava, PG Department of Commerce & Management, Purnea University, Purnia, Bihar, India,

Bharat Kumar Meher, PG Department of Commerce & Management, Purnea University, Purnia, Bihar, India,

Ramona Birau, University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Stefan Margaritescu, University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Gabriela Ana Maria Lupu (Filip), University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada", Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Mircea Laurentiu Simion, University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania
Exploring Japanese stock market volatility using symmetric and asymmetric GARCH models: A case study

P. Vidhya, Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Sharan Kumar Shetty, Department of MBA, AJ Institute of Engineering & Technology – Mangalore, Karnataka, India

N. Devaram, Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Ramona Birau, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences "Eugeniu Carada", University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Virgil Popescu, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

P. Manochithra, Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

M. Devaki, Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Stefan Margaritescu, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences "Eugeniu Carada", University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Roxana-Mihaela Nioata (Chireac), University of Craiova, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences "Eugeniu Carada", Craiova, Romania

D. Renukadevi, Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Algorithmic Hiring and Bias: Evaluating the Accuracy, Fairness, and Ethical Implications of AI-Driven Recruitment Systems

Paula-Simona Gafincu (Ciubotă), Alexandru Ioan Cuza University, Doctoral School of Philosophy and Social-Political Sciences, Romania

Simulation and resistance in the democratization of Romania: Public policy instruments between the normative control of the West and the survival of local elites

Mihai Frunză, Doctoral School of Management, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration (SNSPA), Bucharest, Romania

Lucian Claudiu Anghel, Faculty of Management, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration (SNSPA), Bucharest, Romania

Impact of Energy Price Shocks on the Romanian Electricity Market: An Extended Econometric Analysis Using Local Projections and Error-Correction Modelling

11:00

Panel F2: Digital Humanism and Sustainability: Technologies for the Sustainable Development Goals

Chair: Cătălina Georgescu

Hybrid Session

Aman Shreevastava, Research Scholar, P.G. Dept. of Commerce and Management, Purnea University, Purnea, Bihar-854301, India

Bharat Kumar Meher, Assistant Professor, P.G. Dept. of Commerce and Management, Purnea University, Purnea, Bihar-854301, India

Sunil Kumar, Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Purnea College, Under Purnea University, Purnea, Bihar-854301, India

Ramona Birau, University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania,

Virgil Popescu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania,

Pankaj Kumar, Assistant Professor, P.G. Department of Economics, Purnea University, Purnea, Bihar-854301, India

Stefan Margaritescu, University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania,

Major Financial Scams that Shook Post-Independent India: An Investigative Study for the long term period 1950-2023

P. Vidhya, Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science
Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Sharan Kumar Shetty, Department of MBA, AJ Institute of Engineering & Technology – Mangalore, Karnataka, India

P. Jayasubramanian, Department of Commerce, Dr.N.G.P. Arts & Science College, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India

Ramona Birau, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences” Eugeniu Carada”, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Virgil Popescu, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

N. Devaram, Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

M. Devaki, Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Gabriela Ana Maria Lupu (Filip), University of Craiova, “Eugeniu Carada” Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova

Roxana-Mihaela Nioata (Chireac), University of Craiova, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences ”Eugeniu Carada”, Craiova

D. Renukadevi, Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

P. Manochithra, Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Exploring the Impact of Privacy, Security, and Ethical Considerations on Consumer Trust in E-Commerce

Muhammed Khqairy Qsair, University of Thi-Qar / College of law / Department of private law, ALnassiriy, Thi-Qar, Iraq

The Impact of the Right of Access Principle on Determining the Applicable Law in Cross-Border Insolvency Proceedings: A Comparative Analytical Study

Sarab Thamer Ahmed, University of Thi-Qar / College of law / Department of private law, ALnassiriy, Thi-Qar, Iraq

Digital Humanitarianism and the Principle of Distinction: Protecting Tech-Volunteers under International .Humanitarian Law

D. Renukadevi, Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Sharan Kumar Shetty, Department of MBA, AJ Institute of Engineering & Technology – Mangalore, Karnataka, India

P. Vidhya, Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India Ramona Birau, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences” Eugeniu Carada”, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Virgil Popescu, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

P. Manochithra, Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

M. Devaki, Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

N. Devaram, Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Cristina Sultănoiu (Pătularu), University of Craiova, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences ”Eugeniu Carada”, Craiova, Romania

Ștefan Mărgăritescu, University of Craiova, ”Eugeniu Carada” Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania
Green Technologies and Sustainable Global Business Practices

12:00

General Discussion & Conclusions

All Participants — Chairs of Panels

Hybrid Session

C L O S I N G C E R E M O N Y

12:30

Closing Address & Farewell

Hybrid Session

13:00

End of Conference

Thank you for participating in CEPOS 2026!

We look forward to welcoming you to the 17th edition, 12-13 March 2027

ABSTRACTS

The Relevance of Writing Practice

Cristina Maria Andrei

University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

Is writing practice still necessary in the current world of digitalization? The question is obvious since, whatever message is meant to be transmitted, is subdued to the autocorrect system of any computer software. The word settings are designed to provide the user with possibilities of correction in terms of spelling and grammar as well as replacements of misspelled words. Modern computerized systems detect and provide options which are intended to generate accurate messages at a fast pace. It is thus a constant “struggle” for the English teachers to enhance “writing” in classes and demand students to perform certain tasks connected to it since their tendency is to check it constantly on various devices. Taking into account the above-mentioned aspect, is the writing skill still important to be taught during English classes? Should the teacher focus on it to the same degree as reading, listening and speaking? Is it beneficial to devote time in order to perform writing activities or is it just a waste of time? Are students really involved in improving it when computational intelligence offers them free and immediate support?

Keywords: *Writing, computerized system, English, students*

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Author’s presentation:

I am a Senior Lecturer, PhD at the Department of Applied Modern Languages, University of Craiova. I have been teaching ESP for about 20 years; with a PhD in the area of Humanistic studies, I have published around 30 research papers in specialized national journals and 5 in international ones. I have participated at numerous conferences and I am the author of an English coursebook for the students in Physics and co-author of 3 other coursebooks for Business Students. I was involved in different projects

related to the teaching field and I was an English trainer for various companies. My point of interest is basically focused on research and thus, I am involved in a wide range of scientific activities. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4700-0238>

Florin Șerban's Cinematic Perspective

Simber Atay

Professor Emerita, İzmir, Turkey

Abstract:

Florin Șerban (b. 1975) is an important figure of contemporary cinema, and he won many international awards. The plots of his feature films can be summarized as follows:

If I Want to Whistle, I Will (Eu când vreau să fluier, fluier, 2010) Before his release from juvenile detention, Silviu learns from his brother that their mother has returned home. She has found a job in Italy and wants to take him with her. Then, Silviu struggles to stop his mother.

Box (Box, 2015) Cristina is a theater artist, and Rafael is a young boxer. They are both oppressed and exploited by micro-power representatives, such as the director, husband, or organizer.

Love 1: Dog (2018) (Dragoste 1: Câine, 2018) Simion is a middle-aged man who lives in a mountain cabin with his dog. One day, he finds a wounded young woman in the forest, and over time he falls in love with her.

Love 2. America (Dragoste 2. America, 2020) This movie is about the last twenty-four hours of the love story between Anton and Beatrice.

Hamlet (2024) This film is new experimental adaptation- a horror film- of Shakespeare's Hamlet.

Florin Șerban belongs to the class of philosopher-directors like Alain Resnais, Carlos Reygadas, Terrence Malick, Lav Diaz, or Apichatpong Weerasethakul. This study aims to analyze the films of Florin Șerban mentioned above according to the effects of the Oedipus complex and contemporary paradigms, as well as his political rhetoric.

Keywords: *Florin Șerban, philosopher-director, If I Want to Whistle, I Will (2010), Love 2. America (2020), Oedipus complex.*

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Author's presentation:

Simber Atay is *Professor Emerita, İzmir, Turkey*. ORCID ID: orcid.org/0000-0003-1512-9627

Lexicalised or Dead Metaphor and Metonymy in the Specialised Language of Law

Simina BADEA

Faculty of Law, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

Metaphor is a privileged tool in the process of lexical creation, which finds its utility in various linguistic domains, as well as in specialised languages. The phenomenon of metaphorisation involves the establishment of connections between different things, entities, notions or roles based on similar elements, on certain common qualities. Metaphor in specialised language rests on an equivalence relation and is developed through analogical reasoning in the sphere of mental constructs enabling a process of conceptual abstraction.

Lexicalised metaphor, which is not the same as lexical metaphor, is also called dead/ frozen metaphor in the literature. The name comes from the fact that, due to frequent, repetitive use, this figure of speech has lost not only its vividness and savour, but also its original meaning. Thus, its earlier metaphorical nature has been obscured by overuse and people are no longer aware of this metaphoricality. In legal language, it comes to function as a standard term, encasing abstract legal notions.

Metonymy is another type of figurative language that relies on analogy, but in this case, it is a way of comparing and bringing together concepts, entities or things which do not share similar qualities. A word or term is used as a substitute meant to designate an object or a concept with which it is associated or to which it is somehow related. The purpose of this article is to discuss several dead metaphors and metonymies that pertain to legal language.

Keywords: *lexicalised/ dead metaphor, dead metonymy, specialised language, law*

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Author's presentation:

Assoc. prof. Simina Badea, PhD, teaches legal English at the Faculty of Law, University of Craiova. She has a bachelor's degree in Philology (1998) and Law (2011) and was awarded the PhD title in the field of Philology in 2008. Author of 3 books, 5 coursebooks and numerous articles, she has conducted research in several areas: lexicology, terminology, translation, ESP, cognitive linguistics.

Reading Beyond the Text: The Role of Critical Literacy Skills in English Language Education

Bălănescu Eleonora Olivia

University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

It is well known that words have power, the power to influence people by promoting certain ideas and individual messages meant to shape readers'/ listeners' viewpoints. In this light, language is never neutral, and words always have contextual and subtextual meanings that can be decoded by critical literacy. In our increasingly globalised world, information floods in from all possible sources which are more or less reliable; therefore, we need to be equipped with the right skills to approach a text and read beyond the words in order to understand the writer's cultural and political background, motivation, intention, and overall aim. As globalisation is closely linked to English as the main means of communication around the world, English language teaching have broadened the core competencies in language acquisition to include a number of literacies, such as digital and critical literacies, along with biliteracy and multilingual literacies. The aim of this article is to explore critical literacy in English language education. We shall start by scrutinising the literature on the topic, in order to define the concept, its tenets, benefits and challenges in the classroom. The theoretical presentation is accompanied by practical advice on the strategies and activities that teachers can use in order to develop their students' critical literacy skills.

Keywords: *critical literacy, language acquisition, learning experience, meaning making, power*

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Author's presentation:

Eleonora Olivia Bălănescu, PhD, is Associate Professor at the Faculty of Letters, University of Craiova, where she teaches English for Specific Purposes and Romanian as a foreign language. She has teaching experience in the country and abroad, having worked as Visiting Professor at Delhi University, India, and Charles University, Prague. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-8836-1331

Transactional Realism - recasting power as bargain. The diplomatic strategy of the United States in relation with the Russia-Ukraine war

Lucian Bălănuță

"Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iasi, Faculty of Letters – Journalism and Communication Sciences, Iasi, Romania

Abstract:

This paper highlights features of a possible transactional realism variant, a new mutation of the realism school of international relations, that deals foreign policy as sequences of explicit bargains, encapsulating characteristics such as pricing of commitment, conditional reciprocity, and performative sequencing of deal-making as a replacement option for stable strategies or institutionalized rules. By emphasizing the contractual logic of alliances and the interpretative nature of diplomacy, transactional realism allows a more adequate understanding of the act of governing in contemporary times. Built on recent scholarship on transactionalism, updated versions of realism and Trump-era foreign policy directions as main methodology, this article aims to test the approach on 2025 press-documented statements during the second term of U.S. President Donald Trump, on the topic of the Russia–Ukraine war. Drawing on a corpus of speeches, press releases, Oval Office remarks, leader-summit readouts and transcripts, I underlined these new signals of a broader transformation of global order and how they govern the way policymakers frame security guarantees, territorial concessions and alliance burden-sharing. Transactional practices deserve theorization, mainly through an attachment to realism, due to the fact that it explains the form, the content and the timing of policy. Although rich in theoretical propositions, this mutation may present a series of policy risks when we speak about a deals-based order, where market logics cannot be fully integrated into high politics.

Keywords: *transactional, realism, Trump, international relations*

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Author's presentation:

Lecturer, PhD, "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iasi, Faculty of Letters – Journalism and Communication Sciences, Iasi, Romania. Publications: Bălănuță, L. (2018). *State-Society Relations and The Israeli-Palestinian Conflict*, în volumul EIRP Proceedings al Conferinței International Conference on European Integration - Realities and Perspectives vol. 13, 2018, Print ISSN: 2067 – 9211, Online ISSN: 2069 –9344, pp. 242-249; (indexat BDI). Bălănuță, L. (2019). *Egyptian revolution through social media*, International Journal of Communication Research, vol. 9, issue 1, January / March 2019, ISSN: 2246-9265, pp. 7-11; (indexat BDI). Bălănuță, L. (2019). *Media websites and online browsing. A study case – Radio România Iași*, International Journal of Communication Research, vol. 9, issue 1, January / March 2019, ISSN: 2246-9265, pp. 38-43; (indexat BDI). Bălănuță, L. (2019). *The language of euroscepticism: Study case – Margareth Thatcher and her Bruges speech from 1988*, International Journal of Communication Research, vol. 9, issue 3, June/September 2019, ISSN: 2246-9265, pp. 199-203; (indexat BDI). Bălănuță, L. (2021). *Podcast – towards an inclusive definition*, în volumul Acta Universitatis Danubius. Communicatio vol. 15, Nr. 2, 2021, Print ISSN: 1844-7562, Online ISSN: 2069 – 0398, pp. 31-41 (indexat BDI). Balanuta, L. (2022). *Framing Food Security in the EU*, în Logos Universality Mentality Education Novelty: Political Sciences & European Studies, 7(1), 46-71, 2022, Print ISSN:2284-5968, e-ISSN:2501-0417, pp. 46-71, <https://doi.org/10.18662/lumenpses/7.1/30> (indexat BDI)

From Chalkboard to Chatbots: Integrating AI Tools in the Modern ELT Classroom

Costina Denisa Bărbuceanu
University of Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

Generative AI is changing how we teach and learn English since the old methods are vanishing, and more students turn to AI tools for help with their studies. This shift gives teachers a real challenge: how do we bring these new technologies into the classroom without losing what really matters about education? The answer has a lot to do with keeping real human connection, critical thinking, and genuine learning experiences at the core. In this paper, we lay out a Human-Centered AI-Integrated Framework for English Language Teaching; the main idea is simple: use AI to make language learning better, not to replace it and think of AI as a tool that backs up teachers and students, not something that tries to take over the whole process. This framework builds on recent research into what makes students satisfied, how scaffolding helps people learn, and the basics of human-centered design because AI works best when it acts as a partner in learning. It joins the conversation, gives helpful feedback at the right moments, and helps students check their own progress. The point isn't for AI to just give answers, it's there to get students thinking, digging deeper, and staying active in their own learning. This approach also tackles some of the big problems with group learning and makes sure assessments stay fair and meaningful, moreover AI can speed things up and give super-personalized support for students to really get something valuable out of it, they need to ask questions, notice where the technology falls short, and see how it fits in with how they learn best. When we use AI on purpose, with some thought behind it, it can make learning English more engaging and interactive than ever. Still, we can't forget what matters most: real, honest teaching and helping students grow into independent, lifelong learners. If we keep people at the center-both teachers and students-we can use AI's strengths without losing the human side of education that makes it so powerful.

Keywords: *artificial intelligence in education (aied), ai-mediated pedagogy, digital literacies, human-ai collaboration, technology-enhanced language learning*

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Author's presentation:

I have been teaching English for Specific Purposes - ESP, within different faculties. The acquired teaching experience has helped me develop the main skills associated with the student-centred approach and also to improve the teacher – student relationship. My career development has been streaming in accordance with the process of lifelong learning, based on the professional standards in order to assist students in achieving the specialized language and educational abilities essential to access ESP resources and to offer a public in which students can link content to their lives. My concern for the students' needs has driven me to elaborate course books which strengthen my teaching experience so as to be able to acquire and put into use relevant and diverse knowledge: *English for Biology Students, English for Business Administration, English for Social Sciences, English for Specific Purposes: Agriculture and Horticulture, English for Bible and Theology (EBT)*. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9372-8839

Active Learning Strategies for Increasing Student Engagement in English Language Teaching

Costina Denisa Bărbuceanu
University of Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

Keeping students engaged has always been a challenge, and it has only gotten tougher with hybrid and online classes everywhere. The old routine-teachers talking, students quietly listening-just doesn't work anymore. Students want and need more, like multimodal affect prediction, analytics powered by large language models, and real-time data from environmental sensors. The idea is to build a system that actually knows the instant a student starts drifting, when that happens, teachers can jump in right away with targeted, personal strategies to pull them back in. Some use sensors to pick up subtle emotional changes, others tap into the huge flow of data from learning management systems. They're useful, but on their own, each one is

limited. What we really need is a model that blends social, behavioral, and emotional cues—a full, layered picture of what’s going on with students. This goes deeper than just noticing when someone loses focus. It helps teachers figure out what makes students jump in, stick around, or totally check out, furthermore, the goal is straightforward: turn English Language Teaching classrooms into dynamic, responsive spaces that change as students do. In these classrooms, the way teachers teach and the way students interact can shift in real time, guided by actual data about what’s working. Accomplishing that means letting go of the old idea of classrooms as fixed spaces and see them as living systems where technology and teaching move together, meeting every student right where they are and ensuring active participation in the pedagogical process, supported by machine learning systems that optimize the learning environment.

Keywords: *active learning, student engagement, learner-centered pedagogy, collaborative learning, communicative competence*

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Author’s presentation:

I have been teaching English for Specific Purposes - ESP, within different faculties. The acquired teaching experience has helped me develop the main skills associated with the student-centred approach and also to improve the teacher – student relationship. My career development has been streaming in accordance with the process of lifelong learning, based on the professional standards in order to assist students in achieving the

specialized language and educational abilities essential to access ESP resources and to offer a public in which students can link content to their lives. My concern for the students' needs has driven me to elaborate course books which strengthen my teaching experience so as to be able to acquire and put into use relevant and diverse knowledge: *English for Biology Students, English for Business Administration, English for Social Sciences, English for Specific Purposes: Agriculture and Horticulture, English for Bible and Theology (EBT)*. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9372-8839

Understanding colors in finance - The impact of Green, Blue and Black Finances on sustainable economic growth

Ramona Birau

University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania & "Constantin Brâncuși" University of Târgu Jiu, Faculty of Economic Science, Tg-Jiu, Romania

Virgil Popescu

University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The main aim of this paper is to provide a literature survey of Green, Blue and Black finance and their implications on sustainable development, financial markets and economic growth. This extensive conceptual analysis highlights topics of great current interest. A low-carbon economy represents a global challenge given the dramatic consequences of climate change. Green finance and implicitly blue finance are focused on achieving sustainable economic growth. The environmental sustainability is considering the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions.

Keywords: *Green finance, Blue finance, Black finance, blue economy, economic growth, sustainable development, climate change, renewable energy, environmental sustainability*

Authors' Contributions:

The authors contributed equally to this work.

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Authors' presentation:

Ramona Birau, University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania
& "Constantin Brâncuși" University of Târgu Jiu, Faculty of Economic Science, Tg-Jiu, Romania

Virgil Popescu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

Pragmatic Aspects of Irrealis Tools in the Language of Information Technology

Irina Janina Boncea

University of Craiova, Faculty of Letters, Department of Applied Foreign Languages, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

In post-communist EFL instruction, focus has shifted from the grammar translation approach to the communicative approach in order to satisfy the increasing need for globalisation in trade and communication. The current article seeks to investigate a set of pragmatic aspects regarding the way in which the English language associated with the Information Technology field makes use of the wide range of irrealis tools and hedging to convey non-factual information. The need for the current research derives from the inherent factuality engineering fields, i.e. from the declared focus on **what is** rather than **what is desirable or possible**. Nonetheless, a stringent need for non-factuality is manifesting through a wide range of presumptive tools, both epistemic and deontic, which the current research will attempt to analyse pragmatically within the framework of native Romanian students studying English for Computer Science.

Keywords: *EFL, ESP, hedging, Information Technology, Irrealis tools, non-factual*

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Author's presentation:

Senior Lecturer **Irina Janina Boncea** PhD has been a member of the Department of Applied Modern Languages, Faculty of Letters, at the

University of Craiova since 2004, teaching English for Specific Purposes (Business English, English for Engineering, English for IT etc). She has completed a Master's Programme (2007) in English teaching, a Doctorate in Philology (2012) and has written numerous research articles and books in the domains of Applied Linguistics- *A Syntactic, Semantic and Pragmatic Analysis of Epistemic Modality in English and Romanian* (2014), *Language Teaching- Teaching Metaphors, Idioms and Collocations* (2009), *English for Specific Purposes - English for Engineering* (2013), *English for Computers and Information Technology* (2019). ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9277-0234

Legitimizing the „peaceful rise” of the People's Republic of China. A Conceptual Analysis of Official Chinese Discourses and Trends in Academic Publication

Maria-Mădălina Bulancia

Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iași, Faculty of Philosophy and Social-political Sciences, Romania

Abstract:

This article explores the construction of legitimacy for China's global role through discourse. Through the analysis of 60 public speeches using word-frequency analysis and conceptual mapping, the article pinpoints the aspects that have served to create a pattern in which most salient ideas converge, translated into recurring concepts, towards a defensive and cooperative narrative, which frames China's rise as peaceful and normatively-based. The results inform dialogue on China's "peaceful rise" and demonstrate the potential of quantitative discourse analysis for research on policy analysis. Additionally, we can derive a dual discourse system that balances between external legitimation, as well as internal legitimation, so there is a melting point between official speeches and domestic academic publications which serve as the ideal embodiment for further depicting China's discursive governance. While the official discourses under scrutiny in this study tend to stress 'cooperative' and 'co-defensive' narratives including 'shared future' and 'common destiny,' data from CNKI on China's academic publishing indicates that these constructs have been increasingly institutionalized in domestic research agendas and point to the diffusion of official slogans in the academic sphere for the validation of their legitimacy. The results contribute to the analysis of discourse, legitimation and international policy communication, by providing a systematic and replicable way of analyzing political elite language. More generally, the research also serves to provide us with further insights into the power dynamics of discourse as a governance technology in world politics and how language is strategically wielded to mould perceptions, construct legitimacy and alter global policy landscapes.

Keywords: *discourse analysis, legitimation, policy narratives, discourse coalitions*

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Author's presentation:

I am a researcher in international relations with expertise in geopolitics, geostrategy, and Sino–American relations. I have completed academic stages abroad, including as a visiting student scholar in Germany (Konstanz) and China. My work explores the dynamics of U.S.–China political, diplomatic, and security relations, as well as broader themes of international order and strategic change. I am the author of „Relațiile politico-diplomatice și militare dintre SUA și R.P. Chineză după sfârșitul Războiului Rece” (Editura Universității Naționale de Apărare „Carol I”, 2019) and I have published articles on topics such as Taiwan's strategic role, the rise of BRICS, Chinese security perceptions, digital-era risk management, and Chinese foreign policy in Africa. My recent studies address the limits of international relations theory in explaining Chinese behavior and the methodological role of mind maps in intelligence analysis.

The role of parliament in the communist coup in Czechoslovakia in 1948

PhDr. Jan Bureš, Ph.D.

Metropolitan University Prague, Czech Republic

Abstract:

In my contribution, I will deal with the process of neutralizing parliament in resolving the serious political crisis that broke out in Czechoslovakia in February 1948. We will look at the Communist Party's efforts to exclude parliament from resolving this crisis. We will show the position of other non-Communist political parties in this crisis, as well as President Beneš's efforts to transfer the resolution of the government crisis in February 1948 to parliament. We will also look at the development of parliament in the period shortly after the Communist coup in February 1948 until approximately the end of 1948. We will show the key steps taken by the communists to bring parliament under their complete control, change the electoral law, and organize undemocratic parliamentary elections with a single list of candidates. At the same time, we will examine the role of parliament in passing key laws that enabled the introduction of political repression in Czechoslovakia after February 1948. We will also analyze how, in the period after February 1948, parliament adapted to the new political regime – the dictatorship of the Communist Party of Czechoslovakia. In this sense, we will analyze the transformation of the standard mechanisms of a democratic parliament into the tools of a controlled parliament, whose task is no longer to control the executive power, but to cooperate in building a socialist system of constitutional bodies. We will also examine the transformation of the role of MPs and parliamentary clubs in parliament shortly after the coup in February 1948.

Keywords: *Parliament, Limited Democracy, Communist Party of Czechoslovakia, Coup d'État*

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Author's presentation:

Jan Bureš, Ph.D. (*1975) is member of Political Science and Anglophone Studies Department at Metropolitan University Prague. He is specialised in History of Czech and Czechoslovak Politics, especially in the period of 1945–1989. Most important publications: The President As the Culprit? Edvard Beneš and February 1948 in the Context of History Textbooks, in: Kinga Anna Gajda (ed.): (Non)Commemoration of the Heritage in Eastern Europe. Peter Lang, Berlin, 2025; The party-political system of the Third Czechoslovak Republic, 1945–1948, In: Malíř, Jiří; Marek, Pavel a kol.: Political parties and party systems. An encyclopedic overview of their history in the Czech lands and Czechoslovakia, Volume 2: 1938–2024. Praha, Kauli Publishing 2025, s. 1211-1227; President Edvard Beneš and the Communists in February 1948, in: Podolec, Ondrej a kol.: The establishment of the communist regime in Czechoslovakia in February 1948 and its consequences for society. Volume I., Bratislava: Institute of National Memory, 2023; Bureš, J.; Cvrček, L.; Fialka, J; Rádková, A.: A Shackled Parliament: The Role and Functioning of the Czechoslovak Legislative Assembly during the Communist Dictatorship, Charles University – Karolinum Press, Institute for the Study of Totalitarian Regimes, Praha, 2022; The Presidium of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Czechoslovakia during the post-war rebuilding of the party leading up to the 1946 parliamentary elections, in: Historical Journal, Vol. 70, No. 2, 2022. ISSN 0018-2575, pp. 243-303. ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5212-170X

Using Artificial Intelligence in Teaching Romanian as a Foreign Language

Burtea-Cioroianu Cristina-Eugenia
University of Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in teaching Romanian as a foreign language (RLS) to foreign students is a modern trend that transforms the learning process, offering personalization, instant feedback and interactive resources. This technology is used especially in the preparatory year to support the development of oral and written communication skills of foreign students. In Romanian universities, where AI technologies are used, the emphasis is on a learning model, where AI does not replace the teacher, but helps him. Active learning and teaching with the help of AI of the Romanian language as a foreign language is one of the best ways to learn, and artificial intelligence systems can help foreign students take control of the lessons taught and progress at their own pace. Teaching Romanian to foreign students with the help of digital tools requires more than linguistic knowledge; it requires a mix of psychology, technology and cultural anthropology. The development of language technologies and artificial intelligence at the university level adapted for Romanian as a foreign language is a priority to ensure institutional digital sovereignty and the inclusion of foreign students.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, learning process, Romanian language, resources, foreign students*

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Author's presentation:

Cristina-Eugenia Burtea-Cioroianu is an Associate Professor PhD at the Department of Romanian Language and Literature, Faculty of Letters, University of Craiova. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1996-4574>

Natural Language Processing as an Integrated Model of AI-Mediated Pedagogy

Bușu Adrian-Florin

University of Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The rapid advancement of Artificial Intelligence has intensified interest in the pedagogical applications of Natural Language Processing (NLP) for English Language Teaching (ELT). While NLP-based systems have demonstrated effectiveness in areas such as automated feedback, adaptive tutoring and conversational practice, their integration into educational contexts remains constrained by limitations in emotional intelligence, pragmatic competence and multimodal communication. This article examines how NLP can be productively integrated into AI-driven ELT systems by situating technological developments within a broader theoretical and pedagogical framework. By integrating research from NLP, computer-assisted language learning, affective computing and second language acquisition, the article proposes a framework in which NLP operates as a linguistically precise yet affectively delimited support structure for communicative development. Rather than pursuing full emotional simulation, this article argues for a principled integration of linguistic analysis, discourse modeling and limited affective responsiveness, positioning AI as a complementary agent within human-centered language education.

Keywords: *pragmatic competence, automated analysis, communicative realism*

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Author's presentation:

Adrian-Florin Buşu is a senior lecturer at the Department of Modern Languages, Faculty of Letters, University of Craiova. He has been teaching English for Computer Engineers for over 20 years and has published 12 books and more than 75 articles on topics related to English Language Teaching, English for Specific Purposes and literature. He is interested in any field related to teaching English to Computer Engineering students. ORCID ID: 0000-0003-1379-9918

(Dis)trust in Political Institutions and Long-term Polarising Trends in Europe

Ladislav Cabada

Metropolitan University Prague (MUP), Prague, Czech Republic

Abstract:

One of the significant attributes of the current rise in illiberal sentiments and protagonists in Western democracies is the erosion of trust in political and other institutions. Trust is being increasingly transferred from institutions to closed communities, social bubbles or new leaders who build their charisma on a combination of media presentation and political entrepreneurship. Thus, among political elites and within societies, ideological polarisation is giving way to affective polarisation, which in some cases displays sectarian features. In our analysis, we present both the main causes of the growing polarisation and the possibilities for overcoming this trend.

Keywords: *trust; distrust; polarization; affective polarisation*

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Author's presentation:

Ladislav Cabada is Full Professor in Political Science and Contemporary History at the Metropolitan University Prague. His research interests include comparative political science in Central Eastern Europe, especially political systems, political actors, electoral cycles and political culture. He has authored or co-authored more than 20 books and about 150 other scholarly publications on these topics. ORCID ID: 0000-0001-9604-0987

“Between self-determination and terrorism: the legal qualification of the actions of national liberation movements in contemporary international law”

Livia Călin

Facultatea de Drept, Universitatea din Craiova, România

Abstract:

National liberation movements have represented, especially in the context of the decolonization process in the 20th century, relevant actors in international relations and in the realization of the right of peoples to self-determination. In contemporary international law, however, the use of violence by non-state actors raises complex issues of legal qualification, especially in relation to the concept of terrorism. The paper aims to analyze the legal status of national liberation movements, starting from the principle of self-determination enshrined in the Charter of the United Nations and in other relevant international instruments. At the same time, the study examines the limits of the use of violence in armed conflicts and the way in which international humanitarian law and international counter-terrorism law intersect in the qualification of the actions of these actors. In this context, the paper aims to highlight the conceptual and normative difficulties in delimiting the legitimate struggle for self-determination and acts of terrorism. The analysis focuses on the evolution of the international legal framework and on the relevant doctrinal and jurisprudential interpretations, with the aim of

assessing whether current international law provides clear criteria for this distinction.

Keywords: *International law, self-determination, terrorism, non-state actors*

Legal perspectives on the regulation of artificial intelligence systems and the protection of the stability of employment relationships

Armand Mihail CALOTĂ

University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The evolution of artificial intelligence systems requires a profound reassessment of the foundations of labor law, moving from the classic vision of subordination to the employer, whether a natural or legal person, to a reality in which the algorithm acquires control and coordination powers. The establishment of a regulatory framework capable of legally integrating these autonomous agents requires the definition of a form of hybrid responsibility, which prevents the dilution of the employer's obligations through the use of technology. The protection of employees' interests in this context cannot be limited to simple temporary measures, but must be shaped around the recognition of a fundamental right to job stability in the face of uncontrolled automation. From a legal perspective, this protection involves the imposition of strict limits on the replacement of human labor, based on the principle of social utility and the need to maintain a balance between technological efficiency and social security.

A rigorous analysis of algorithmic control mechanisms reveals the need to introduce "human safeguard clauses", which would guarantee that decisions affecting the essence of the individual employment contract remain under the jurisdiction and discernment of the human factor. The law must intervene through imperative norms that condition the implementation of artificial intelligence systems on the demonstration of the fact that they do not cancel the employee's right to exercise their profession, transforming technological progress from a threat to economic existence into a support tool. Thus, the outline of a liability regime for the acts of intelligent agents and the consolidation of mechanisms to combat dismissals based exclusively on algorithmic performance become the basis of a new labor law, capable of protecting the dignity and viability of the employee status in a labor market dominated by automation.

Keywords: *Digital legal personality, employment security, guarantee of human intervention, algorithmic law, artificial intelligence (AI).*

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Author's presentation:

Lecturer, Ph.D., University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Department of Public Law and Administrative Sciences, Craiova, Romania.

The legal challenges of artificial intelligence in data and consumer law

Armand Mihail Calotă

University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The integration of Artificial Intelligence into contemporary commercial strategies has opened a new chapter in the balance of power between economic operators and consumers. Analyzing the legal vulnerabilities that arise at the intersection of technological innovation and fundamental rights of the individual, we discover two essential pillars, namely the protection of personal data and the integrity of consent. Exploring the risks that artificial intelligence systems pose to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and analyze the phenomenon of invisible data collection, where profiling algorithms can infer sensitive information without a clear legal basis, defying the principle of transparency and purpose limitation. Nowadays, data is the new oil, traditional protection mechanisms seem increasingly difficult to apply in the face of algorithms that process information at superhuman speeds.

Thus, our research focuses on deceptive commercial practices enhanced by artificial intelligence. Dark patterns and personalized pricing algorithms are examined, which can manipulate consumer decision-making by exploiting automatically identified cognitive biases. We can ask a legal question: where does legitimate personalization end and where does misleading begin? The

analysis aims at the need to adapt consumer protection legislation to include legal liability for autonomous acts of AI systems, going beyond simple human error. We underline the urgency of a hybrid regulatory framework, which harmonizes the new European regulations (AI Act) with existing legislation and which argues that real consumer protection in the digital age cannot be achieved without a rigorous algorithmic audit and without reaffirming the right to human intervention, thus ensuring that technological progress is not achieved by sacrificing data security and the citizen's freedom of choice.

Keywords: *Artificial intelligence (AI), algorithmic management, dark patterns, GDPR compliance, informed consent.*

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Author's presentation:

Lecturer, Ph.D., University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Department of Public Law and Administrative Sciences, Craiova, Romania.

Macroeconomic Determinants of Bank Profitability. Research Trends and Future Perspectives in the Era of Artificial Intelligence

Daniela Iulia Maria Carbune
University of Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The aim of this study is to conduct a bibliometric analysis of the academic literature that examines the relationship between macroeconomic variables and the bank profitability. The paper seeks to identify the most influential publications, the most productive and representative authors, dominant thematic clusters and prevailing methodological approaches that investigate the relationship between macroeconomic variables and key bank profitability indicators such as Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE). Using bibliographic data extracted from the Web of Science Core Collection, the study maps citation networks, co-authorship structures and keyword co-occurrence patterns in order to reveal the intellectual architecture of research examining the relationship between banking performance and macroeconomic variables.

By mapping research trends, the paper serves to clarify the current state of knowledge, identify gaps in the existing empirical literature and outline directions for future investigation, in the field of banking performance under the AI impact.

Furthermore, the bibliometric findings reveal an emerging intersection between traditional macro-financial modeling and advanced analytical techniques, suggesting that artificial intelligence tools may enhance overall operational efficiency, optimize resource allocation and support more resilient strategic decision-making within banking institutions. The paper thus contributes to a deeper understanding of the academic landscape and supports future research integrating macroeconomic determinants with technological innovation in the banking sector.

Keywords: *bibliometric analysis, bank profitability, macroeconomic determinants, artificial intelligence, ROA, ROE.*

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Author's presentation:

Daniela Iulia Maria Carbune: Ph.D. Student, University of Craiova, “Eugeniu Carada” Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Finance specialization, Romania. ORCID ID: 0009-0009-5673-8251

Food and Politics: State Food Controls in Totalitarian Regimes

Casangiu Laetitia

Independent Researcher, Constanta, Romania

Abstract:

This study brings to the forefront a lesser-known aspect of private life under two political regimes at opposite ends of the political spectrum, from different historical periods. It examines the state-imposed restrictions on food supply and consumption under the Fascist regime in Italy and those established by the Communist regime in Romania, which share many points in common despite the numerous ideological differences and the temporal and geographical distance between them.

Keywords: *nutrition, autarky, communism, fascism, state food controls, totalitarianism*

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Communication Mediated by Digital Means

Chirițescu Ileana Mihaela

University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Păunescu Floriana Anca

University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

Online communication produces linguistic structures and variations that are challenging to manage both methodologically and theoretically. The languages employed on social media platforms are, in many respects, hybrid, with participants engaging in diverse forms of interaction—from dialogues between one or multiple interlocutors simultaneously in chat environments, to text, image, and/or audio-video posts, with multiple options for feedback, such as likes, shares, or comments. As a result, significant transformations have emerged, both rhetorically—in the broadest sense of the term—and sociolinguistically, given the spontaneous formation of new linguistic communities and the consequent establishment of a genuinely new communicative paradigm.

The effects and realities associated with this shift, driven by digital evolution and widespread internet access, demand predominantly interdisciplinary approaches. Some researchers focus on the psychological implications of these phenomena, while others examine the configuration of digital environments and the distinctive features of emerging communication channels. Linguistic variations are also a central object of study, as innovations at the language level reflect the profound changes taking place across all spheres of life on online social networks.

In response, scholars have proposed concepts such as computer-mediated communication, internet-mediated communication, Net Ligua, and textspeech, among others. In this work, we refer primarily to those terms we will use most frequently, which have the additional advantage of avoiding implicit evaluative or pejorative connotations. Our objective is to provide an analytical, objective description of the phenomenon, without preemptive value judgments or normative stances, as is often the case in discussions of so-called “language degradation” online. While efforts to normalize the languages used in digital spaces are natural, such initiatives must adhere to the principles and epistemological frameworks of linguistic research. Undertaking this requires moving beyond the comfort zones of existing theories and scholarly conventions.

Keywords: *discourse, online communication, digital, Internet, linguistic variations.*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work.

Author's presentation:

Chirițescu Ileana Mihaela, Associate Professor, PhD at the University of Craiova, Department of Modern Languages, has written 12 books and over 100 specialized articles. Chirițescu Ileana Mihaela teaches French for students from non-philological faculties. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-2272-7580

Păunescu Floriana Anca, Associate Professor, PhD Habil. at the University of Craiova, Department of Romanian Language and Literature, has written 12 books and over 100 specialized articles. Păunescu Floriana Anca teaches Romanian language for foreign students. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9646-7718

Art and Democracy. The Body in Post-Communist Romanian Art

Tudora Crăciun

University of Bucharest/The Doctoral School of Philosophy, Bucharest, Romania

Abstract:

I will analyze the transformations of the representation of the body in post-communist Romanian art, arguing that this visual mutation reflects and, at the same time, contributes to the reconfiguration of the democratic imaginary after 1989. During the communist period, the body was integrated into an ideological iconographic apparatus: either idealized in the socialist-realist paradigm of the heroic worker, or disciplined and normed through strict biopolitical control, which particularly affected corporeality. The official body was a total, productive body, subordinated to the abstract community of "the people."

After 1989, in the context of the transition to democracy and the emergence of a plural public space, the body becomes a place of vulnerability, fragmentation and critical exposure. The practices of artists such as Ion Grigorescu, Geta Brătescu or Adrian Ghenie mark a break with the monumental aesthetics of the communist period: the body no longer functions as a symbol of political order, but as a space of traumatic memory, identity instability and confrontation with recent history. If in communism the

body was represented as a stable and teleologically oriented form, in post-communist art it often appears distorted, precarious, or self-reflexive.

I will argue that this transformation is not only stylistic, but structurally political: the transition from the collective, ideologically normed body to the singular and vulnerable body corresponds to the mutation from a totalitarian regime of visibility to a democratic one, characterized by pluralism and contestation. In this sense, the representation of the body in post-communist Romanian art becomes a privileged indicator of the democratization process and the reconfiguration of the relationship between the individual, community and power.

Keywords: *art, democracy, body, post-communism, Romanian art*

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Author's presentation:

Tudora Crăciun is a PhD student at the University of Bucharest, Doctoral School of Philosophy, with a thesis on the transfiguration of the body in contemporary art. She holds a B.A. in Philosophy, (2018), a M.A. in Philosophy (2020) at the Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova. She published „The Myth's Way Back into the Body. A Visual Analysis of the Anti-War Film” in *CONCEPT*, Vol. 24 No. 1 (2022) and she contributed to the collective book *The Body in the Cinematographic Imaginary* (under publishing). She participated at CIVIS Summer School: Transitive

Modernities – Mobilities, Mediations, Circulations, Stockholm, 2022, and other international conferences. Research interest: aesthetics and philosophy of art, the body in art and cinema, cinematographic imaginary.

Redefining American Conservatism after 2016: Transatlantic Illiberal Currents and the Crisis of Liberalism

Karina Beatrice Crețu

Faculty of Political Science, University of Bucharest, Bucharest, Romania

Abstract:

Over the past decade, American conservatism has undergone a profound ideological reorientation. Traditionally grounded in a “three-legged” fusion of free-market liberalism, social traditionalism, and hawkish foreign policy, the post-2016 right has increasingly questioned the very liberal foundations of this consensus. This paper maps three emerging intellectual currents within contemporary U.S. conservatism—the postliberals, the Claremont-inspired constitutional traditionalists, and the national conservatives—and analyzes how each seeks to redefine first principles of political order.

Postliberal thinkers such as Patrick Deneen and Adrian Vermeule argue that liberalism’s emphasis on individual autonomy has eroded the moral and communal foundations of society, calling instead for a politics oriented toward the “common good.” The Claremont school, associated with figures such as Michael Anton, frames contemporary political conflict as a struggle to restore the American founding against what it sees as progressive elite capture. National conservatives, led by Yoram Hazony, advocate national sovereignty, cultural cohesion, and resistance to global liberalism, actively cultivating transatlantic networks linking American and European critics of liberal democracy.

Although analytically distinct, these currents collectively mark a decisive break with Reagan-era fusionism and reveal a broader Western crisis of liberal orthodoxy. Drawing on intellectual history and network analysis, this study situates the post-2016 American right within a wider East–West reconfiguration of conservative thought, highlighting ideological exchanges between the United States and post-communist Europe. By tracing these developments, the paper contributes to understanding how debates once peripheral to mainstream conservatism have become central to contemporary political realignment.

Keywords: *American conservatism, postliberal right, illiberal democracy, transatlantic ideological exchange, common good constitutionalism, democratic backsliding.*

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Author's presentation:

Karina-Beatrice Crețu is a PhD candidate in Political Science at the Faculty of Political Science, University of Bucharest. Her doctoral research examines the ideological transformation of American conservatism after the Cold War, with a particular focus on the breakdown of fusionism and the rise of postliberal and illiberal currents within the American New Right. Her work combines intellectual history and political theory to trace the genealogy of contemporary right-wing critiques of liberal democracy. She has presented her research at international academic conferences, including the Aleksanteri Conference on Extremisms and doctoral seminars organised by the Roosevelt Institute for American Studies. Her broader research interests include American political thought, populism, postliberalism, and transatlantic ideological exchange. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-1505-8598>

Presidential Advisers in post-communist Romania

Radu Cupcea

Institute of Political Science and International Relations “Ion I. C. Brătianu” of the Romanian Academy, Bucharest, Romania

Abstract:

The Presidential Administration is a pivotal political institution within the Romanian state mechanism. Despite its importance, the President's entourage remains largely under-researched by social scientists, a gap resulting from both the scarcity of dedicated studies and inherent biases within existing literature. Current analyses prioritize the presence of high-ranking civil servants while rarely offering a qualitative perspective. Utilizing a mixed-methods approach, this article draws on semi-structured interviews conducted with advisors at the Cotroceni Palace who served between 1990 and 2025. It examines professional trajectories, recruitment processes, the advisor-president relationship, and the impact of politicization. Ultimately, this study highlights the dynamics of presidential entourage formation and seeks to establish a framework for future large-scale qualitative research.

Keywords: *Advisors, policy advice, democracy, Presidential Administration.*

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Author's presentation:

Radu Cupcea is a Scientific Research Assistant at the Institute of Political Sciences and International Relations “Ion I. C. Brătianu” of the Romanian Academy and he holds a PhD in Sociology from the Faculty of Sociology and Social Assistance of the University of Bucharest (2023). He is the author of several studies published in specialized scientific journals dealing with subjects such as the role and the perspectives of the Republic of Moldova in International Relations, the Black Sea region and the ex-Soviet space.

Philosophical hesitations on the nature and consequences of the human right over one's own body

Dan Claudiu Dănișor

University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Department of Public Law, Romania

Abstract:

Although the concept of human right over one's own body seems clear, the nature and consequences of this right are in reality particularly confusing, as there is no indisputable philosophical substantiation of them. Philosophical hesitations on the nature and consequences of this right make the option of constitutionalizing either the principle of the unavailability of the human body as such, or that of its complete availability impossible. The two principles weigh each other in a conjunctural manner. But the choice of the criterion of conjunctural balancing is not decided either, as it does not seem clear in this area whether liberal democracies are determined to stand firmly on the ground of neutrality towards moral doctrines, aiming only at the achievement of a just society, or are willing to give in to perfectionist temptations, aiming to achieve the good society in itself.

Keywords: *human rights, habeas corpus, unavailability of the human body.*

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Vertical separation of power – a means of guaranteeing freedom in states governed by the rule of law

Dan Claudiu Dănișor

University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Department of Public Law, Romania,

Mădălina Cristina Dănișor

University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Department of Public Law, Romania

George Liviu Gîrleşteanu

University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Department of Public Law, Romania

Elena Mădălina Nica

University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Department of Public Law, Romania

Abstract:

The separation of powers is most often understood only as a horizontal one, between the organs or systems of organs that exercise the three functions of the state – legislative, executive and judicial. The vertical separation of powers is either neglected or metamorphosed into a technique for organizing the state form, with no direct connection to the purpose of the other separation: effective guarantee of the rights and freedoms of the subjects. In fact, its purpose is the same, and the two forms of separation are an integral part of the system of guarantees constitutionally synthesized in the concept of the rule of law. Our study draws attention to the way in which the analysis of the state form must be resituated, in order to then focus on the way in which the history of the Romanian political and constitutional system has made any discussion about tempering the unity of the state seem like a betrayal of the unity of the Romanian nation. Following the criticism of this excessive attachment to a certain restrictive understanding of state unity, we finally show how the current Romanian constitutional framework should be revised, even in the restrictive manner in which it is interpreted by the Constitutional Court, so that the vertical separation of powers can be transformed into a means of guaranteeing fundamental rights and freedoms, which contributes to the building of an effective rule of law.

Keywords: *unitary state, regionalization, separation of powers, rule of law, human rights.*

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Authors' Contributions:

The authors contributed equally to this work.

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The importance of the promise to sell in the context of the development of the real estate market in Romania

Matei DIACONU

University of Craiova/ Faculty of Law, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The real estate market in Romania has experienced significant development during the recent decades, amid increased investment in the construction sector and the growing interest in purchasing homes. In this context of social reality, legal instruments that regulate real estate transactions have acquired particular importance. One of these instruments is the promise of sale, also known as the preliminary sale-purchase contract. This is an agreement by which the parties undertake to conclude the actual sale-purchase contract in the future, establishing from the outset the main conditions of the transaction. The importance of the promise of sale lies both in its legal role and in its contribution to the development and stability of the real estate market. By specifying the obligations of the parties and the main conditions of the sale, it contributes to increasing the legal certainty and reducing the risks associated with real estate transactions.

Keywords: *real estate market, stability, certainty, reducing risks.*

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Author's presentation:

Matei DIACONU is a lawyer, PH.D in law and lecturer at the Faculty of Law of the University of Craiova. Civil law and Real Estate Publicity are its fields of research. He has published alone or as a co-author 6 books and 21 articles. ORCID ID: 0009-0006-6619-986X

Infrastructure Integration and Energy Security Governance: Observing Romania's Role in Regional Natural Gas Transport Systems

Dinulescu Alexandra-Ştefania

*Baku State University, Faculty of International Relations and Economy,
Department of Diplomacy and Modern Integration Processes, International
Relations Specialization*

Abstract:

Energy infrastructure has become a principal element for contemporary governance, influencing not only market efficiency, but also national security, regional stability, and state decisions regarding foreign policy. In Europe's tensed geopolitical environment, natural gas transport systems represent long-term advantages whose political relevance goes beyond their technical purpose. This article analyzes how integration into international and regional gas transport infrastructures contributes to national and energy security, describing infrastructure connectivity as a form of governance strategy. This is done by introducing a new indicator named GTII (Gas Transport Infrastructure Integration) which will examine the degree to which states are involved in operational gas transmission systems. The indicator reveals integration as a dimension of security, explaining how diversification of partners and routing optionality can reduce exposure regarding disruptions, political pressure, or technical failure.

This study will focus on Romania's participation in two major regional and international gas transport systems: the BRUA pipeline and the Trans-Balkan gas corridor. Despite their differences regarding historical origins and technical designs, both systems improve Romania's access to different supply routes and integrate the country within wider regional governance frameworks. The results reveal that Romania's integration into different operational pipeline systems reduces vulnerability to one route dependency, enhances crisis response capacity, and grows its relevance in the regional energy landscape. By applying GTII, the article assigns Romania a high level of infrastructural integration, validating the hypothesis that involvement in multiple gas transport pipelines can generate positive effects for national security. In doing so, it highlights the everlasting political importance of energy infrastructure that influences the security governance in Europe.

Keywords: *energy security; infrastructure governance; natural gas transport; national security; diversification; regional integration.*

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Author's presentation:

Ph.D. Student, Bilateral Agreement for Education between Romania and Azerbaijan, Baku State University, Faculty of International Relations and Economy, Department of Diplomacy and Modern Integration Processes, International Relations Specialization. Participated in multiple conferences such as the one with the Social Research Center of Azerbaijan, International Scientific and Practical Conference of the Social Research Center in Baku Azerbaijan, In the framework of "2025 – The Year of Constitution and Sovereignty" and the NASCO XXVIII National Conference for PhD students and Young Researchers. Multiple publications in the Volume 5, Issue 2 of the Caucasus International University's Journal of Social Sciences and the Social Research Scientific-analytical journal of Social Research Center in Azerbaijan. ORCID ID: 0009-0005-4226-3815

The issue of teaching Polish in diaspora regarding the political and historical background

Andrzej Dubicki

Uniwersytet Łódzki/WSMiP, Łódź, Poland

Abstract:

The Polish presence in Brazil dates back at least to the 17th century, but at the respective time there was no organized settlement in the then Portuguese colony. Organized migration to the independent Brazilian state dates back to 1870's.

It is accurately estimated that about 115 000 Poles had arrived in Brazil by 1933. These are approximate figures, mainly due to the fact that before 1918, Poles were very often classified according to their citizenship.

Polish education and the issue of teaching the Polish language played an important role in the social behaviour of Polish migrants. Importantly, as a rule, moving to an overseas superpower meant significant facilitation and, as a rule, the lifting of all restrictions on learning Polish for the younger generation. The essence of the problem for migrants was signified by the fact that school was usually the third building built by settlers in their new

place of residence, right after their own house and church. It is worth noting that the main direction of Polish emigration to Brazil were the southern states: Parana, Santa Catarina and Rio Grande do Sul.

The aim of the presentation will be to show the circumstances in which the teaching of Polish language (as well as those of others minorities) evolved in Brasil regarding the political circumstances from XIX century until nowadays.

Keywords: *Polish diaspora, diaspora, politics, Brazil, language teaching.*

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Author's presentation:

Dr hab. Andrzej Dubicki, prof. UŁ (born 1978), historian and political scientist, associate professor at; Department of Political Theory and Political Thought at the Faculty of International Relations and Political Science at the University of Lodz. Scientific interests: Contemporary Romanian politics; History and Politics of Balkan Peninsula and its relations with the rest of the Europe; Electoral Law, especially old voting systems and formulas used in the process of politicization and modernization of modern societies; Author of 6 books and 61 scientific articles, in 2016 laureate of the Waclaw Felczak and Henryk Wereszycki Prize for the best book concerning the history and politics of the Middle Europe in the 19 and 20 Century. In 2019 laureate of Juliusz Demel prize for the historic book about the Lucjan Skupiewski, famous MD and politician, promotor of mutual Polish-Romanian cooperation. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9949-210X

Assessing the Impact of Financial Risk on Organizations by Modeling the Unemployment Rate Using the ARIMA Model

Cezar Catalin Ene

University of Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The unemployment rate is a critical macroeconomic indicator that directly influences the financial stability and risk exposure of organizations, yet the dynamic relationship between unemployment fluctuations and corporate financial risk remains insufficiently explored through rigorous quantitative methods. This article aims to model and forecast Romania's unemployment rate using the ARIMA methodology, thereby assessing its implications for organizational financial risk within an international comparative framework. Monthly unemployment rate data were sourced from the European Central Bank database, covering the period January 1997 to November 2024, totaling 335 observations. The series was log-transformed to stabilize variance, and stationarity was tested using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test, which confirmed the original series as non-stationary ($p = 0.5935$); first-order differencing successfully achieved stationarity ($p = 0.0000$). Following the Box-Jenkins methodology implemented in EViews 12, multiple ARIMA specifications were evaluated based on the Bayesian Information Criterion, adjusted R^2 , and standard error of regression. The ARIMA(1, 2, 2) model was selected as optimal, with statistically significant AR(1) and MA(2) coefficients of -0.9843 and -0.9975 , respectively. Residual diagnostics confirmed white noise behavior through the Ljung-Box Q-statistic, and model stability was validated via inverse root analysis. Forecast evaluation demonstrated strong predictive accuracy, yielding an RMSE of 0.042, a Theil inequality coefficient of 0.012, and a covariance proportion of 81.7%. These findings confirm that ARIMA models effectively capture Romania's unemployment dynamics across major economic disruptions, including the 2008 financial crisis and the COVID-19 pandemic, offering practical value for managers, investors, and policymakers seeking to anticipate labor market shifts and mitigate associated financial risks.

Keywords: *unemployment rate, ARIMA, financial risk, time series forecasting*

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Author's presentation:

Ph.D. Student Cezar Catalin Ene, under the supervision of dr. Cristi Spulbar, graduated from the University of Craiova, Mathematics and Informatics specialization, earned in 2021, following a Master's in Finances and Business Administration. He is currently pursuing a Ph.D. at "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral Schools of Economic Sciences. His field of study is a multidisciplinary approach on finance domain and Machine Learning domain. His expertise encompasses artificial neural networks, artificial intelligence, deep learning, financial markets, econometrics, software and web development and cybersecurity. On the practical part his experience in cybersecurity is directed towards implementing safeguarding solutions of the operational activities for private companies. In software and web development, he develops scalable and secured platforms tailored to the needs of private sector, including here the implementation of AI solutions. Since 2022, Cezar has also been a consultant in European funds and digitalization for private entities, leveraging his extensive knowledge and skills in both finance and technology. ORCID ID: 0009-0008-4401-0194

The Crisis of Euroscepticism and the Rise of the Illiberal Parties. A Comparative Analysis of Party Manifestoes from Romania, Poland and Hungary in the Context of National and European Elections

Filimon Luiza-Maria

"Ovidius" University of Constanta, Constanta, Romania

Abstract:

In the post-enlargement and post-Lisbon Treaty era, the crisis of Euroscepticism has upended the processes of Europeanisation and integration on which the European Union (EU) was built. A fixture in Western Europe, Euroscepticism has begun to encroach on the political agenda of parties from Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) Member States (MSs). If in the West, Euroscepticism has been traditionally associated with smaller and fringe parties given the dominance of pro-European parties affiliated with the European People's Party group (EPP) at the European and national levels, in Central and Eastern Europe, the emergence of the Eurosceptic current has been driven by mainstream parties that underwent a process of illiberalisation as was the case in Hungary and Poland with Fidesz and Law and Justice parties. The present study analyses what are the causes driving the support of Euroscepticism in CEE MSs with a focus on parties from Romania, Poland and Hungary that occupy different governmental positions (in power, in opposition or former ruling parties). The case-study selection

reflects the interdependence between Eurosceptic and illiberal dynamics, and how, in turn, this relation influences the development of party positions towards the EU. For this purpose, the analysis reviews the party manifestoes adopted during the European and national elections organised between 2019 and 2024 to trace the evolution of this phenomenon across three of the largest MSs from the CEE region.

Keywords: *Euroscepticism, Euro-phobia, European elections, national elections, illiberalism, radical right parties, Law and Justice (PiS), Fidesz, Alliance for the Union of Romanians*

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Author's presentation:

Luiza-Maria Filimon is Assistant Professor at the Faculty of History and Political Science, "Ovidius" University of Constanta, Romania. She holds a PhD in Political Science from the National University of Political and Administrative Studies, Bucharest, Romania. The research interests are centered on recent developments in European politics, focusing on the analysis of the rise of the radical right and the way in which right-wing parties use European elections as an entry point into the political mainstream. Relevant publications: Luiza-Maria Filimon și Mihaela Ivănescu, "The SOE

Redux: The 2024 European Parliament Elections in the Romanian Context”, în *L’Europe Unie*, vol. 23, 2025, pp. 132-150, https://leuropeunie.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/12/art-9-132_150.pdf. Luiza-Maria Filimon, “The Poster Child for the Radical Right Ascent: *Rassemblement National* and the 2024 European Elections”, *Revista de Științe Politice. Revue des Sciences Politiques*, no. 86, 2025, pp. 132-144, https://cis01.ucv.ro/revistadestiintepolitice/files/numarul86_2025/11.pdf
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7916-0562>

Impact of Energy Price Shocks on the Romanian Electricity Market: An Extended Econometric Analysis Using Local Projections and Error-Correction Modelling

Mihai Frunză

Doctoral School of Management, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration (SNSPA), Bucharest, Romania

Lucian Claudiu Anghel

Faculty of Management, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration (SNSPA), Bucharest, Romania

Abstract:

This study investigates how external energy shocks, particularly fluctuations in natural gas prices (TTF) and crude oil (BRENT), transmit into the Romanian electricity market. Using monthly data for the period 2018–2025 (96 observations), the analysis employs an extended econometric framework combining (i) Local Projections with cumulative impulse responses and (ii) an Error-Correction Model supported by formal cointegration tests (Engle-Granger and Johansen procedures). The methodological approach allows for robust identification of both short-run dynamics and long-run equilibrium adjustments, while explicitly incorporating structural breaks associated with the 2021–2022 energy crisis.

The results show strong evidence of cointegration between electricity prices and natural gas prices ($p < 0.001$), consistent with the merit-order theory where gas-fired plants often set marginal electricity prices. The estimated long-run elasticity of electricity with respect to TTF is approximately 0.77%, while the short-run pass-through coefficient is 0.44%. Local Projections confirm a cumulative elasticity of approximately 1.05% after 12 months, indicating moderate overshooting but statistically indistinguishable from the long-run equilibrium predicted by the ECM ($p = 0.39$). The adjustment half-life is estimated at 1.7 months. Structural break tests (Chow test) identify two major ruptures during the crisis period (January and June 2022), and rolling-window estimates reveal stable transmission parameters outside crisis intervals (CV = 15.5%).

Exogeneity tests—including Granger non-causality, placebo lead-shock estimation, and sub-sample analysis—support the treatment of TTF shocks as external to the Romanian market, reflecting the country's price-taker status in European energy markets.

Policy implications highlight the relevance of early-warning mechanisms based on gas price monitoring, targeted consumer protection measures, and structural interventions such as diversification of the energy mix and increased cross-border interconnection capacity.

Keywords: *Energy shocks; Electricity prices; Local Projections; Error-Correction Model; Cointegration; Romania*

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Author's presentation:

Since December 2025, I have been working as a Senior Risk Analyst – Strategic Risk at Libra Internet Bank, where I develop and validate quantitative models, contribute to strategic risk assessments, and support decision-making frameworks focused on market and credit risk exposure. In parallel, I am a PhD candidate at the Școala Doctorală de Management, SNSPA, with research focused on credit risk modeling, early-warning indicators, and the interaction between macro-financial variables and

portfolio risk. My academic background in mathematics and econometrics supports my applied research on price dynamics, risk transmission mechanisms, and model-based forecasting. I am also the author of “Trading-ul din spatele graficelor” (ISBN 978-9975-3524-9-9, 2024), a book dedicated to financial education and practical risk-management methods. My work aims to integrate rigorous quantitative analysis with strategic risk governance to improve forecasting accuracy and support informed financial decisions. ORCID ID: 0009-0006-9353-3018

Simulation and resistance in the democratization of Romania: Public policy instruments between the normative control of the West and the survival of local elites

Paula-Simona Gafincu (Ciubotă)

Universitatea Alexandru Ioan Cuza, Școala Doctorală de Filosofie și Științe Social-Politice, Iași, România

Abstract:

This paper aims to analyze the process of decommunization and democratization of Romania, emphasizing both the normative control exercised by Euro-Atlantic institutions and the power-preserving strategies used by post-communist elites.

The transition to a democratic state was not achieved, as expected, through immediate and transparent reform policies. These were marked, on the one hand, by the formal adoption of Western institutions and procedures (to satisfy the accession criteria) and, on the other hand, by an informal resistance aimed at neutralizing their impact on inherited power structures.

From a methodological point of view, the study relies on public policy analysis and the path dependency model to identify the mechanisms through which local elites slowed down lustration legislation and “captured” independent institutions through political appointments. The paper demonstrates that although the West imposed democratic control instruments (such as the MCV or transparency laws), their success was partly due to the ability of the Romanian political system to mimic compliance without giving up discretionary control over state resources. The conclusions emphasize that in the process of democratization of Romania, important democratic forms were often emptied of content by various techniques of institutional resistance, which made it a hybrid one. The establishment of the rule of law with all its specific principles and values is possible by gradually removing the mechanisms inherited from communism and by creating a culture of citizen empowerment to fight against authoritarian tendencies that might emerge.

Keywords: *decommunization, path dependency, public policies, political resistance, institutional capture, normative control.*

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Author's presentation:

My name is Ciubotă Paula-Simona and I am a PhD candidate at the Faculty of Philosophy and Social-Political Sciences, with a research topic of "Public policies for the decommunization and democratization of Romania". Since 2018 I have been a professor of Social Education in secondary education. An important article that I have published is "Problems of Democratization in Post-communist Romania", Vol. 20 No. 1 (2025): Political Sciences, Tome XX, 2025. ORCID ID: 0009-0000-8966-6500

Assessing the Correlations between Socioeconomic Development and Sustainable Policy Outcomes: A Multidimensional Analysis of Health, Education, Equality, Employment, Security and Climate Resilience

Cătălina Maria Georgescu

University of Craiova, Romania

Anca Parmena Olimid

University of Craiova, Romania

Daniel Alin Olimid

University of Craiova, Romania

Silviu Dorin Georgescu

Independent Researcher, Craiova, Romania

Cosmin Lucian Gherghe

University of Craiova, Romania

Abstract

Scope and Objectives: This study focuses on the correlations between multidimensional socioeconomic and security objectives and sustainable policy outcomes, investigating the linkages of key indicators such as health, education, gender equality and employment gaps, youth employment, income distribution, security objectives, climate resilience, and sustainable development goals (SDGs).

Methodology: An exploratory, cross-national, and quantitative research was conducted, employing data from international databases. The empirical research advanced descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and multivariate regression models to examine relationships between policy variables, such as government expenditure, on the one hand, and, on the other hand, outcomes across the selected indicators.

Results and Discussion: Findings indicate that higher government expenditure on social sectors is significantly associated with improvements in health and education results, and improving income equality, while policies promoting security, climate resilience and sustainable development are positively correlated to socioeconomic outcomes, demonstrating the interconnected nature of SDG implementation.

Conclusions: The study pinpoints the essence of multidimensional policy approaches targeting social, economic, security and environmental resilience objectives. Effective government spending and labor market strategies, enforced by security measures and sustainable climate policies can create spinoffs for achieving multiple SDGs. Policymakers are encouraged to adopt interconnected decisional and evaluation frameworks to monitor progress, link resource allocation, and minimize the disadvantages that come from choosing one development goal option over another.

Keywords: *Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), health, education, inequality, unemployment, security, climate resilience.*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work.

Authors' presentation:

Cătălina Maria Georgescu is Lecturer Ph.D. at the Faculty of Social Sciences, Political Sciences Specialization within the University of Craiova. She received her Ph.D. in 2011 from the University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration. She has a BA degree in Political Sciences (2006) in English Specialty from the Faculty of Political Sciences, University of Bucharest. She completed her MA degree in Political Sciences – National and Euro-Atlantic Security at the University of Craiova (2011). She is the (co-)author of 5 books and of over 60 studies and reviews published as book chapters or articles in publications indexed in international data bases. Her areas of scientific interest include the politics-administration relations, public policies, management of public organizations, European governance and democratization in South-Eastern Europe. Deputy Editor-in-chief at *Revista de Științe Politice/Revue des Sciences Politiques*. ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4462-4689>.

Anca Parmena Olimid Ph.D. is Associate Professor at the University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Department of History, Political Sciences, International Relations, Political Sciences Specialization. She holds a B.A. in Law from the Faculty of Law (2003) and a B.A. in Political Sciences from the Faculty of History, Philosophy and Geography, University of Craiova (2003) and a Ph.D. in Humanities from the Faculty of History, Philosophy and Geography of the University of Craiova (2008). Her specialist subject areas are Romanian Politics since 1989, Modern and Contemporary Political Thought, the relationship between society, state and religion, Geopolitics and Geostrategy. Two of Professor Olimid's outstanding achievements is her receipt of Economic and Social Council, ECOSOC (WYA), UN Headquarters, New York for a three months internship in 2005 and her Erasmus Scholarship for six months at the University Charles de Gaulle Lille III, France in 2001-2002. Mrs. Olimid has published widely in international databases and national political journals and is the (co)author of several books, notably, *Politics and Religion in EU and USA. Legal commentaries and social*

controversies (2010), *Political and spiritual life in Modern Romanian. A Romanian Model of Church-State Relations* (2009) awarded by the Ministry of Education and Research in 2009, *Romanian Politics since 1989* (2009); *Politics, Security and Participatory Governance: Key Concepts, Policies and Legislation* (2015). Editor-in-chief of *Revista de Științe Politice/Revue des Sciences Politiques*. ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7546-9845>.

Daniel Alin Olimid is lecturer Ph.D. at the Department of Biology and Environmental Engineering of the University of Craiova, Biology Specialization. His research interest and activity includes research articles in the field of cell biology, genetics and related field in journals indexed ISI Thomson Reuters and other international databases. He hold a Ph.d. in Medical Sciences, a BA and a MA in Medical Sciences from the University of Craiova, Faculty of Medicine. ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5583-668X>.

Silviu Dorin Georgescu holds a Ph.D. diploma in the field of management from the Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova. He has a BA degree in Management and Marketing from the Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova. He completed his MA degree in the Management of Human Resources at the University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration. Currently he is an entrepreneur in the private sector in the services market. He was a stagiary of the Robert Schumann Foundation in the European Parliament in Brussels, Belgium. Silviu Dorin Georgescu was assistant researcher at the Institute of Agrarian Economies, the Romanian Academy and assistant professor at the University of Craiova. Author of 1 book and several studies published as book chapters or articles in publications indexed in international data bases the field of services management and marketing. ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5187-6892>.

Cosmin Lucian Gherghe, Ph.D. is Associate Professor at the Political Sciences Specialization, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova. He holds a Ph.D. degree in History (2008) from the Faculty of History, Geography and Philosophy, University of Craiova and a B.A. in Political Sciences (2003) from the Faculty of History, Geography and Philosophy, University of Craiova and in Law (1999) from the Faculty of Law and Administrative Sciences, University of Craiova. He is the author of over 40 articles, studies and papers published in scientific journals or presented in national and international conferences. He is the author of “Emanoil Chinezu – Om politic, avocat și istoric”, Editura Sitech, Craiova, 2009 and (co-author) “Partidele politice”, Editura Sitech, Craiova, 2008. His areas of interest include political parties, constitutional law, administrative and political institutions. He is member of 3 research projects/grants and also a member of the editorial board of *Revista*

de Științe Politice/Revue des Sciences Politiques. ORCID ID
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9131-0391>.

Comparative Analysis of National Security Strategies: Policy Formation, Institutional Actors, and Instruments of National Power

Cătălina Maria Georgescu

University of Craiova, Romania

Silviu Dorin Georgescu

Independent Researcher, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

Scope and Objectives: This study examines the formulation and content of national security strategies through a comparative analysis of two selected states and their official national security strategy documents. The research aims to analyze how national security is defined within these strategic documents and how this definition outlines the national interests, values, and policy objectives. The study seeks to identify the decision-making models involved in the development of national security strategies, the institutional actors involved in their formulation and implementation, and the instruments of national power employed to achieve strategic objectives. The central objective is to pinpoint the similarities and differences between the selected cases and to identify the major political and institutional factors that influence the strategic planning process.

Methodology: The research is based on a qualitative methodology combining content analysis of official strategic documents with a comparative analytical approach. The selected national security strategies constitute the primary sources of analysis, allowing for the examination of key concepts, definitions, and strategic priorities. The study is structured around three main analytical dimensions: the national security environment and decision-making models, the actors and institutions involved in national security governance, and the instruments of national power available to the state. The comparative framework enables the identification of patterns, similarities, and differences in the strategic approaches of the two states.

Results and Discussion: The findings indicate that national security strategies reflect both the external security environment and the internal political and institutional structures of each state. Differences in historical experience, geopolitical positioning, and political systems influence how national security is conceptualized and prioritized. The analysis highlights the role of key institutional actors—such as executive authorities, defense and security institutions, and advisory bodies—in shaping national security policies and strategies. Furthermore, the study demonstrates that national power is exercised through a combination of diplomatic, military, economic, and informational instruments, whose relative importance varies depending on national priorities and strategic culture.

Conclusions: The research confirms that national security strategies are complex policy documents shaped by a combination of domestic political dynamics, institutional frameworks, and international security challenges. The comparative analysis contributes to a better understanding of how different states conceptualize and operationalize national security. The applied methodology proved effective in identifying both structural similarities and context-specific differences between the analyzed cases. Future research could expand the comparative framework by including additional states or by examining the evolution of national security strategies over time, thereby offering deeper insights into the transformation of national security policy in the contemporary international environment.

Keywords: *national security strategy, decision-making model, institutional actors, diplomatic instruments, military instruments, economic instruments, informational instruments.*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work.

Authors' presentation:

Cătălina Maria Georgescu is Lecturer Ph.D. at the Faculty of Social Sciences, Political Sciences Specialization within the University of Craiova. She received her Ph.D. in 2011 from the University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration. She has a BA degree in Political Sciences (2006) in English Specialty from the Faculty of Political Sciences, University of Bucharest. She completed her MA degree in Political Sciences – National and Euro-Atlantic Security at the University of Craiova (2011). She is the (co-)author of 5 books and of over 60 studies and reviews published as book chapters or articles in publications indexed in international data bases. Her areas of scientific interest include the politics-administration relations, public policies, management of public organizations, European governance and democratization in South-Eastern Europe. Deputy Editor-in-chief at

Revista de Științe Politice/Revue des Sciences Politiques. ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4462-4689>.

Silviu Dorin Georgescu holds a Ph.D. diploma in the field of management from the Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova. He has a BA degree in Management and Marketing from the Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova. He completed his MA degree in the Management of Human Resources at the University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration. Currently he is an entrepreneur in the private sector in the services market. He was a stagiary of the Robert Schumann Foundation in the European Parliament in Brussels, Belgium. Silviu Dorin Georgescu was assistant researcher at the Institute of Agrarian Economies, the Romanian Academy and assistant professor at the University of Craiova. Author of 1 book and several studies published as book chapters or articles in publications indexed in international data bases the field of services management and marketing. ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5187-6892>.

Rethinking Educational Policies to Counteract Social Media Dependence: Grit and Self-Efficacy as Protective Factors for Youth

Cătălina Maria Georgescu

University of Craiova, Romania

Silviu Dorin Georgescu

Independent Researcher, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

Purpose and Objectives: Framed within the growing concern of social media dependence as an educational policy challenge, this study examines the relationships between resilience-related traits—specifically perseverance (“grit”) and general self-efficacy—and social media dependence among adolescents and young people. The research aims to explore whether these psychological resources function as protective factors against excessive social media use, with potential implications for educational policy and youth development.

Methodology: An exploratory, cross-sectional, and descriptive design was employed. The data were analyzed using correlation and regression analyses, and the Cronbach’s alpha coefficient was calculated to assess the internal consistency of the measurement scales. The sample consisted of young participants (N = 31) aged between 14 and 23 years who completed an online questionnaire comprising 35 items administered through the Google Forms platform. The instrument included demographic questions and standardized scales measuring perseverance (grit), general self-efficacy, and social media dependence. Based on prior empirical research

and theoretical frameworks, it was hypothesized that both grit and self-efficacy would be negatively associated with social media dependence.

Results and Discussion: The findings indicate that perseverance is positively associated with general self-efficacy and negatively associated with social media dependence. Likewise, general self-efficacy shows an inverse relationship with social media dependence. These results suggest that adolescents who demonstrate higher levels of perseverance and self-efficacy are less likely to develop problematic patterns of social media use.

Conclusions: The results support the view that grit and general self-efficacy may function as protective factors against social media dependence by strengthening adolescents' resistance to compulsive online engagement. From a policy perspective, fostering these psychosocial competencies within educational environments may represent a relevant strategy for addressing the risks associated with excessive social media use while promoting improved academic and developmental outcomes.

Keywords: *educational policy, social media, academic results, correlation analysis, regression analysis.*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work.

Authors' presentation:

Cătălina Maria Georgescu is Lecturer Ph.D. at the Faculty of Social Sciences, Political Sciences Specialization within the University of Craiova. She received her Ph.D. in 2011 from the University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration. She has a BA degree in Political Sciences (2006) in English Specialty from the Faculty of Political Sciences, University of Bucharest. She completed her MA degree in Political Sciences – National and Euro-Atlantic Security at the University of Craiova (2011). She is the (co-)author of 5 books and of over 60 studies and reviews published as book chapters or articles in publications indexed in international data bases. Her areas of scientific interest include the politics-administration relations, public policies, management of public organizations, European governance and democratization in South-Eastern Europe. Deputy Editor-in-chief at *Revista de Științe Politice/Revue des Sciences Politiques*. ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4462-4689>.

Silviu Dorin Georgescu holds a Ph.D. diploma in the field of management from the Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova. He has a BA degree in Management and Marketing from the Faculty

of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova. He completed his MA degree in the Management of Human Resources at the University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration. Currently he is an entrepreneur in the private sector in the services market. He was a stagiary of the Robert Schumann Foundation in the European Parliament in Brussels, Belgium. Silviu Dorin Georgescu was assistant researcher at the Institute of Agrarian Economies, the Romanian Academy and assistant professor at the University of Craiova. Author of 1 book and several studies published as book chapters or articles in publications indexed in international data bases the field of services management and marketing. ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5187-6892>.

Montaigne on Otherness: The Cannibal as Noble Savage

Ștefan Viorel Ghenea

University of Craiova/Faculty of Social Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

Michel de Montaigne, in his essay "Of Cannibals," challenged prevailing stereotypes by presenting indigenous peoples as embodiments of certain virtues. I will argue that Montaigne does not merely describe the inhabitants of the New World but mobilizes their image as a rhetorical device through which European norms are destabilized and re-evaluated. His work encouraged readers to reconsider the designation of "savage" and question the assumed superiority of European civilization. I will analyze the representations of the "savage" in the writings of Montaigne, and emphasize his critiques of European society. I will situate Montaigne within the intellectual genealogy of the "noble savage," later associated with Jean-Jacques Rousseau, while underscoring a crucial distinction. In Montaigne, the cannibal is not a moral ideal grounded in a theory of natural goodness, but a skeptical instrument that reveals the contingency of cultural norms. His treatment of otherness is thus less utopian than critical, rooted in epistemological modesty and moral skepticism.

Keywords: *Montaigne, otherness, cannibals, noble savage*

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Author's presentation:

Ștefan Viorel Ghenea is an Associate Professor at University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, and he was a postdoctoral researcher at Romanian Academy (2014-2015). He holds a B.A. in Psychology (2011), a

B.A. in Philosophy and Sociology (2002), M.A. in Contemporary Philosophy (2006), and in Clinical Psychology (2020), and a PhD. in Philosophy at University of West of Timisoara. Autor of the books: *Social Psychology* (2023), *Religious Imaginary, and the Hermeneutics of Symbols* (2020), *European Identity, Cultural Difference and Collective Imaginary* (2015), *Realism and Pragmatism in Contemporary Philosophy* (2015), *Introduction to Philosophy* (2011), and coordinator of the volumes: *Visual Cultures and Imaginary Spaces* (2019), *Human and Technology: Reality, Imaginary and Discourse* (2015), *Human and Nature. Contemporary Philosophical Perspectives on Human-Nature Relations* (2012). Research interest: philosophy and history of imaginary and mentalities, cultural identities, cinematographic imaginary, philosophical approaches on psychology and psychopathology.

Assessing the Political and Legal Implications of the UN Security Council Resolutions in Supporting Justice Mechanisms in Conflict Zones

Cosmin Lucian Gherghe

University of Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

This paper analyses the regulations set forth by several UN Security Council Resolutions in its meetings regarding the situation in conflict zones. The analysis aims to focus on the principles and mandate of peacekeeping missions, underlying security challenges, institutional assistance, solutions to the challenges and political processes. Thus the research follows its main objective of highlighting the political and legal implications of the UN Security Council Resolutions in supporting justice mechanisms in conflict zones: promoting peace and political stability, security, justice, protection of human rights, humanitarian assistance, socio-economic recovery. The conclusions underscore the institutionalized authority and mandate delivered through UN Security Council Resolutions to enhance the political and security context that enforces peacekeeping and justice mechanisms, the protection of civilians, humanitarian law and assistance to victims.

Keywords: *UN Security Council Resolution, justice mechanisms, political stability, national security, humanitarian action.*

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Author’s presentation:

Cosmin Lucian Gherghe, Ph.D. is Associate Professor at the Political Sciences Specialization, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova. He holds a Ph.D. degree in History (2008) from the Faculty of History, Geography and Philosophy, University of Craiova and a B.A. in Political Sciences (2003) from the Faculty of History, Geography and Philosophy, University of Craiova and in Law (1999) from the Faculty of Law and Administrative Sciences, University of Craiova. He is the author of over 40 articles, studies and papers published in scientific journals or presented in national and international conferences. He is the author of “Emanoil Chinezu – Om politic, avocat și istoric”, Editura Sitech, Craiova, 2009 and (co-author) “Partidele politice”, Editura Sitech, Craiova, 2008. His areas of interest include political parties, constitutional law, administrative and political institutions. He is member of 3 research projects/grants and also a member of the editorial board of *Revista de Științe Politice/Revue des Sciences Politiques*. ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9131-0391>.

A Comparative Analysis of the Legal Status of Political Parties in European Democracies

Cosmin Lucian Gherghe

University of Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The study investigates the legal status of political parties across European democracies. The main objective is to follow the differences among the legal statuses of political parties and to assess the manner in which they are influenced by party systems in selected countries. The study employs a comparative methodology focusing on the general context and relevant characteristics for the analysis, constitutional norms and legislative regulations, other indicators and relevant data, structure of party systems and democracy indicators. The study concludes on the similarities and differences to explain the variation among selected cases.

Keywords: *political parties, democracy, comparative analysis, party system.*

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Author’s presentation:

Cosmin Lucian Gherghe, Ph.D. is Associate Professor at the Political Sciences Specialization, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova. He holds a Ph.D. degree in History (2008) from the Faculty of History, Geography and Philosophy, University of Craiova and a B.A. in Political Sciences (2003) from the Faculty of History, Geography and Philosophy, University of Craiova and in Law (1999) from the Faculty of Law and Administrative Sciences, University of Craiova. He is the author of over 30 articles, studies and papers published in scientific journals or presented in national and international

conferences. He is the author of “Emanoil Chinezu – Om politic, avocat și istoric”, Editura Sitech, Craiova, 2009 and (co-author) “Partidele politice”, Editura Sitech, Craiova, 2008. His areas of interest include political parties, constitutional law, administrative and political institutions. He is member of 3 research projects/grants and also a member of the editorial board of *Revista de Științe Politice/Revue des Sciences Politiques*. ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9131-0391>.

Defense strategies in civil proceedings

Daniel Ghiță

University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The dynamics of the civil trial allow and sometimes even require the reevaluation of defense strategies. On the other hand, the principles and rules governing the trial in appeals restrict the parties' ability to extend the limits set for the trial. In this context, the modification of the defense strategy after the first instance ruling or the total change of defenses must be examined from the perspective of admissibility.

Keywords: *remedies in civil trial, limits of retrial, new defences*

Author presentation:

Daniel Ghiță has been deputy dean of the Faculty of Law, University of Craiova, since 2008. He is a professor, PhD holder, doctoral supervisor and holder of the Civil Procedural Law course. He is the author or co-author of over 15 books, coursebooks or monographs, over 50 articles and studies published in journals indexed in international databases or highly prestigious scientific journals in the field of legal sciences. He has participated in over 40 national or international scientific events.

Rule of law standards

George Liviu Gîrleşteanu

University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

Rule of Law standards are a set of fundamental principles that ensure that all members of a society (including the government) are subject to the law, which is applied equally, impartially and transparently. These standards are essential for democracy and the protection of fundamental rights. The main standards and principles analyzed include: Legality, Legal certainty, Prohibition of arbitrary exercise of power, Independence and impartiality of courts, Judicial review, Equality before the law, Separation of powers in the state.

Keywords: *rule of law, legal certainty, equality before the law, non-discrimination, access to justice, independence of the judiciary.*

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Author's presentation:

GÎRLEȘTEANU George is Professor Ph.D. and Vice-Dean at University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, and coordinator of Ph. theses in the area of Constitutional Law since 2015. The research areas of Professor GÎRLEȘTEANU are Constitutional Law and Human Rights. In his professional carrier, Professor GÎRLEȘTEANU published 12 books and 70 articles. Also, he participated in 35 national and international conferences and was coordinator/member in 11 national or international research grants. Professor GÎRLEȘTEANU is Visiting Professor at Université de Bourgogne, Faculté de Droit et Science Politiques, Dijon, France (2009-2014) and has performed a 2 months Post Ph.D. mobility stage in Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Scholl of Law, Thessaloniki, Greece. Major scientific contributions: 1. Constitutional Law and Political Institutions, Universul Juridic PH, Bucharest, 2012, ISBN 978-973-127-604-5; 2. The Fundamental Right to Economic Freedom: Legal Consequences, International Journal of Business and Management Studies, ISSN 2158-1479, Volume 01, Number 01 (2012), p. 225-238. ORCID ID: 0009-0007-7498-1509

Emergency Powers and The Rule of Law: Theoretical Reflections and Legal Realities

George Liviu Gîrleşteanu

University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Department of Public Law, Romania

Iohan-Andrei Ghibu

University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Department of Public Law, Romania

Abstract:

This paper investigates the enduring tension between states of exception and constitutional frameworks, seeking to understand how democratic societies can effectively manage crises such as terrorism, pandemics, or war, without undermining the very legal and institutional norms that define them. Drawing upon a range of theoretical perspectives on sovereignty, legality, and exceptionality, including the works of Carl Schmitt, Giorgio Agamben, and contemporary constitutional theorists, the study critically examines the legal and political implications of emergency powers.

Keywords: *State of exception, Rule of law, Emergency powers, Sovereignty, Fundamental rights.*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work.

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Authors' presentation:

GÎRLEȘTEANU George is Professor Ph.D. and Vice-Dean at University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, and coordinator of Ph. theses in the area of Constitutional Law since 2015. The research areas of Professor GÎRLEȘTEANU are Constitutional Law and Human Rights. In his professional carrier, Professor GÎRLEȘTEANU published 12 books and 70 articles. Also, he participated in 35 national and international conferences

and was coordinator/member in 11 national or international research grants. Professor GİRLEŞTEANU is Visiting Professor at Université de Bourgogne, Faculté de Droit et Science Politiques, Dijon, France (2009-2014) and has performed a 2 months Post Ph.D. mobility stage in Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Scholl of Law, Thessaloniki, Greece. Major scientific contributions: 1. Constitutional Law and Political Institutions, Universul Juridic PH, Bucharest, 2012, ISBN 978-973-127-604-5; 2. The Fundamental Right to Economic Freedom: Legal Consequences, International Journal of Business and Management Studies, ISSN 2158-1479, Volume 01, Number 01 (2012), p. 225-238. ORCID ID: 0009-0007-7498-1509

Ghibu Iohan-Andrei - University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Department of Public Law, Romania.

Global models of digital governance and their adaptation in Romania: International lessons and implementation pathways

Diana-Maria Grosu

"Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași, Iași, Romania

Abstract:

Digital governance has become a cornerstone of public administration modernization, providing new tools for efficiency, transparency, and civic participation. **The scope** of this research is to propose a contextualized adaptation framework for applying global models within the Romanian administrative system. **The central question** guiding this research is: to what extent can the global model of digital governance be adapted to the Romanian context in order to strengthen administrative efficiency, information security, and citizens' trust in the state? To address this, the research employs a **qualitative comparative methodology**, analyzing the models of Estonia (interoperability), Denmark (citizen services), and Singapore (strategic coordination) against Romanian policy documents, such as the National Strategy on the Digital Agenda and the activity of the Authority for the Digitalization of Romania (ADR). **The analysis answers** the central question by demonstrating that while Romania has made progress, its adaptation is currently hindered more by institutional fragmentation and limited interoperability than by technological gaps. Drawing from these findings, **the study concludes** that successful adaptation is not merely a technological upgrade but a foundational prerequisite for institutional reform. **Finally**, achieving this requires strict alignment with European standards (NIS 2, eIDAS, GDPR) to ensure democratic accountability and increase public trust in the digital state.

Keywords: *digital governance, Romania, interoperability, public administration, institutional reform, public trust.*

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Author’s presentation:

I am a graduate of the Faculty of Philosophy and Social and Political Sciences, specializing in International Relations and European Studies (Class of 2019), the Master's program in Public Policy and Institutional Management (Class of 2021), and the Faculty of Law (Class of 2022), all within "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași. Currently, I am a third-year PhD student at the Faculty of Philosophy and Social-Political Sciences, specializing in Political Science. Publications: Risks and Opportunities of Smart Education, published in RSP 86/2025 – Political Theory and Social Interaction in the Digital Era; Teachers’ Perspectives on the Digitalization of Education, published in RSP 86/2025 – Political Theory and Social Interaction in the Digital Era; Digital governance in education: between the promise of inclusion and the risk of exclusion - published in RSP 88/2025 – Political Theory and Social Interaction in the Digital Era; Period Poverty, Pioneers and Laggards. Case Study: Scotland and New Zealand vs Romania, published in Scientific Annals of “Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, Volume XVIII/1, Sociology and Social Work, 2025. ORCID ID: 0009-0002-8256-7600

Cybersecurity and institutional trust in digital governance: lessons from Romania and the European Union

Diana-Maria Grosu

"Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași, Iași, Romania

Abstract:

The accelerated digitization of public administration in Romania and the European Union offers new perspectives for efficiency, but simultaneously intensifies structural risks associated with cybersecurity. **The scope** of this research is to evaluate the interdependence between cybersecurity performance and the dynamics of institutional trust. **The central question** guiding this research examines to what extent cybersecurity acts as a pillar for strengthening trust or, conversely, generates new forms of vulnerability and institutional exclusion. To this end, the research employs a **comparative policy analysis** framework, triangulating data from public policy documents, institutional reports, and national and European cyber incident databases. **The study highlights** the main threats (ransomware, DDoS, cyber espionage) and structural vulnerabilities affecting institutional response. **The analysis answers** the central question by demonstrating that in Romania, trust is undermined not by the threats themselves, but by fragmented inter-institutional coordination and a diffusion of responsibilities. Drawing from these findings, **the study concludes** that personal data protection is an implicit pact whose breach directly affects the legitimacy of institutions. **Finally**, the research argues for strategic alignment with European directives (NIS 2, GDPR) to transform cybersecurity into a tool for institutional integrity rather than a systemic vulnerability.

Keywords: *digital governance; cybersecurity; institutional trust; public administration; Romania, European Union*

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Author's presentation:

I am a graduate of the Faculty of Philosophy and Social and Political Sciences, specializing in International Relations and European Studies (Class of 2019), the Master's program in Public Policy and Institutional Management (Class of 2021), and the Faculty of Law (Class of 2022), all within "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași. Currently, I am a third-year PhD student at the Faculty of Philosophy and Social-Political Sciences, specializing in Political Science. Publications: Risks and Opportunities of Smart Education, published in RSP 86/2025 – Political Theory and Social Interaction in the Digital Era; Teachers' Perspectives on the Digitalization of Education, published in RSP 86/2025 – Political Theory and Social Interaction in the Digital Era; Digital governance in education: between the promise of inclusion and the risk of exclusion - published in RSP 88/2025 – Political Theory and Social Interaction in the Digital Era; Period Poverty, Pioneers and Laggards. Case Study: Scotland and New Zealand vs Romania, published in Scientific Annals of "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași, Volume XVIII/1, Sociology and Social Work, 2025. ORCID ID: 0009-0002-8256-7600.

Digital governance in education: between the promise of inclusion and the risk of exclusion

Diana-Maria Grosu

"Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași, Iași, Romania

Ioan-Sebastian Buduroi

"Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași, Iași, Romania

Victor Stoica

"Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași, Iași, Romania

Abstract:

This article examines the dynamics of digital governance in education as a profound transformation that is reshaping the relationships between educational institutions, state authorities, and individual educational actors. The research question is clearly stated from the outset: how can digital governance facilitate inclusion, or conversely, lead to structural exclusion within education systems? Beginning with the transition from traditional administration to contemporary governance models, the study explores how digital technologies are transforming decision-making processes, mechanisms of accountability, and resource allocation in educational systems. The methodology combines an analysis of data from European educational reforms and international digital policy frameworks, through a conceptual lens focused on equity and knowledge. By adopting this dual conceptual approach, the study demonstrates how digital governance can support inclusion, yet also contribute to the emergence of structural inequalities. Ultimately, this article argues that digital governance in

education is a contested terrain, where the promise of inclusion coexists with the structural threats of exclusion, emphasizing the need for a critical and reflexive perspective.

Keywords: *edTech governance, digital equity, marginalized learners, educational policy, challenges.*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work.

Authors' presentation:

Diana-Maria Grosu: Third-year PhD student in Political Science – Faculty of Philosophy and Social and Political Sciences, "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași. ORCID ID: 0009-0002-8256-7600

Ioan Sebastian Buduroi: Associate Professor, PhD - Department of Political Sciences, International Relations and European Studies - "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași. ORCID ID: 0009-0007-0146-8907

Victor Stoica: Assistant Professor, PhD - Department of Sociology, Social Work and Human Resources - "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași. ORCID ID: 0009-0001-7244-647X

Managerial Myopia and Sustainable Urban Governance: Legal Perspectives on Environmental Protection in Romanian Local Administration

Adrian-Barbu Ilie

University of Craiova/Faculty of law, Craiova, România

Abstract:

The development of modern societies leads to a lot of new challenges, like urban governance increasingly facing the need of reconciling short-term political decision-making with the long-term requirements of sustainable urban development. This paper start exploring a phenomenon commonly described in managerial literature as *managerial myopia* and examines its relevance in the context of local public administration in Romania. It does not treat managerial myopia as a normative accusation against state authorities, but the study approaches it as a structural feature generated by a lot of factors starting from incomplete and inconsistent legislation to electoral cycles, annual budgeting practices, and fragmented institutional responsibilities. Based on large Romanian cites, but basically applying to the majority of European cities, the paper analyses how these structural constraints may influence urban policies related to environmental protection, infrastructure development, and strategic planning. The study examines the current Romanian legislative framework governing local administration, urban planning, and environmental protection, identifying both the institutional limitations that may encourage short-term decision-making and the legal instruments that can support long-term governance. The paper further discusses recent social and institutional developments, including European urban policies, sustainability frameworks, and participatory governance mechanisms, which provide new opportunities for mitigating the effects of managerial myopia at the local level. The article concludes that while managerial myopia remains a structural risk within urban governance systems, existing legislative tools and evolving governance practices offer viable pathways for strengthening long-term decision-making in Romanian local administration.

Keywords: *Managerial Myopia, Sustainable Development, Environmental Protection, Urban Governance, Local Public Administration, Environmental Governance*

Author's presentation:

Adrian-Barbu Ilie is a lawyer, Doctor of Law and associate professor at the Faculty of Law of the University of Craiova. Environmental law and Civil law are its fields of research. He has published alone or as a co-author 7 books and more than 20 articles. ORCID ID: 0009-0009-7319-0494

Olympic Peace Made in Russia: The Soviet Union and the Russian Federation in the Olympic Movement

Rafał Jung

*Political Theory and Political Thought (Sports Policy Research Group),
Faculty of International and Political Studies, University of Lodz, Łódź,
Poland*

Abstract:

In the last two decades, the international Olympic movement, alongside the Islamic terrorist threat, has primarily blamed Russians for violating the Olympic peace. In reference to the perverted tradition of disrupting the peace of the Olympics with aggressive political actions from the period of Soviet Russia and the USSR, such as the war with Poland in 1920 (implications for the Antwerp 1920 Olympics), the intervention in Hungary in 1956 (in the context of Melbourne 1956), Czechoslovakia in 1968 (the Mexico City 1968 Olympics), and Afghanistan in 1979 (the adverse consequences for the Moscow 1980 Olympics), modern Putin's Russia also uses the time of the Olympic games to pursue particular political interests on the international stage. This is evident in the examples of the 2008 Beijing Summer Olympics (aggression against Georgia), the 2014 Sochi Winter Olympics (the beginning of the war in Ukraine and its implications after the full-scale aggression in 2022, primarily for the Summer Olympics in Paris 2024 and the Winter Olympics 2026 in Milan/Cortina). The presentation will focus on the policies of the Soviet Union and the Russian Federation regarding sports mega-events organized by the International Olympic Committee, the Summer and Winter Olympic Games. This will confirm the hypothesis that the undemocratic Russian state, regardless of its system of government, cynically treats sports in its politics.

Keywords: *sports policy, Olympics, IOC, the Soviet Union, the Russian Federation*

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Author's presentation:

PhD, Research areas: history of the XX-XXI century, sports policy, history of the sport, Polish-German relations; author of the monograph *The history of the German Legation and Embassy in Warsaw 1918–1939*, Łódź 2012; co-editor of the monographs *Sport and politics*, Łódź 2018; and *Political forms of sport*, Poznań 2020; and several dozen articles on the above issues, including: *Józef Piłsudski - protector of Polish football?*, [in:] *Józef Piłsudski. Man-Soldier-Politician*, ed. Z. Girzyński and J. Kłaczek, Toruń 2016; *Around 'the Water Battle of Frankfurt'. On the Political Dimension of the Polish Football Team's Performance in the 1974 World Cup*, „*Przegląd Zachodni*” 2017, no. Spec. II; *Polish football in Hitler's shadow. Political implications of the rivalry between the football teams of the Second Republic of Poland and the Third Reich*, „*Przegląd Zachodni*” 2024, special issue; *UEFA Euro 2012 - the first big sporting project in Poland after communism*, „*Revista de Științe Politice. Revue des Sciences Politiques*” 2024, No. 81. ORCID ID: 0000-0003-3721-8559

Post-Crisis Governance and Bank Risk-Taking in Europe

Matei Kacso-Carstocea

*National University of Political Studies and Public Administration (SNSPA),
Bucharest, Romania*

Lucian Claudiu Anghel

*National University of Political Studies and Public Administration (SNSPA),
Bucharest, Romania*

Abstract:

This study explores the relationship between governance standards and the risk-taking behavior of European banks, focusing on those listed on stock markets, and considering the regulatory changes that followed the financial crisis. In light of the governance deficiencies observed during the global financial crisis and the subsequent COVID-19 epidemic, this research underscores risk management as the primary objective of bank governance, above the pursuit of short-term profitability. This study employs fixed-effects regressions to analyze bank-level panel data. The data comes from the European Banking Authority's (EBA) EU-wide Transparency Exercise, covering the years 2021 to 2024. This study aims to investigate if stronger governance, as represented by the Common Equity Tier 1 (CET1) capital ratio, is associated to less risk on the balance sheet, which is evaluated by the leverage ratio. The results demonstrate a strong and statistically

significant association between a bank's governance and its willingness to take risks. Specifically, a higher level of capitalization is associated to a much lower level of risk. In contrast, a strong association between governance variables and profitability indicators is not identified. The data imply that European banks mainly utilize prudential approaches to manage their operations, which helps to limit excessive risk-taking. This study adds to the previous research on bank governance, especially focusing on findings related to risk. Moreover, our analysis gives vital information for regulators and policymakers who are worried about the financial stability of the European banking system.

Keywords: *Corporate Governance, Financial Regulation, Bank risk-taking, European banking sector, Banking stability, Bank performance*

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Authors' Contributions: Lucian Claudiu Anghel

Author's presentation:

Matei Kacso-Carstocea is a Master's graduate in Programs and Investments Management at SNSPA Bucharest, ranked top of his class, with academic experience at the University of Insubria (Italy) through the Erasmus program. His research interests focus on corporate governance, financial regulation, banking stability, and risk management in the European banking sector. He is now a student of the Doctoral School of SNSPA. Fluent in five languages, he is particularly interested in the intersection of governance standards and financial performance, aiming to contribute to research and policy discussions on banking stability and prudent risk-taking in Europe.

Lucian Claudiu Anghel – Professor, PhD, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration (SNSPA), Bucharest, Romania

The Impact of the Right of Access Principle on Determining the Applicable Law in Cross-Border Insolvency Proceedings: A Comparative Analytical Study

Muhammed Khqairy Qsair

Universtiy of Thi-Qar / college of law / department of private law, ALnassiriy, Thi-Qar, Iraq

Abstract:

This research provides a comprehensive and critical analysis of the "Right of Access" principle and its profound influence on the mechanisms of determining the applicable law within the complex framework of cross-border insolvency. In an era of globalized financial markets, insolvency proceedings frequently transcend national borders, creating significant legal friction between the territorial sovereignty of states and the necessity for a unified, global judicial response. The central problem addressed in this study is how the procedural right of an foreign representative or creditor to access a local court fundamentally alters the choice-of-law rules, shifting the focus from the traditional *Lex Fori Concursus* (law of the opening court) toward a more integrated approach centered on the "Center of Main Interests" (COMI). The study is structured into four extensive sections. It begins by tracing the historical evolution of insolvency law, moving from the era of "Strict

Territorialism"—where foreign creditors were often marginalized—to the modern era of "Modified Universalism" championed by the 1997 UNCITRAL Model Law. The research argues that the Right of Access is not merely a formal gateway to the courtroom but a substantive pillar of procedural justice that forces national courts to recognize and apply foreign legal standards to preserve the value of the debtor's estate. Through a detailed examination of landmark cases, such as *In re Eurofood IFSC Ltd* and *In re Bear Stearns*, the paper demonstrates how courts balance the "Right of Access" against the risks of strategic "Forum Shopping".

The researcher's perspective, woven throughout the analysis, highlights that while the Right of Access enhances transparency and fairness, it must be tempered by the "Legitimate Expectations" of the parties to prevent legal ambiguity. The findings suggest that the future of international insolvency lies in a "Transnational Public Policy" that narrows the grounds for refusing to apply foreign law. Finally, the research concludes with a series of legislative recommendations aimed at Middle Eastern jurisdictions, advocating for the elimination of strict reciprocity requirements and the adoption of digital judicial protocols to facilitate seamless cross-border cooperation and legal certainty.

Keywords: *Cross-Border Insolvency, Right of Access, Applicable Law, Choice of Law, Center of Main Interests (COMI), UNCITRAL Model Law, Modified Universalism, Forum Shopping*

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Author's presentation:

Assistant Professor at the College of Law, University of Dhi Qar. Works as an instructor of Private International Law for undergraduate students. Works as an instructor of Private International Law for postgraduate students (PhD and Master's). Holds a PhD from the Faculty of Law, University of Bucharest, for his dissertation entitled: *The Legal regime of Punitive damages in Iraqi and Romanian Law: A Comparative Study*.

Emotions in Politics: The Anti-Immigrant Discourse of the Radical Right Vox Party in Spain

Stanislaw Kosmyka

University of Lodz, Faculty of International and Political Studies, Lodz, Poland

Abstract:

This paper examines the phenomenon of the crystallization of the radical right on the Spanish political scene in the context of the Vox party. It explores the political and social conditions influencing the emergence of this formation, as well as its key postulates. It shows the discursive dimensions at which Vox incorporated nationalist and nativist themes into its narrative. The article analyzes the rationale for support for this group and presents the social profile of its voters. In diagnosing the Vox phenomenon, the paper draws on Casa Mudde's understanding of the radical right. The main conclusion drawn from this observation is that, after years of absence from the Spanish political scene, a radical right-wing party has managed to emerge. Its message resonated with voters representing anti-establishment attitudes and disillusioned with the traditional political system. The paper highlights the discursive threads of the Vox party that refer to conservative, anti-immigrant (including Islamophobic) attitudes, revive historical resentments, and critically perceive the development of a multicultural society, seeing it as a threat to traditionally understood values and culture of Spain.

Keywords: *Spain, Vox party, radical right, nationalism, identity, immigrants*

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Author’s presentation:

Dr hab. **Stanisław Kosmyńka**, is an Associate Professor of the University of Lodz, Faculty of the International and Political Studies. Author of two monographs: *Od Boga do terroru. Rola religii w ideologii dżihadyzmu na przykładzie organizacji Al-Kaida* (2012), *Święta wojna w Al-Ándalus. Przeobrażenia aktywności dżihadystycznych komórek terrorystycznych w Hiszpanii w latach 1995–2012* (2015). and numerous articles published in scientific journals. His research interests focus primarily on the mechanisms of jihadist terrorism in Spain. In this context, he analyses the processes of violent radicalisation among representatives of Muslim communities in Spain and the preventive measures. He also examines the political and social processes of contemporary Spain. In 2009–2014 Stanisław Kosmyńka was a visiting professor in Spain in the Universities of Granada, Santiago de Compostela, La Laguna and Vic. ORCID ID: 0000-0003-4131-4762

Rien ne pousse à l’ombre des grands arbres: Constantin Brâncuși and the Politics of Cultural Heritage

Selma Kozak

Kütahya Dumlupınar University, Faculty of Fine Arts, Department of Visual Communication Design, Kütahya, Turkey

Abstract:

The year 2026 marks the global commemoration of Constantin Brâncuși’s 150th birth anniversary. Constantin Brâncuși (1876-1957) stands as one of the founding figures of modern and avant-garde art. He transformed 20th-century modernism through an abstractive approach to form, establishing an original and distinctive artistic style. Consequently, a reassessment of Brâncuși’s aesthetic legacy assumes critical significance, demanding renewed analysis within both cultural and political frameworks.

Brâncuși began his artistic education at the Craiova School of Arts and Crafts in Romania, before relocating to France and spending the majority of his life at the center of the modernist art milieu in Paris. While Brâncuși positioned himself at the heart of international modernism, he simultaneously became an emblematic figure of Romanian national identity. During the communist period, the artist was approached with caution due to the tensions between abstract art and the regime’s ideologically framed conception of art. However, in the post-communist era, he was reappropriated as a strategic reference point in the reconstruction of cultural

heritage. Brâncuși's contemporary significance within the realm of cultural heritage stems from his position as an Eastern European artist at the core of Western modernism and his symbolic role in the global redefinition of Romania's cultural legitimacy; as such, he constitutes a figure whose work warrants analysis within the ideological intersections of contemporary art and cultural memory.

This study aims to examine Brâncuși's artistic practice within the framework of the ideological framing of cultural heritage and its post-communist reinterpretation. It seeks to analyze Brâncuși's vision through the lenses of modernism, visual culture, cultural heritage policies, cultural memory, and public art, adopting a detailed and multifaceted approach. The artist's formal investigations, abstractive methodology, atelier organization, photographic production, and exhibition strategies will be explored through selected examples, with particular attention to his public artworks, including the Constantin Brâncuși Ensemble of Monuments in Târgu Jiu, inscribed as a UNESCO World Heritage Site in 2024. In this way, the study discusses how Brâncuși's legacy has been repositioned within the interplay between national and global visual cultures in the post-communist era.

Keywords: *Constantin Brâncuși, Cultural Heritage, Avantgard Art, Public Art, Modern Sculpture Art*

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Author's presentation:

Selma Kozak, an academic, graphic designer and a multidisciplinary artist graduated from the Department of Graphic Design at the Faculty of Fine Arts, Dumlupınar University, Turkey, in 2011. In 2022, I completed my doctoral studies at the Institute of Fine Arts, Dokuz Eylül University, with a dissertation titled "Environmental Graphic Design and Public Installation in the Context of 21st Century Postmodernism." Between 2019 and 2020, I continued my doctoral research as a Visiting Researcher at Yale University,

Yale School of Art, Graphic Design (MFA) Department, working under the supervision of Prof. Sheila Levrant de Bretteville. During this research period, I exhibited my public installation “Things Inside Me / Gaslighting” (2019) in New Haven, Connecticut, and later showed it for a second time at the Long Wharf Theatre in New Haven, upon invitation from Nasty Women Connecticut. There is a substantial body of published articles, book chapters, and conference papers available at the international level. My recent works and publications focus on public installations, installation design and art, exhibition design, environmental graphic design, graphic design, feminist design, new media, and digital installations. In addition, my current research and publications explore posthumanism and posthumanist design. ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0469-5922.

Energy Output and (De)industrialisation: Redefining the Socio-Economic and Cultural Fabric of the World’s Three Major Blocs (EU, US and China)

Lăpădat Lavinia Costinel
University of Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

Energy production has become a decisive factor shaping the economic competitiveness and industrial development of major global powers. This paper examines the relationship between energy output and processes of industrialisation and deindustrialisation in the world’s three major economic blocs: the European Union, the United States, and China. While the United States has strengthened its position through increased domestic energy production, particularly in oil and natural gas, China continues to expand its energy capacity to sustain large-scale industrial growth. In contrast, the European Union faces significant challenges related to energy dependency, rising costs, and energy transition policies, which may influence its industrial competitiveness. These differences in energy availability and strategy are redefining not only industrial production but also the broader socio-economic and cultural fabric of these regions. The study argues that energy output and energy policy will play a crucial role in shaping future patterns of industrial development, labour markets, and geopolitical influence among these three global economic blocs.

Keywords: *the European Union, the United States, China; industrialisation; global economy; energy policy.*

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Author's presentation:

Lăpădat Lavinu Costinel is a doctor of philology, and an Assistant Professor at the University of Craiova, Faculty of Letters, Department of Romanian Language and Literature since 2014. He teaches Romanian as a foreign language in the Preparatory Year at the University of Craiova. He is interested and specialised in exploring the issue of interculturality and the manner in which it impacts the teaching of Romanian as a foreign language. ORCID ID: 0000-0001-6107-1011.

Integrating Romanian Culture and Civilisation in Language Instruction for Foreign Students

Lăpădat Lavinu Costinel
University of Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

Teaching Romanian as a Second Language (RSL) requires not only the development of linguistic competence but also the understanding of the cultural and civilizational context in which the language is used. This paper emphasizes the importance of integrating elements of Romanian culture and civilization as an effective instrument in teaching Romanian to foreign students. Cultural aspects such as traditions, historical references, literature, social norms, and everyday practices provide meaningful contexts that facilitate language comprehension and communication. By incorporating authentic cultural materials into language instruction, teachers can increase students' motivation, enhance intercultural awareness, and support the acquisition of vocabulary and pragmatic language use. Furthermore, exposure to Romanian cultural values and social conventions helps foreign students better understand the linguistic nuances of the language and adapt more easily to the Romanian academic and social environment. The study highlights that combining linguistic instruction with cultural content significantly contributes to the effectiveness of teaching Romanian as a second language.

Keywords: *Romanian as a second language (RSL); culture and civilisation; intercultural competence; language teaching; foreign students.*

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Author's presentation:

Lăpădat Laviniu Costinel is a doctor of philology, and an Assistant Professor at the University of Craiova, Faculty of Letters, Department of Romanian Language and Literature since 2014. He teaches Romanian as a foreign language in the Preparatory Year at the University of Craiova. He is interested and specialised in exploring the issue of interculturality and the manner in which it impacts the teaching of Romanian as a foreign language. ORCID ID: 0000-0001-6107-1011.

The AI Revolution: Friend or Foe in Higher Education and the Subsequent Job Market Integration

Lăpădat Laviniu Costinel
University of Craiova, Romania

Lăpădat Maria-Magdalena
University of Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The rapid development of artificial intelligence (AI) has generated significant debate regarding its role in higher education and its potential impact on students' future integration into the job market. This paper explores the opportunities and challenges that AI technologies bring to the teaching and learning process in universities. On the one hand, AI tools can support personalized learning, facilitate access to information, and assist students in developing research, writing, and problem-solving skills. On the other hand, concerns have emerged regarding academic integrity, overreliance on automated systems, and the possible decline of critical thinking and independent learning. The study examines how AI is reshaping pedagogical practices and influencing the competencies required in the contemporary

labour market. Particular attention is given to the need for educators to adapt teaching strategies and promote responsible and ethical use of AI technologies. The paper argues that, when used appropriately, AI can function as a valuable educational ally rather than a threat.

Keywords: *artificial intelligence (AI); higher education; teaching and learning; academic integrity; job market integration.*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work.

Author's presentation:

Lăpădat Lavinia Costinel is a doctor of philology, and an Assistant Professor at the University of Craiova, Faculty of Letters, Department of Romanian Language and Literature since 2014. He teaches Romanian as a foreign language in the Preparatory Year at the University of Craiova. He is interested and specialised in exploring the issue of interculturality and the manner in which it impacts the teaching of Romanian as a foreign language. ORCID ID: 0000-0001-6107-1011.

Lăpădat Maria-Magdalena is a doctor of philology, and an Assistant Professor at the University of Craiova, Faculty of Letters, Department of Modern Languages since 2015. She teaches English and French at the Faculty of Law at the University of Craiova. Her scientific activity is solid, as evidenced by her numerous publications in the field. ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2299-4977.

Classical Legacy vs. Modern Dissemination in Teaching English for Psychology Students: From Freud and Jung to Jordan Peterson

Lăpădat Maria-Magdalena
University of Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

This paper examines the pedagogical value of integrating both classical and contemporary psychological figures in teaching English for Psychology students within an English for Specific Purposes (ESP) framework. Classical theorists such as Sigmund Freud and Carl Gustav Jung represent foundational pillars of modern psychology, whose theories on the unconscious, personality, and archetypes continue to influence psychological discourse and academic terminology. Their work provides reliable conceptual frameworks and specialized vocabulary essential for psychology students' academic literacy. In contrast, contemporary psychologists such as Jordan Peterson reach wider modern audiences through digital media, public lectures, and popular publications, demonstrating new forms of psychological dissemination and communication. By combining classical theoretical sources with modern communicative models, ESP courses can expose students both to traditional academic discourse and to contemporary forms of psychological communication. This approach supports the development of specialized vocabulary, critical thinking, and academic communication skills while also illustrating how psychological ideas evolve and circulate in modern public discourse.

Keywords: *English for Specific Purposes (ESP); psychology education; Freud; Jung; Jordan Peterson.*

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Author's presentation:

Lăpădat Maria-Magdalena is a doctor of philology, and an Assistant Professor at the University of Craiova, Faculty of Letters, Department of Modern Languages since 2015. She teaches English and French at the Faculty of Law at the University of Craiova. Her scientific activity is solid, as

evidenced by her numerous publications in the field. ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2299-4977.

Specialized Vocabulary and Academic Communication Skills in English for Psychology: An ESP-Based Approach

Lăpădat Maria-Magdalena
University of Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

English for Specific Purposes (ESP) plays an important role in helping psychology students develop the linguistic skills required for academic communication in their field. This paper examines an ESP-based approach to developing specialized vocabulary and academic communication skills in English for Psychology courses. The study focuses on the integration of discipline-specific terminology, reading activities based on psychological texts, and tasks that promote both written and oral academic communication. Particular emphasis is placed on contextualized vocabulary learning and the use of authentic materials that reflect the language of psychology. These strategies aim to support students in understanding and using key psychological concepts and terminology commonly encountered in academic discourse. The findings indicate that combining language instruction with subject-related content improves students' academic literacy and confidence in using English within their discipline. The study highlights the importance of ESP methodologies in facilitating the acquisition of specialized vocabulary and enhancing communication skills in psychology-focused academic contexts.

Keywords: *English for Specific Purposes (ESP); English for Psychology; specialized vocabulary; communication skills.*

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Author's presentation:

Lăpădat Maria-Magdalena is a doctor of philology, and an Assistant Professor at the University of Craiova, Faculty of Letters, Department of Modern Languages since 2015. She teaches English and French at the Faculty of Law at the University of Craiova. Her scientific activity is solid, as evidenced by her numerous publications in the field. ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2299-4977.

The Cairo Negotiations in SOE. Documents from Spring and Summer 1944

Stoica Lascu

Academia Oamenilor de Știință din România/ The Academy of Romanian Scientists, Constanța, Romania

Marian Zidaru

Asociația „Casa Mării Negre”/ Black Sea House, Constanța, Romania

Abstract:

From the summer of 1943 until the following spring, on the Eastern Front, the German armies were constantly pushed back towards the borders of Romania. The futile grinding of Romanian troops made more politicians in Romania think about actions to take the country out of the war. The key figure was Iuliu Maniu, the leader of the democratic opposition. At the end of 1943, the Western Allies had accepted Maniu's proposal to send a representative for negotiations. He had proposed Prince Barbu Știrbei, who, in February 1944, was sent to Cairo, where the headquarters of the Allied Command for the Middle East was located. He was to be followed, in May, by the diplomat Constantin Vișoianu. The prince's departure was made with the approval of Ion Antonescu, with whom he had discussed the matter before the trip. From the summer of 1943 until the following spring, on the Eastern Front, the German armies were constantly pushed back towards the borders of Romania. The futile grinding of Romanian troops made more politicians in Romania think about actions to take the country out of the war. The key figure was Iuliu Maniu, the leader of the democratic opposition. At the end of 1943, the Western Allies had accepted Maniu's proposal to send a representative for negotiations. He had proposed Prince Barbu Știrbei, who, in February 1944, was sent to Cairo, where the headquarters of the Allied Command for the Middle East was located. He was to be followed, in May, by the diplomat Constantin Vișoianu. The prince's departure was made with the approval of Ion Antonescu, with whom he had discussed the matter before the trip.

Keywords: *SOE, Barbu Știrbei, Cairo, Constantin Vișoianu, negotiations*

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Gheorghe Buzatu, *Petrol, spionaj, dictaturi, război*, Univers Enciclopedic, 2023.

Authors' Contributions - The authors contributed equally to this work.

Author's presentation:

LASCU Stoica (born 18 June 1951) is a Romanian historian. He has authored over a dozen books and over 340 studies and articles in journals and volumes from Romania and abroad (papers about Modern and Contemporary History of Romania, Dobrudja, Aromanians, Modern Balkan, Romanian Historiography). Former Professor at Ovidius University of Constanța – Faculty of History and Political Science). Now is retired.

ZIDARU Marian (born 8 May 1964) is a Romanian historian. He hwas Associate Professor at Andrei Șaguna University Constanța and wrote 6 books as a sole author and over 100 articles and studies (especially, the history of the Romanians, including those from Dobrudja and Bessarabia). He used to teach History International Relations, Theory of International Relations, and History of Europe. Now is retired.

Who Controls the Decision? Artificial Intelligence, Algorithmic Control, and Consumer Trust in Banking

Valentin Manguirea

Doctoral School of Management, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration (SNSPA), Bucharest, Romania

Lucian Claudiu Anghel

National University of Political Studies and Public Administration (SNSPA), Bucharest, Romania

Abstract:

This article aims to provide a rigorous synthesis of market data and literature on algorithmic control, explainability/transparency, and consumer trust in the banking sector, with a particular focus on Central Europe and Romania. As an introductory article providing the latest market analysis, it will present measurement approaches, empirical findings, industry reports, and regulatory frameworks, identify methodological and substantive gaps specific to the CEE context, and propose a clear research agenda for structuring subsequent articles of the cumulative thesis.

Keywords: *Algorithmic control, Explainability (Explainable AI / XAI), Consumer confidence, Perceived risk, Banking sector, Algorithmic governance.*

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Authors' Contributions: Co-author: Prof. Lucian Claudiu Anghel, PhD

Author's presentation:

My name is Valentin Manguirea and I am a first-year doctoral student at the SNSPA Doctoral School, under the supervision of Prof. Lucian Anghel. I graduated from the Faculty of Management in 2023 with a thesis dedicated to the impact of critical thinking on media consumers, and in 2025 I completed the master's program in Programs and Investments Management, analyzing the role of emotional intelligence and agile decisions in HPE customer satisfaction in the DACH region. Together with Associate Professor Sergiu Octavian Stan, PhD, I published the article *Elements of Critical Thinking Used in Decision-Making Process by Romanian Media Consumers*. Professionally, I work at Hewlett Packard Enterprise, where I have evolved into the role of Business Analyst for the DACH area. My research areas include critical thinking, managerial decision-making, emotional intelligence, and customer satisfaction dynamics. My doctoral thesis is entitled: "Algorithmic control and trust in artificial intelligence in banking: a comparative study of Romania and central Europe." ORCID ID: 0009-0004-6865-2651

Lucian Claudiu Anghel – Professor, PhD., National University of Political Studies and Public Administration (SNSPA), Bucharest, Romania

The Integration of AI into the Lives of Engineering Students: A Case Study

Diana Marcu

University of Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

In a world of technological innovations, the artificial intelligence (AI) has become more and more present in people's lives, be it for personal entertainment or for professional reasons. The educational system is part of this change as well, with both students and teachers relying on AI-platforms for various activities and tasks. The aim of the present paper is to analyse students' attitudes and expectations related to the use of AI in their personal and academic lives. The focus group consists of students from the Faculty of Electrical Engineering, University of Craiova, Romania. The analysis is based on a survey among first and second-year undergraduates and is meant to assess how frequently students use AI-powered platforms, to what end, as well as the benefits and drawbacks of such platforms. At the same time, students are asked to offer their perspectives on the future of AI in the educational process. The results are of importance to both educators and decision-makers when it comes to reshaping the academic world.

Keywords: *Academic studies, artificial intelligence, AI- powered learning platforms, benefits, drawbacks*

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Author's presentation:

Diana Marcu, PhD, is Senior Lecturer at the Faculty of Letters, University of Craiova, where she teaches English for Specific Purposes. Holding a PhD in Philology, she's been interested in topics such as the teaching of English in different contexts, the development of students' skills, age-group learners or designing ESP courses. She has participated in numerous national and international conferences, being also involved in various scientific activities. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-2696-8621

Abbreviations Used in Tourism Terminology

Marin Cristina-Gabriela

University of Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

Tourism is a complex industry and the understanding of its terminology, especially abbreviations or acronyms can sometimes feel like you are learning an entirely new language. They are used by many companies and organizations for the purpose of conveying the appropriate information to the auditory in a short period of time. Students should be made aware of the importance of acquiring these international conventions in order to avoid being caught off-guard in tourism-related conversation or context as abbreviations and acronyms are heavily used in tourism. The conventions must be strictly followed but they vary between countries and universities. They often exist in a slightly different form in Romanian as well and should not be used instead of the English ones. My interest in abbreviations has arisen when gathering materials for a dictionary on Tourism terminology. This study has attempted to bring a new approach on a list as comprehensible as possible (comprising 174 examples which we have encountered through the close examination of a corpora which has been selected to assist the research) by revealing not only their abundant number but also their Romanian equivalent. This study is meant to be a useful tool not only for students, but also for the English teachers, because a common drawback that might arise when teaching English for Special Purposes, in particular, could be the insufficient training of the teacher in this field.

Keywords: *terminology, space saving, individual letters, contemporary English, etc.*

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Author's presentation:

I have been teaching English for Special Purposes (ESP) for over 15 years at the University of Craiova, Romania. My main academic activities imply not only a teaching load (especially at non-philological faculties) but also a researching load (more than 50 publications and several textbooks and two dictionaries). ORCID ID: 0000-0001-7551-7125

Biblical Idioms Used in Travel-Related Contexts

Marin Cristina-Gabriela

University of Craiova, Romania

Ispas Loredana

University of Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

This article analyzes 42 Biblical idioms used in travel-related contexts using the British National Corpus, blogs and social media. It, also, emphasizes both their historical (biblical) meaning which is sometimes completely forgotten and the way their meaning have shifted in modern language, namely travelling situations. Each idiom mentioned in the paper stem from the Bible and with newly derived and synchronic meanings which can be employed in new contexts, namely travel-related ones, that are not just religious.

Aware of the significance of a corpus linguistic research for a better understanding of idiom use, this work will, therefore, examine the function of a series of Bible idioms in the British National Corpus, narrowing their usage to travel-related contexts. In texts that deal with travelling, Bible idioms have a more marked interpersonal function, writers employ the idioms to express their ideas in an almost euphemistic manner, in the hope of influencing their readers' opinions, too. As a result, Bible idioms in this context carry a dual function, on the one hand they have a striking and influential effect upon readers, on the other hand they allow writers to deliver personal opinions in an impersonal manner conveyed by the idiom.

Keywords: *a different approach, dual function, unexpected syntactic-layout, flexible frame of reference, new connotations, etc.*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work

Author's presentation:

Marin Cristina Gabriela - I have been teaching English for Special Purposes (ESP) for over 15 years at the University of Craiova, Romania. My main academic activities imply not only a teaching load (especially at non-philological faculties) but also a researching load (more than 50 publications and several textbooks and two dictionaries). ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7551-7125>

Ispas Loredana - I have been teaching English for Special Purposes (ESP) since 2003. My main academic activities imply not only a teaching load (especially at non-philological faculties). In addition to my teaching activity, I am also involved in research, having published over 30 academic papers as well as several textbooks. ORCID ID: <http://orcid.org//0009-0006-0772-7757>

Comprehension and Retention in Print, Digital, and AI-Mediated Reading: A Scoping Review

Valentina Marinescu

University of Bucharest, Bucharest, Romania

Teodor Dumitrache

University of Bucharest, Bucharest, Romania

Abstract:

Declines in leisure reading have renewed scholarly attention to reading as a socially patterned practice with implications for cognitive outcomes, mental health, and broader health inequalities. Literacy is unevenly distributed across populations and closely associated with educational attainment, socioeconomic status, and access to health information, shaping individuals' capacity to comprehend and retain written material in everyday contexts (DeWalt & Pignone, 2005). Research across the life course has linked reading practices to well-being in neurological, pediatric, and older adult populations (Latchem & Greenhalgh, 2014; Shulman et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2022). Further studies suggest that engagement with narrative fiction may support aspects of emotional regulation and well-being, including modest benefits for mood and adolescent mental health (Carney & Robertson, 2022; Arslan et al., 2022). Much of this evidence, however, is based on print reading and does not fully reflect contemporary reading environments.

This scoping review maps empirical research comparing comprehension and retention across print, digital, and AI-mediated reading formats. As reading increasingly occurs on digital platforms and within algorithmically structured systems, reading practices are shaped not only by text characteristics but also by interface design, platform features, and patterns of use such as multitasking and fragmented attention. Comparative studies frequently focus on screen versus paper reading and examine outcomes related to comprehension, memory, and attention under varying task conditions (Clinton, 2019; Delgado et al., 2018).

The review also documents how emerging AI-enabled reading technologies, including adaptive interfaces, automated summarization, and personalized recommendations, are incorporated into reading contexts addressed in the literature. By situating comprehension and retention within socially and technologically mediated reading practices, this scoping review aims to identify the range of study designs, populations, outcomes, and methodological approaches currently used, and highlights areas where further research is needed to address inequality, literacy, and technological change in reading practices.

Keywords: *reading comprehension, print reading, digital reading, AI-mediated reading, reading platforms, literacy and inequality*

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Authors' Contributions: Both authors have the same contribution at the presentation.

Author's presentation:

Valentina Marinescu is a PhD professor in the field of sociology. Her research interests are in the field of communication and mass media, with a special focus on Eastern Europe. She teaches the courses “Communication Theories” and “Mass Media Sociology” at the undergraduate level, “Media Content Analysis,” “Media Planning” and “Qualitative Methods of Study in Communication” at the master's level. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9882-5902

Teodor Dumitrache, PhD, is a researcher in sociology specializing in communication, media, and future technology studies. His work focuses on media discourse, digital culture, disruptive innovations, and artificial intelligence. ORCID ID: 0000-0001-6901-816X

From Spells to Code: Comparing Medical Authority in Medieval Romania and the Age of AI

Valentina Marinescu

University of Bucharest, Bucharest, Romania

Teodor Dumitrache

University of Bucharest, Bucharest, Romania

Abstract:

This paper offers a comparative analysis of medical authority in medieval Romania and in the contemporary age of artificial intelligence, arguing that these two moments (pre-reflectively assumed as radically opposed) share structurally similar negotiations of trust, legitimacy, and expertise. Drawing on qualitative analysis of medieval social and documentary sources, the study examines the roles of barbers, shamans, midwives, confessors, and physicians in Romanian medieval society, highlighting how medical care emerged from the coexistence of empirical practice, spiritual intervention, and experiential knowledge rather than from a single authoritative system.

In medieval Romania, barbers functioned as versatile practitioners, shamans employed ritual and magical healing, midwives oversaw childbirth and early care, confessors acted as spiritual healers, and physicians applied treatments prepared in apothecaries. Authority was not centralized but distributed, constructed through reputation, cultural belief, and social function. The paper places this pluralistic medical landscape in dialogue with contemporary healthcare systems increasingly shaped by artificial intelligence, algorithmic diagnostics, and data-driven decision-making.

Rather than framing AI as a teleological successor to earlier medical practices, this study emphasizes parallel dynamics: the coexistence of multiple forms of expertise, ongoing challenges of explainability, and persistent questions regarding trust and accountability. By comparing medieval Romanian medicine and AI-driven healthcare as parallel systems of authority formation, the paper demonstrates how historical analysis can illuminate present debates on medical disruption, ethical governance, and patient acceptance. Ultimately, the study argues that medieval medical history provides a critical framework for understanding how societies negotiate medical authority in moments of technological transformation.

Keywords: *medical authority, medical trust, comparative medical history, medieval medicine, AI in healthcare*

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Authors' Contributions: Both authors have the same contribution at the presentation.

Author's presentation:

Valentina Marinescu is a PhD professor in the field of sociology. Her research interests are in the field of communication and mass media, with a special focus on Eastern Europe. She teaches the courses “Communication Theories” and “Mass Media Sociology” at the undergraduate level, “Media Content Analysis,” “Media Planning” and “Qualitative Methods of Study in Communication” at the master's level. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9882-5902

Teodor Dumitrache, PhD, is a researcher in sociology specializing in communication, media, and future technology studies. His work focuses on media discourse, digital culture, disruptive innovations, and artificial intelligence. ORCID ID: 0000-0001-6901-816X

Paradoxes of Socialist Ideology in Yugoslavia: Coca-Cola Socialism as a Diplomatic Strategy?

Marija Martinović

Sorbonne Université – CEFRES, Paris, France

Abstract:

This study examines the role of American popular culture in Yugoslavia during the 1950s to 1970s as a tool of international diplomacy and domestic management. The quite unrestricted import of cultural and consumer products from the United States into the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia (SFRY) served strategic interests on both sides. From the American perspective, the deliberate export of films, music, literature, and consumer goods was not intended to overthrow Yugoslavia's state socialism. Rather, it aimed to widen the ideological gap between Belgrade and Moscow, undermining the cohesion of the Eastern Bloc by demonstrating that alternative paths to socialism were feasible (Vučetić 2018; Konta 2020). For the Yugoslav government, access to Western cultural products reinforced the country's liberal international image, signaling openness and modernity to both capitalist and communist audiences, despite ongoing domestic censorship and authoritarian control. While Slavoj Žižek characterizes this dynamic as paradoxical, where the export of Western culture simultaneously promotes ideological openness while reinforcing the very structures of power it claims to loosen, there are very practical advantages of this choice. The presence of American cultural goods contributed to internal stability by cultivating a sense of personal freedom and material well-being among Yugoslav citizens. Exposure to popular music, cinema, fashion, and other cultural symbols offered a contrast with more restrictive socialist societies, mitigating domestic discontent and reinforcing the legitimacy of the Titoist regime (Vučetić 2018). This dual utility, enhancing U.S. diplomatic strength while stabilizing Yugoslavia's domestic order, highlights the centrality of culture as a component of Cold War soft power. By framing American cultural imports as instruments of both foreign and domestic policy, this research underscores the complex interplay between popular culture and international relations, demonstrating how while seeming apolitical, cultural exchanges served profound diplomatic and political functions during the Cold War (Konta 2020).

Keywords: *Consumer Socialism, Non-Aligned, Diplomacy, Pop Culture Ideology, Realpolitik Strategy*

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Author's presentation:

PhD candidate in philosophy since 2023 at Sorbonne University (ED20), I am conducting doctoral research on the crisis of Yugoslav socialism under the supervision of Daniel Baric. I hold a master's degree in political philosophy from Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne (with honors), with research focused on the failure of Yugoslav socialism and religion in Rousseau's work. My academic background includes international study experiences in Rome and Belgrade. Since 2024, she has been teaching French literature and has also worked as a cultural journalist. She is currently undertaking a research stay at CEFRES in Prague. My recent works are participation at the conference in Croatia (Cres) *Thinking with Ivan Illich* (on Slavoj Žižek), as well as a paper for *Balkanistic Worlds* about the concept of Agape and the social bond in socialist Yugoslavia. I also wrote a review of *La Yougoslavie que racontent les humanistes marxistes* by Sacha Markovic for *Balkanologie*. ORCID ID: 0009-0007-0389-7617

Reconfiguring Journalistic Roles in Romania: A Longitudinal Analysis Based on the Worlds of Journalism Study (2016 - 2023)

Antonia Matei

University of Bucharest/ Faculty of Journalism and Communication Sciences, Bucharest, Romania

Abstract:

The paper examines the evolution of professional roles adopted by Romanian journalists in the context of recent transformations of the media environment, through a longitudinal comparison of the two waves of the Worlds of Journalism Study: WJS2 (2016) and WJS3 (2023). Its main objective is to identify the ten most frequently endorsed journalistic roles and to highlight significant changes occurring during a period marked by accelerated technological, political, and economic shifts.

Methodology

The paper is based on the survey of 341 Romanian journalists in WJS2 (data collected between 2014 and 2015) and 365 journalists in WJS3 (data collected between 2022 and 2023), representing a cross-section of media

(TV and radio stations, newspapers, online outlets, independent newsrooms).

RQ1. What are the ten most strongly endorsed journalistic roles among Romanian journalists in 2016 and 2023, and how are these roles hierarchically structured in each wave?

RQ2. To what extent have Romanian journalists' perceptions of key journalistic roles changed between 2016 and 2023, and which roles exhibit the most significant shifts over time?

RQ3. How do observed changes in the endorsement of journalistic roles reflect broader transformations in the professional orientation of Romanian journalism within the comparative framework of the WJS?

Results

The findings reveal a major shift in traditional journalistic roles and professional values. Romanian journalists increasingly move away from role conceptions grounded in strict objectivity, showing a growing inclination toward more engaged forms of journalism that emphasize involvement within society and communities. Notably, two newly introduced proactive roles - countering disinformation and shine a light on society's problems - rank among the most strongly endorsed. Overall, the results point to greater journalistic involvement and a redefinition of normative role expectations in response to contemporary social and informational challenges.

Keywords: *Journalistic Roles, Worlds of Journalism Study, Countering Disinformation*

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This paper is based on data collected as part of the Worlds of Journalism Study (WJS), a comprehensive international research initiative that assesses the state of journalism worldwide. The author would like to thank the international team the researchers, and also the Romanian team and media representatives for their invaluable contributions and support.

Author's presentation:

Antonia Matei, PhD., is Senior Lecturer at the Faculty of Journalism and Communication Sciences (University of Bucharest). She has accumulated over a decade of professional experience as a reporter, editor, and host at the Romanian Broadcasting Corporation. Her research interests focus on sociology of journalists, emerging technologies, comparative media studies, and media CSR. Throughout her career, she was a member of multiple international research projects. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9110-9700> Relevant scientific contributions: Vasilendiuc, N., Bardan, A., Matei, A. et al. (2025). How Safe Is Journalism? Unpacking Risks and Implications for the Profession in Romania. *Journalism Studies*, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1461670X.2025.2594654> Anton, A. et al. (including Matei, A.). (2025). A media CSR model for wartime contexts. *Journal of Media Business Studies*, 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16522354.2025.2592392> Von Nordheim, G., et al. – incl. Matei, A. (2023). The different worlds of Google – A comparison of search results on conspiracy theories in 12 countries. *Convergence: The International Journal of Research into New Media Technologies*, 0(0) 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13548565231203102>

Urban space and collective memory: the role of commemorative monuments built after 1990 in the Municipality of Bucharest

Florentina-Cristina Merciu

University of Bucharest, Faculty of Geography, Bucharest, Romania

Bogdan Suditu

University of Bucharest, Faculty of Geography, Bucharest, Romania

George-Laurențiu Merciu

University of Bucharest, Faculty of Geography, Bucharest, Romania

Abstract:

This study analyzes the role of commemorative monuments created after 1990 in representing the memory of historical and cultural personalities in the public space of Bucharest and in shaping the urban memorial landscape. In the context of the political and social transformations generated by the post-communist period, the urban space has become an important framework for recovering and reinterpreting collective memory. Commemorative monuments dedicated to prominent figures of history, culture, or public life reflect both the process of identity reconstruction and the symbolic dynamics of the city.

The objective of the research is to identify and analyze commemorative monuments erected after 1990 in the capital city of Romania, highlighting their spatial distribution, the typology of representations, and their significance in the urban landscape. The methodology used includes documentary analysis, direct field observation, and the interpretation of symbolic and cultural elements associated with the commemorative monuments. The study's results indicate that commemorative monuments represent symbolic landmarks that contribute both to increasing the visibility and appreciation of historical and cultural personalities and to shaping the cultural identity of the capital city. By valorizing representative figures of the past, these monuments become symbolic markers of collective memory and significant elements of urban cultural heritage. The study emphasizes the role of public space as a support for cultural memory and as a means of transmitting historical values to the community.

Keywords: *public monuments, collective memory, public space, urban identity, commemorative function*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work.

Authors' presentation:

Merciu Florentina-Cristina is lecturer at the Faculty of Geography, University of Bucharest, Romania. She is senior researcher Rank 2 at the Interdisciplinary Center for Advanced Research on Territorial Dynamics of the same university. Her research interests include cultural heritage (especially industrial heritage), cultural geography, cultural regeneration, circular economy, etc. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2993-5136>.

Suditu Bogdan is associate professor at the Faculty of Geography, University of Bucharest, Romania. His research interests include toponymy, cultural geography, urban geography, etc. He published over 50 articles and 5 books.

Merciu George-Laurențiu is researcher at the Faculty of Geography, University of Bucharest, Romania. His research interests include urban geography, Geographic Information System applied to cultural heritage. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5128-7345>

The Impact of PropTech Technologies on Office Building Management Efficiency

Daniel-Marius Mitrache

*University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration,
Craiova, Romania*

Abstract:

The real estate industry is going through a structural reconstruction phase, imposed by the need to optimize costs and the new demands of hybrid work. Through this medium, we will analyze the impact of digitalization on commercial property management, focusing on the transition from traditional administration to Smart Building ecosystems, exploring how the integration of advanced technologies reconfigures the operation of office buildings, transforming them into dynamic and efficient assets.

The paper examines the role of building automation systems (BMS) and IoT sensors in infrastructure monitoring. The direct benefits of these technologies are analyzed, from predictive optimization of energy consumption to reducing carbon footprint, demonstrating how digitalization is becoming a central pillar of corporate sustainability (ESG) strategies. Operational efficiency represents a competitive advantage in attracting top tenants while also offering maintenance benefits.

Changes in the relationship with the end beneficiary through tenant management applications (Tenant Experience Apps) must also be analyzed. These digital platforms centralize communication, building access, co-working space bookings, and concierge services, facilitating a personalized and fluid user experience. It is argued that property management is evolving from a purely administrative function to a Space-as-a-Service model, where real-time data allows managers to adapt spaces to the real occupancy needs of companies.

Based on the results, we emphasize that the digitalization of property management is no longer an optional option, but a condition for resilience in the modern real estate market. The implementation of PropTech solutions leads to an increase in the value of assets in the long term and increased tenant loyalty, defining the new standard of excellence in real estate business management.

Keywords: *PropTech (Property Technology), Smart Building Management, Tenant Experience, Building Management Systems (BMS).*

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Author's presentation:

Associate Professor, PhD, University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Management specialization. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-4816-2814>.

Management challenges in the internationalization of Romanian SMEs

Daniel-Marius Mitrache

*University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration,
Craiova, Romania*

Abstract:

Going out with a business outside Romania's borders is not just a business decision, but is, in essence, an act of courage that tests the very foundation on which an SME was built. In our approach, we move away from the cold figures of statistics to look into the heart of the management of a business that dares to dream on a European or global scale. We rightly ask ourselves: why do so many brilliant Romanian ideas stop at the border? The answer often lies not in the lack of creativity, but in administrative problems and the culture shock of foreign management systems.

We have observed how our entrepreneurs are forced to go through a contradiction: on the one hand, the specifically Romanian agility to solve problems on the fly, and on the other, the rigor and strict procedures required by mature markets. This paper explores the tension between these two worlds. We are talking about the fear of the legislative unknown, about the burden of bureaucracy that doubles at every step across the border and about the loneliness of the SME manager who must be, simultaneously, a strategist, a lawyer and an expert in international logistics.

It is a journey about adaptation. We analyze how digitalization and new models of remote management become the lifeline for small companies that cannot afford entire consulting departments. But, above all, this article is a plea for the professionalization of local management. We argue that internationalization is not just about selling a product in another language,

but about rebuilding the entire architecture of the business. In the end, we are left with a conclusion that we hope will inspire, namely that the external success of a Romanian SME depends on the ability to learn from administrative failures and to transform the spirit of survival into a strategy for sustainable and disciplined growth.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurship, Cross-border expansion, Managerial agility, Administrative barriers.*

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Author's presentation:

Associate Professor, PhD, University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Management specialization. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-4816-2814>

Quality education as a determinant of progress towards the Sustainable Development Goals

Lavinia-Adelina Mitrache

Universitu of Craiova, Craiova, România

Abstract:

The quality of education is recognized at the international level as an important part of the structural factors that support sustainable development, both as a specific goal of the Agenda 2030 and as a cross-cutting element that affects a majority of the global goals set at that level. It is recognized that education as a key factor in social and economic transformation and one of the most important investments with a high return. The study aims to highlight the role that achieving a high level of education plays in strengthening a more aware and resilient global society, by assessing its role through a comparative analysis between Romania and the European average. The recent data confirm that there is a gap between Romania and the European Union average. The interpreted results showed us that the average score of a Romanian student is 428 points, lower than both the European Union average and the OECD average, with over 40% of students below the minimum level of proficiency in all domains. These gaps reveal the constraints that affect human capital and highlight the necessity of systemic measures that aim to support an improvement in educational performance and reduce inequalities between social classes. The role that education plays in sustainable development is a complex process that aims to support individuals' capacities to make informed decisions and responsible actions, both for the present and for future generations. The comparative studies carried out at the European level highlight that a third of the member states, including Romania, are still below the optimal level of performance regarding this domain. Therefore, under these circumstances, closing the educational gap between Romania and the European Union average is a key element that can support an acceleration of progress regarding sustainable development goals.

Keywords: *quality education, sustainable development, SDG 4, human capital, educational performance*

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Author's presentation: Lavinia-Adelina Mitrache - Phd Student, University of Craiova, Doctoral School Of Economics Sciences "Eugeniu Carada", Craiova, Romania. ORCID ID: 0009-0001-9514-3527.

The Impact of the War in Ukraine on Sustainable Development and Global Economic Resilience

Lavinia-Adelina Mitrache

Universitu of Craiova, Craiova, România

Abstract:

The recent escalation of geopolitical tensions, with special emphasis on the war in Ukraine, has led to various consequences, which are not limited only to the theatre of war but have significant effects on the global trajectory of sustainable development. It is evident from existing literature that wars have various effects, including those on the economic, environmental, and political dimensions of sustainable development, not only on the regions directly involved in the war but also on distant regions through global economic, environmental, and political systems.

The Russian-Ukrainian conflict shows that military aggression can have a simultaneous effect on the integrity of the environment, the economy, and social welfare. The damage to infrastructure, industrial accidents, and military activities all contribute to the degradation of the environment, which includes pollution, loss of biodiversity, and the disruption of ecosystems. At the same time, the Russian-Ukrainian conflict has heightened the global economic pressures by disrupting the energy sector, the food supply chain, and the inflation rate globally.

In addition to immediate damage to ecosystems, war is responsible for long-term damage to the environment, which can last for decades. Wars lead to pollution of soil, deforestation, and water pollution. Today, people are referring to it as ecocide, with a focus on the massive damage done to the environment as a result of wars. The complex nature of these impacts, therefore, suggests that sustainable development cannot be pursued without the consideration of geopolitical stability. The case in Ukraine demonstrates the vulnerability of SDGs strategies in the face of extensive conflicts, thus

underscoring the need to incorporate resilience, environmental conservation, and cooperation in the formulation of future sustainable development policies. The understanding of these dynamics is imperative in the formulation of more effective governance policies aimed at promoting sustainable development in an unstable geopolitical environment.

Keywords: *sustainable development, armed conflict, ecological impact, global economy, SDGs.*

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Author's presentation: Lavinia-Adelina Mitrache - Phd Student, University of Craiova, Doctoral School Of Economics Sciences "Eugeniu Carada", Craiova, Romania. ORCID ID: 0009-0001-9514-3527.

From PISA to Prosperity: How Education Quality Is Associated with Economic Development in the EU-27 (2018, 2022)

George Teodor Mitu

*University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration,
Craiova, Romania*

Narcis Eduard Mitu

*University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration,
Craiova, Romania*

Mihaela Zglavoci

*University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration,
Craiova, Romania*

Abstract:

This paper provides a descriptive benchmark on the relationship between learning quality and economic development in the European Union. The analysis focuses on the EU-27 and two reference points, 2018 and 2022, using PISA performance (PISA_mean) as a proxy for cognitive skills and real GDP per capita (chain-linked volumes, base year 2015) as an indicator of living standards. In cross-sectional comparisons, the association between PISA performance and GDP per capita is positive in both years and appears clearer in 2022. By contrast, examining changes over 2018–2022 points to weak co-movement between the change in PISA outcomes and the change in ln(GDP per capita), which calls for caution when interpreting short-run relationships, especially in a period marked by major educational and economic disruptions. A brief regional contrast (CEE vs the rest of the EU) shows that prosperity gaps are, on average, accompanied by gaps in educational outcomes. The results should be read as comparative benchmarks and starting points for more in-depth analysis, suggesting that debates on convergence have solid reasons to incorporate the learning-quality dimension explicitly.

Keywords: *PISA, education quality, real GDP per capita, EU-27, convergence*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work.

Authors' presentation:

George Teodor Mitu graduated from the Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova, completing both his bachelor's and master's degrees, and also holds a bachelor's degree from the Faculty of Law, University of Craiova. His interests lie in the economic field, with a particular focus on finance. He currently works in a financial role at the European Food Safety Authority in Parma. ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0551-2497.

Narcis Eduard Mitu is a Habilitated Associate Professor at the Department of Finance, Banking and Economic Analysis, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova, Romania. He has held a PhD in Accounting since 2006 and has been habilitated in the field of Finance since 2025. His research interests encompass taxation, public finances, and

ethics in the public domain. For 9 years, he worked as a civil servant in leading positions (Head of Department, Deputy Executive Director) in the Public Finance (General Directorate of Public Finances). At this time, he teaches public finance and taxation. He was visiting professor at different European universities (Facultat de Ciències Econòmiques i Social, Universitat Internacional de Catalunya, Barcelona—Spain; Universidade Autónoma de Lisboa—Portugal; Aberdeen Business School, Robert Gordon University—Great Britain). He is the author or coauthor of important scientific books in the field of taxation in Romania (e.g., Fiscal Code Commented; Tax Systems Compared; Tax Procedures—received first prize awarded by the Association of Faculties of Economics in Romania—AFER, Ethics and Business Negotiation, etc.). He is also the author of numerous articles and studies on taxation, taxpayer behaviour, and public finance, which have been published in the most important national scientific journals. Between 2008 and 2023, he was a member of the International Fiscal Association (IFA) and in 2018–2019, he was a member of the International Institute of Global Economy (IIGE). As of 2024, he became a member of the World Economics Association (WEA). ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0265-7658.

Mihaela Zglavoci graduated from the Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova, completing both her bachelor's and master's degrees. Her interests lie in the economic field. ORCID ID: 0009-0002-1704-1274.

ESG and Economic Resilience in the EU: Evidence from Macro Indicators

George Teodor Mitu

*University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration,
Craiova, Romania*

Narcis Eduard Mitu

*University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration,
Craiova, Romania*

Mihaela Zglavoci

*University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration,
Craiova, Romania*

Abstract:

This paper examines the relationship between ESG-related performance and economic resilience in the European Union using widely available macro-level indicators. Building on the premise that environmental quality, social conditions, and institutional capacity shape countries' ability to absorb shocks and recover from adverse episodes, we develop a parsimonious set of ESG proxies drawn from international datasets and relate them to standard measures of resilience, including output volatility, post-downturn recovery dynamics, and labor-market adjustment. The empirical approach relies on panel regressions for EU Member States with country and year

fixed effects, complemented by descriptive benchmarking around major stress episodes. The findings suggest that governance-related variables and selected social indicators are most consistently associated with stronger resilience, whereas environmental proxies exhibit a more context-dependent relationship. The paper contributes a pragmatic and data-feasible framework for assessing ESG-resilience linkages at the country level and derives policy implications for strengthening shock-absorption capacity through institutional and social investment.

Keywords: *ESG, economic resilience, European Union, governance, macroeconomic indicators.*

Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work.

Authors' presentation:

George Teodor Mitu graduated from the Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova, completing both his bachelor's and master's degrees, and also holds a bachelor's degree from the Faculty of Law, University of Craiova. His interests lie in the economic field, with a particular focus on finance. He currently works in a financial role at the European Food Safety Authority in Parma. ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0551-2497.

Narcis Eduard Mitu is a Habilitated Associate Professor at the Department of Finance, Banking and Economic Analysis, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova, Romania. He has held a PhD in Accounting since 2006 and has been habilitated in the field of Finance since 2025. His research interests encompass taxation, public finances, and ethics in the public domain. For 9 years, he worked as a civil servant in leading positions (Head of Department, Deputy Executive Director) in the Public Finance (General Directorate of Public Finances). At this time, he teaches public finance and taxation. He was visiting professor at different European universities (Facultat de Ciències Econòmiques i Social, Universitat Internacional de Catalunya, Barcelona—Spain; Universidade Autònoma de Lisboa—Portugal; Aberdeen Business School, Robert Gordon University—Great Britain). He is the author or coauthor of important scientific books in the field of taxation in Romania (e.g., *Fiscal Code Commented; Tax Systems Compared; Tax Procedures*—received first prize awarded by the Association of Faculties of Economics in Romania—AFER, *Ethics and Business Negotiation*, etc.). He is also the author of numerous articles and studies on taxation, taxpayer behaviour, and public finance, which have been published in the most important national scientific journals. Between 2008 and 2023, he was a member of the International Fiscal Association (IFA) and in 2018–2019, he was a member of the International Institute of Global Economy (IIGE). As of 2024, he became a member of the World Economics Association (WEA). ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0265-7658.

Mihaela Zglavoci graduated from the Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova, completing both her bachelor's and master's degrees. Her interests lie in the economic field. ORCID ID: 0009-0002-1704-1274.

Educational Vulnerabilities and School Participation among Vocational and Lower Secondary Students: A Sociological Needs Assessment in Dolj County, Romania

Gabriela Motoi

University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Alexandrina-Mihaela Popescu

University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

School participation and the prevention of early school leaving remain key priorities within contemporary European educational policies, particularly in the context of socio-economic inequalities that affect students from vulnerable backgrounds. This paper presents the results of a sociological needs analysis conducted among lower secondary and vocational education students in the urban area of Dolj County, Romania. The research aimed to identify the main educational, social, and family-related factors influencing school participation, absenteeism, and the risk of dropout. The study was based on a quantitative sociological survey using a structured questionnaire applied to a non-probabilistic sample of 532 students enrolled in three educational institutions: a lower secondary school and two vocational high schools. The analysis focused on students' school attendance patterns, motivations for absenteeism, perceived academic difficulties, family involvement, access to financial support, and career aspirations. The findings indicate that school absenteeism and dropout risk are primarily associated with structural factors such as learning difficulties, financial constraints, and limited parental involvement in the educational process. A significant proportion of students reported the need for additional academic support, particularly in core subjects required for national examinations. At the same time, financial support mechanisms, such as social scholarships, play an important motivational role in maintaining school participation. The results also highlight the importance of strengthening school-family relationships and expanding career guidance and practical learning opportunities through partnerships with economic actors.

Keywords: *Early school leaving; Educational inequality; Vocational education and training (VET); School participation and absenteeism; Socio-economic vulnerability*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this paper.

Author's presentation:

Gabriela MOTOI is Associate Professor, PhD., at University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Department of Sociology, Philosophy and Social Work. Her research agenda is focused on sociology of education, EU social policy, contemporary sociology, labour market policies, with a strong interdisciplinary approach that bridges sociology, public policy, and education. In 2012, he received a PhD. in Sociology, with a thesis focusing on the Educational Offer and the Labour Market Needs. In 2017, she was Postdoctoral Researcher at EHESS-Paris (France), developing research activities on the topic of youth values, attitudes and perceptions. She has published over 50 articles in academic sociology journals, and she is author and co-author at 21 sociology books. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5333-6216>

Alexandrina Mihaela POPESCU is Associate Professor, PhD at University of Craiova, Director of the Department of Teacher Training. Since 2011, she has a PhD in Education Science, with thesis focusing on the conflict management in school organization. Her research agenda is focused on initial and continuous training of teachers: didactic professionalization; the conflict management in school organization; lifelong learning; optimization of the students' activities for learning – future teachers; teacher's skills profile. She is coordinator of the Research Axis Good practice in students training from the perspective of management and student class leadership – constructivist approach. She is expert in 16 national and European projects, author of over 35 articles in education sciences, author and co-author of 12 books. Also, she is Editor-in-chief of *Annals of the University of Craiova*.

Series Psychology- Pedagogy. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2276-3941>

Gender Equality in Research: A Sociological Analysis of European Statistics and Public Policies

Gabriela Motoi

University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Romania

Alexandrina-Mihaela Popescu

University of Craiova, Department of Teacher Training, Romania

Abstract:

This article explores gender equality within the research field through a sociological analysis. Drawing upon structural functionalism, conflict theory, and symbolic interactionism, the study investigates the phenomena of the glass ceiling and the leaky pipeline, focusing on the persistence of gender disparities in European academia. Statistical data from sources like the European Institute for Gender Equality and the European Commission highlight ongoing disparities, despite increased female participation in higher education. The article also evaluates the effectiveness of current public policies and offers insights into sociological mechanisms perpetuating gender inequality.

Keywords: *gender equality, sociology, academia, structural functionalism, conflict theory, symbolic interactionism, glass ceiling, leaky pipeline.*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this paper.

Author's presentation:

Gabriela MOTOI is Associate Professor, PhD., at University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Department of Sociology, Philosophy and Social Work. Her research agenda is focused on sociology of education, EU social policy, contemporary sociology, labour market policies, with a strong interdisciplinary approach that bridges sociology, public policy, and education. In 2012, he received a PhD. in Sociology, with a thesis focusing on the Educational Offer and the Labour Market Needs. In 2017, she was Postdoctoral Researcher at EHESS-Paris (France), developing research activities on the topic of youth values, attitudes and perceptions. She has published over 50 articles in academic sociology journals, and she is author and co-author at 21 sociology books. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5333-6216>

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the students' activities for learning – future teachers; teacher's skills profile. She is coordinator of the Research Axis Good practice in students training from the perspective of management and student class leadership – constructivist approach. She is expert in 16 national and European projects, author of over 35 articles in education sciences, author and co-author of 12 books. Also, she is Editor-in-chief of Annals of the University of Craiova. Series Psychology- Pedagogy. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2276-3941>

Oltenia - the image of a post-communist evolution

Florin F. NACU

Institute for Research in Social Sciences and Humanities, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The article presents a projection of how Oltenia presented itself during the post-communist period. The architecture in Oltenia was of European inspiration, modern and contemporary, trying to reintegrate itself on all levels in the Western European perspective, which had stopped after 1945 and partially resumed in 1965-1980. The article points out the main considerations on the Romanian economic, historical writings, published in books, articles and studies, concerning the post-communist evolution of Oltenia, a well defined and structured region in the South-Western Romania.

Keywords: *Oltenia, post-communism, historiography, economy, evolution*

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Author's presentation:

Florin Nacu is scientific researcher in ICSU "C.S.Nicolaeescu Plopsor" in Craiova. He is a historian specialized on problems of social structures, social, economic and political importance of Oltenia in the modern and in the contemporary history. Also, having a juridical education he made in his scientific works, the connections between law, history, economy, society, history. He is preoccupied in historical articles and books about revolutions, ideologies and political regimes in the modern and contemporary ages. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-5665-1252>

Artificial Intelligence and the Reconfiguration of History Learning: An Interdisciplinary Analysis from the Perspective of Educational Sciences and Behavioral Anthropology

Daniela Naidin

Universitatea din Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

This article proposes a new approach in learning and teaching history: the use of artificial intelligence. The novelty of this proposal resides in the fulfillment of the gap between the way of how the new generation thinks versus how the old ones do. It is essential to find a workable approach in sharing information in an adequate way to the new generation. And because the presence of AI cannot be denied, we need two things: to teach the new generation how to use it constructively in order not to lose their critical thinking or the development of IQ and at the same time to remap the informational transfer. This article highlights AI's potential to counter narrative biases, support critical source analysis, and generate innovative narrative forms for studying history. The use of AI in history education does not substitute historiographical work, but amplifies it and reorients it towards reflective, participatory, and interdisciplinary learning.

Keywords: *History Learning and AI, Artificial Intelligence in Education, Behavioral Anthropology of Learning, AI-Mediated Knowledge Construction, Human–AI Interaction in Learning.*

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Author's presentation:

Lecturer at the University of Craiova, where I teach courses in Communication and Educational Sciences. My research focuses on anthropology—particularly behavioral anthropology—and on the role of nonformal education in shaping contemporary learning practices. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8577-5854>

Navigating the AI Labour Market: Career Guidance Strategies for Romanian Youth

Andreea-Mihaela Niță

University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Mihaela-Cristina Pârvu

University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The accelerated expansion of artificial intelligence (AI) is contributing to a fundamental transformation of the global labor market, generating both opportunities and risks for young people starting their careers. In Romania, these transformations overlap with existing structural vulnerabilities in the transition from education to the labor market. According to Eurostat data, Romania has the highest proportion of NEET (Not in Employment, Education or Training) young people in the European Union, with approximately 19–20% of people aged 15–29 outside the education, training, or employment systems, compared to a European average of approximately 11%. From a sociological perspective, these dynamics can be analyzed through the lens of human capital theory (Becker), which highlights the role of education and skills in facilitating integration into the labor market, as well as economic, cultural, and social (Bourdieu), which explains how differentiated access to information resources and counseling services can reproduce inequalities in the professional trajectories of young people and society risk (Beck) and reflexive modernity (Giddens), which emphasizes the increase in uncertainty and individualization of life paths in contemporary societies, where individuals are forced to make professional decisions in a context marked by rapid technological changes and structural transformations of the labor market. Based on these premises, we aim to analyze the role of career counseling strategies in facilitating the adaptation of young people in Romania to the labor market transformations generated by artificial intelligence. We want to verify the extent to which limited access to career counseling services increases the likelihood of belonging to the NEET category, and whether the use of digital tools and AI-assisted career guidance platforms contributes to increasing the level of information on emerging professions and improving the chances of professional integration. The methodology used combines quantitative and qualitative methods,

through the application of a questionnaire addressed to young people aged between 15 and 29 and the conduct of semi-structured interviews with career counselors, teachers, and human resources specialists.

Keywords: *Career counselling, AI Labour Market, NEET*

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Authors' Contributions:

Author: NIȚĂ ANDREEA MIHAELA

Co-authors: PÂRVU MIHAELA-CRISTINA

Authors' presentation:

Andreea-Mihaela NIȚĂ is an Associate Professor at University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Department of Sociology, Philosophy and Social Work. She is PhD in Sociology from 2009, graduated at the University of Bucharest with a thesis focusing on the Community Development in a rural area of Romania. In 2011-2013, she was Postdoctoral Researcher at Romanian Academy in the field of Sociology of Culture. Her main research interests include analysis of labor market and human resources, community development and sociology of family. She is author and co-author at 25 sociology books, 55 articles in national and international academic Journals and participated in over 100 national and international conferences. She is also the author and co-author of several sociological quantitative researches in the field of Sociology of work and organizations, labor market, project management, sociology of family and sociology of professions and careers. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6213-5926.

Mihaela Cristina PÂRVU is Assistant Teacher PhD at the Faculty of Social Sciences of the University of Craiova, Social Work Department. She holds two bachelor degrees at the University of Craiova, from the Faculty of Social Sciences and the Faculty of Letters. She is uthor and co-author of several papers published in national and international Journals, most of them on the topic of resilience of vulnerable categories, which has also made the object of her doctoral thesis, presented in September 2020, with

the title "The resilience of children belonging to vulnerable groups. A sociological research in Dolj County". ORCID ID: 0009-0005-2418-5489.

Digital Public Services and Human Development in the AI Era: A Citizen-Based Anticipatory Governance, Security Policy and Information Approach

Anca Parmena Olimid

University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Daniel Alin Olimid

University of Craiova, Biology Specialization, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

Objectives: This article sets as its central objective the analysis of the role of digital transformations and in particular of artificial intelligence. The second operational objective assesses the impact of artificial intelligence on public services and human development setting five dimensions of analysis: access to services, quality of services, the role of anticipatory governance, the role of information and the equity of digital public services

Methods and methodology: A threefold methodological framework is established. 1) First, the research reviews the interdisciplinary literature in the field focusing on topics such as: public policy, human development, information policy, security policy and anticipatory governance. 2) The second methodological perspective focuses on a comparative legal analysis and a policy analysis regarding the objectives, instruments and fields of application of legal acts at the European Union level such as AI Act (2024), Digital Services Act – Reg. (UE) 2022/2065, GDPR – Reg. (UE) 2016/679, NIS 2 Directive – Dir. (UE) 2022/2555, EU Digital Strategy / EU AI Strategy (2020–2021), but also at an international level such as UN Roadmap for Digital Cooperation (2020), UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence (2021), OECD AI Principles (2019), OECD Framework for the Classification of AI Systems (2022) și OECD Digital Government Policy Framework (2020). The second methodological level aims at consistency analysis, which evaluates the degree of implementation, compliance and alignment at the state level using topical indicators such as normative convergence and gaps in the regulatory process.

Findings and discussions: The research results demonstrate that artificial intelligence is predominantly used to streamline the performance of public services and less often in outcomes related to human development, and AI policies configure the mechanisms of anticipatory governance based on algorithmic transparency and data protection.

Conclusions: In conclusion, the paper arguments that artificial intelligence is no longer just a technological tool, but is becoming a primary factor for human development and the efficiency of public services. In this context,

anticipatory governance reduces the risks associated with digital exclusion and algorithmic discrimination

Keywords: *public services, human development, artificial intelligence, anticipatory governance, security policy.*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work.

Authors' presentation:

Anca Parmena Olimid Ph.D. is Associate Professor at the University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Department of History, Political Sciences, International Relations, Political Sciences Specialization. She holds a B.A. in Law from the Faculty of Law (2003) and a B.A. in Political Sciences from the Faculty of History, Philosophy and Geography, University of Craiova (2003) and a Ph.D. in Humanities from the Faculty of History, Philosophy and Geography of the University of Craiova (2008). Her specialist subject areas are Romanian Politics since 1989, Modern and Contemporary Political Thought, the relationship between society, state and religion, Geopolitics and Geostrategy. Two of Professor Olimid's outstanding achievements is her receipt of Economic and Social Council, ECOSOC (WYA), UN Headquarters, New York for a three months internship in 2005 and her Erasmus Scholarship for six months at the University Charles de Gaulle Lille III, France in 2001-2002. Mrs. Olimid has published widely in international databases and national political journals and is the (co)author of several books, notably, *Politics and Religion in EU and USA. Legal commentaries and social controversies* (2010), *Political and spiritual life in Modern Romanian. A Romanian Model of Church-State Relations* (2009) awarded by the Ministry of Education and Research in 2009, Romanian Politics since 1989 (2009); *Politics, Security and Participatory Governance: Key Concepts, Policies and Legislation* (2015). Editor-in-chief of *Revista de Științe Politice/Revue des Sciences Politiques*. ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7546-9845>.

Daniel Alin Olimid is lecturer Ph.D. at the Department of Biology and Environmental Engineering of the University of Craiova, Biology Specialization. His research interest and activity includes research articles in

the field of cell biology, genetics and related field in journals indexed ISI Thomson Reuters and other international databases. He hold a Ph.d. in Medical Sciences, a BA and a MA in Medical Sciences from the University of Craiova, Faculty of Medicine. ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5583-668X>.

Demographic Change, Social Cohesion and Human Development Sustainability and Security: Health Policy Innovation and Regulatory Sandboxes

Daniel Alin Olimid

University of Craiova, Biology Specialization, Craiova, Romania

Anca Parmena Olimid

University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

Objectives: This study aims to analyze the impact of demographic and societal transformations on the degree of social involvement, civic participation, cohesion and social commitment. The study evaluates the role of regulatory sandboxes configured as temporary and monitored public policies intended to test strategies and legal-institutional mechanisms of involvement tested and used to increase social inclusion and the adaptability of government services to demographic changes.

Methods and methodology: The methodological framework applies a methodological approach focused on multiple methods, namely: (a) comparative legal analysis regarding regulatory sandboxes depending on the regulatory and application field such as: social, digital and public services; (b) legal doctrinal analysis to highlight applicable legal principles such as proportionality and legal certainty and (c) scoping review, used as a systemic research method intended to configure a broad research framework regarding key concepts, recurring themes and synthetic theoretical frameworks of a topic or several associated topics.

Findings and discussions: The results of the analysis demonstrate that demographic transformations require the testing of regulatory sandboxes that allow the adaptation of regulations in different sectors and the subsequent integration of efficient models designed to respond to new social feedback mechanisms and human development sustainability.

Conclusions: The study's conclusions identify the need to test new regulatory sandboxes to increase civic engagement and social cohesion, given that the human-centric approach is no longer just normative.

Keywords: *demographic change, social cohesion, human development, public policy, regulatory sandboxes.*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work.

Authors' presentation:

Daniel Alin Olimid is lecturer Ph.D. at the Department of Biology and Environmental Engineering of the University of Craiova, Biology Specialization. His research interest and activity includes research articles in the field of cell biology, genetics and related field in journals indexed ISI Thomson Reuters and other international databases. He hold a Ph.d. in Medical Sciences, a BA and a MA in Medical Sciences from the University of Craiova, Faculty of Medicine. ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5583-668X>.

Anca Parmena Olimid Ph.D. is Associate Professor at the University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Department of History, Political Sciences, International Relations, Political Sciences Specialization. She holds a B.A. in Law from the Faculty of Law (2003) and a B.A. in Political Sciences from the Faculty of History, Philosophy and Geography, University of Craiova (2003) and a Ph.D. in Humanities from the Faculty of History, Philosophy and Geography of the University of Craiova (2008). Her specialist subject areas are Romanian Politics since 1989, Modern and Contemporary Political Thought, the relationship between society, state and religion, Geopolitics and Geostrategy. Two of Professor Olimid's outstanding achievements is her receipt of Economic and Social Council, ECOSOC (WYA), UN Headquarters, New York for a three months internship in 2005 and her Erasmus Scholarship for six months at the University Charles de Gaulle Lille III, France in 2001-2002. Mrs. Olimid has published widely in international databases and national political journals and is the (co)author of several books, notably, *Politics and Religion in EU and USA. Legal commentaries and social controversies* (2010), *Political and spiritual life in Modern Romanian. A Romanian Model of Church-State Relations* (2009) awarded by the Ministry of Education and Research in 2009, *Romanian Politics since 1989* (2009); *Politics, Security and Participatory Governance: Key Concepts, Policies and Legislation* (2015). Editor-in-chief of *Revista de Științe Politice/Revue des Sciences Politiques*. ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7546-9845>.

Public opinion on Russia in Ukraine and Georgia. Comparative Analysis

Pătrașcu Radu

Faculty of Sociology and Social Work – University of Bucharest, Bucharest, Romania

Abstract:

The aim of this paper is to analyze the public opinion of citizens in Georgia and Ukraine towards the Russian Federation, on the grounds that the two states have in common several elements. Among them, we mention the fact that both are states that have been in conflicts with Russia, both have a past in the sphere of the Soviet Union and therefore in both Russia has never ceased to exert its influence.

In our opinion, from the perspective of a psychosocial dimension of the conflict, the repercussions are felt at the level of identity, of collective traumas (social memory theory), victimization, opinions about the enemy ("demonization"), stereotypes, existential fears. Conflict trauma can be passed on from generation to generation (social memory theory), forming a new collective identity, one marked by existential fear.

Thus, after the institutionalization of conflict (creating, in practice, a culture of conflict), violence becomes a way of relating to the other identity. Living in a culture of conflict, of violence, international mediation almost becomes an utopian idea. Therefore, despite multiple attempts of mediation by international institutions, the conflicts in the breakaway regions of South Ossetia and Abkhazia and Ukraine persist, albeit not in the form of open conflict, but in the form of frozen conflict, as the case may be.

In our opinion, it is important to note what was the opinion of Ukrainians on the development of their country in relation to Russia both before 2022 (the year of invasion) and after, in order to compare these results with the opinion of Georgians in the same time units on similar issues.

Keywords: *conflict, cooperation, social trauma, public opinion, identity*

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Author's presentation:

PhD student. Researcher focused on the post-communist space evolution. Links to publications: "The Geopolitical Dynamism of the Russian Federation: A Multidimensional Strategic Analysis", Journal of Community Positive Practices, 2026, link: <https://jppc.ro/index.php/jppc/article/view/1042> "Migration, a current issue: The crisis of today, the challenge of tomorrow", in Europolity – Continuity and Change in European Governance Vol. 9, no. 2 (2015) (link: http://europolity.eu/wp-content/uploads/2015/12/Vol.-9.-No.-2.-2015_241-264.pdf). In December 2015, I wrote an article for the Journal for Political Science

and International Relations, published by the Institute of Political Sciences and International Relations, part of the Romanian Academy. The material entitled "The geopolitical dynamism of Eastern Europe from a constructivist point of view" and can be accessed at the following link: <http://revista.ispri.ro/wp-content/uploads/2012/09/70-86-Radu-Patrascu.pdf>.

Co-author of "Prospective of Ukraine Crisis: Scenarios for a mid-long term Evolution", published in English by the Publishing House of the Institute of Political Studies and International Relations, Romania, ISBN 978-606-8656-01-4 (link: http://www.cpc-ew.ro/pdfs/ukraine_crisis.pdf, page 100). "Turkey's diplomacy with Russia and Ukraine in the context of the annexation of the Crimean Peninsula", material published in the Proceedings of the International Summer School "GeoPolitica" - the eighth edition, page 264, having as central theme "Turkey's geopolitical strategies in the Middle East". The Summer School was organized with the support of the Embassy of the Republic of Turkey in Romania, the Faculty of International Economic Relations (ASE), the Association of Turkish Businessmen in Romania (TIAD) and the "Ion Conea" Geopolitics Association, ISBN 978-606-8550-29-9 Link to paper: <http://bit.ly/2qA4Klp> . Following a research program focused on

Post-conflict reconstruction, I wrote a paper entitled US assistance in combating drug trafficking in Colombia. The “PLAN COLOMBIA” program, published in the European Journal of Latin American Studies, Vol. 3, No. 1 – 2015 link: <http://www.isla.eu.com/wp-content/uploads/2013/01/EJLAS-vo15.pdf> , page 105. In February 2013, I published an article in the Strategic Colloquy entitled “China vs. the USA: Will China manage to surpass the USA in the race for obtaining global hegemony?”, at the Centre for Defence and Security Strategic Studies, the National University of Defense “Carol I”, Bucharest, Romania Link: http://cssas.unap.ro/ro/pdf_publicatii/cs02-13.pdf

Clarity, Coherence, and Communication: The Case for Standardized Administrative Language

Păunescu Floriana Anca

University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Chirițescu Ileana Mihaela

University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

Communication in public administration requires the use of specific and precise vocabulary, employing standardized terminology that helps avoid misinterpretations or ambiguities and ensures coherence in the transmission of information. Precise and concise terminology is essential for describing complex concepts and theories in an accessible and easily understandable manner. Public administration language is marked by specialized, technical, and frequently formal terminology.

However, the terms used do not always have a single, stable meaning; they can exhibit semantic variations depending on the administrative, legal, or institutional context. Such variations may lead to confusion and interpretive difficulties, particularly in communication with citizens or between institutions operating in different fields. Semantic variations refer to the differences in meaning that a word or specialized term may carry across different contexts. The development of communication channels both among employees and between employees and the outside world is crucial. Through communication, public administration also receives from external sources the information it needs in order to achieve its objectives.

Within any administrative structure, communication is important as it ensures the quality of existing relationships. Public communication, as the term itself suggests, operates in the public sphere, under the influence of administrative relations between the public sector employee and the citizen. Public communication involves sharing information of collective interest, as well as maintaining social relations for which public institutions are responsible.

Keywords: *semantic variations, communication, terminology, information.*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work.

Authors' presentation:

Păunescu Floriana Anca, Associate Professor, PhD Habil. at the University of Craiova, Department of Romanian Language and Literature, has written 12 books and over 100 specialized articles. Păunescu Floriana Anca teaches Romanian language for foreign students. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9646-7718.

Chirițescu Ileana Mihaela, Associate Professor, PhD at the University of Craiova, Department of Modern Languages, has written 12 books and over 100 specialized articles. Chirițescu Ileana Mihaela teaches French for students from non-philological faculties. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-2272-7580

The Romanian Press During the Transition from the Communist to the Post-Communist Period. Case Study: Art, Culture, and Economy

Păușan-Barna Leonard-Denis

West University of Timișoara, Timișoara, Romania

Abstract:

The transformation of the Romanian press from the communist to the post-communist period reflects the profound political, social, and ideological changes that reshaped Romanian society after 1989. During the regime of Nicolae Ceaușescu, publications such as "Astra," "Contemporanul," "Flacăra," and "Scînteia" operated within a strictly controlled ideological framework, functioning as instruments of state propaganda and vehicles for the promotion of official narratives, particularly in the spheres of Economy, Culture, and Art. Following the collapse of the communist regime, the emergence and redefinition of publications such as "Dilema," "Renașterea Bănățeană," and "Tribuna" signaled a gradual shift toward pluralism, freedom of expression, and diversification of public discourse, extending into the 2000s. The comparative analysis of these newspapers and magazines reveals both structural continuities and significant ruptures in journalistic language, thematic priorities, and representations of economic and cultural realities. By examining media discourse across these two distinct historical contexts, the study highlights the press as a central space in which ideological control, cultural production, and democratic transformation intersected.

Keywords: *Romanian; 1989; Newspapers; Astra; Economic;*

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Andrei Ursu, Roland O. Thomasson, *Căderea unui dictator*, Editura Polirom, Iași, 2022; & Communist + Postcommunist press.

Author's presentation:

PhD candidate at the West University of Timișoara, specializing in Modern and Contemporary History. Current doctoral research focuses on "The Circles of Power Around King Carol I", examining the political elites, influence networks, and decision-making mechanisms that shaped Romania's state consolidation during the reign of Carol I of Romania. Academic activity includes the publication of several scholarly articles in journals such as "Cronos" (Caraș-Severin branch of the Societatea de Științe

Istorice din România), “Columna 2000”, and other academic periodicals. Research interests encompass political elites, monarchy and state-building, international relations, media discourse under communism, and the ideological construction of power. Selected publications include: “The Hohenzollern-Sigmaringen Monarchy and Its Beginnings in Romania”, “The 1989 Revolution in Reșița”, “International Relations on June 28, 1919: The Treaty of Versailles”, “The Cult of the Ceaușescu Couple and the False Prosperity of Romania’s Economy in the Communist Media”. Through interdisciplinary approaches combining political, social, and media history, current research aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of power structures and ideological narratives in modern and contemporary Romania. ORCID ID: 0000-0001-7414-4021.

Economic and Sociological Theories on the Impact of Technology on Labor: Toward an Institutional Task-Mediation Framework

Ramona Costina Pîrvu

*University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration,
Craiova, Romania*

Constantina Alina Ciurilă (Tapi)

*University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration,
Craiova, Romania*

Abstract:

The rapid expansion of digital technologies and artificial intelligence has renewed academic and policy debates concerning the relationship between technological progress and labor market transformation. While economic theories emphasize productivity and task reallocation, sociological approaches stress power, control, and institutional embedding. This paper addresses the following research question: How can economic and sociological theories be integrated into a unified framework explaining the distributional consequences of contemporary technological change?

Building on classical political economy, skill-biased and task-based models (notably those developed by Daron Acemoglu and David Autor), and institutional sociology inspired by Karl Polanyi, the paper proposes an Institutional Task-Mediation Framework (ITMF). The model conceptualizes technology as influencing labor outcomes indirectly through task restructuring processes that are structurally mediated by institutional configurations.

Using a structured synthesis of theoretical literature and secondary empirical evidence from international labor market reports, the study argues that technological change primarily restructures task composition rather than eliminating work per se. However, distributional consequences vary systematically according to institutional arrangements. The framework

provides an integrative analytical tool for comparative political economy and future empirical research.

Keywords: *technological change, artificial intelligence, labor markets, institutional economics, task restructuring, inequality*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work.

Authors' presentation:

Prof. Univ. Dr. Habil. Pîrvu Ramona Costina
Phd. Student Ciurilă(Tapi) Constantina Alina

From Vulnerability to Resilience: Developing Emotional Resilience in Children at Risk

Pârvu Mihaela-Cristina

University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Niță Andreea-Mihaela

University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

Children living in contexts of social vulnerability are frequently exposed to multiple risk factors that may affect their emotional development, psychological well-being, and long-term social integration. Poverty, family instability, parental migration, neglect, and other adverse childhood experiences can undermine children's capacity to regulate emotions and cope effectively with stress. At the same time, contemporary research in developmental psychology and social work emphasizes that resilience represents a dynamic process through which children can positively adapt despite significant adversity. This paper explores the development of emotional resilience in children exposed to social risk situations and highlights the role of protective factors that may foster positive adaptation. Particular attention is given to the interaction between individual characteristics, relational support, and community resources that contribute to strengthening children's emotional coping capacities. Emotional resilience is approached as a multidimensional construct that includes emotional regulation, adaptive coping strategies, positive relationships with significant adults, and access to supportive social environments. The study adopts a qualitative research design focused on understanding how resilience is fostered in real-life contexts of social work practice. The empirical component will consist of several case studies involving children identified as being in situations of social vulnerability. In addition, semi-structured interviews will be conducted with social workers from Dolj County, Romania, in order to explore their professional perspectives on the mechanisms that support emotional resilience among vulnerable children. The research aims to identify both the challenges faced by practitioners and the effective strategies used in practice to strengthen children's adaptive capacities. By integrating theoretical perspectives on resilience with insights derived from professional practice, this paper aims to contribute to a better understanding of how social work interventions can support children in transforming experiences of vulnerability into opportunities for emotional growth and adaptive development. The findings are expected to highlight the importance of resilience-oriented approaches in child protection and social services, as well as the need for coordinated collaboration between social workers, families, schools, and community institutions in order to promote healthier developmental trajectories for children at risk.

Keywords: *emotional resilience, vulnerable children, social risk, child protection, social work intervention*

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Authors' Contributions

Author: PÂRVU MIHAELA-CRISTINA

Co-authors: NIȚĂ ANDREEA MIHAELA

Authors' presentation:

Mihaela Cristina PÂRVU is Assistant Teacher PhD at the Faculty of Social Sciences of the University of Craiova, Social Work Department. She holds two bachelor degrees at the University of Craiova, from the Faculty of Social Sciences and the Faculty of Letters. She is author and co-author of several papers published in national and international Journals, most of them on the topic of resilience of vulnerable categories, which has also made the object of her doctoral thesis, presented in September 2020, with the title "The resilience of children belonging to vulnerable groups. A sociological research in Dolj County". ORCID ID: 0009-0005-2418-5489

Andreea-Mihaela NIȚĂ is an Associate Professor at University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Department of Sociology, Philosophy and Social Work. She is PhD in Sociology from 2009, graduated at the University of Bucharest with a thesis focusing on the Community Development in a rural area of Romania. In 2011-2013, she was Postdoctoral Researcher at Romanian Academy in the field of Sociology of Culture. Her main research interests include analysis of labor market and human resources, community development and sociology of family. She is author and co-author at 25 sociology books, 55 articles in national and international academic Journals and participated in over 100 national and international conferences. She is also the author and co-author of several sociological quantitative researches in the field of Sociology of work and organizations, labor market, project management, sociology of family and sociology of professions and careers. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6213-5926.

Artificial Intelligence vs. Human Factor in Applied Behavior Analysis: A Comparative Analysis for Future Integration in Behavioral Sciences

Roxana Plesa

University of Petrosani, Social Sciences Department, Petrosani, Romania

Abstract:

This paper explores the growing intersection between Artificial Intelligence (AI) and human-driven interventions in Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA). It seeks to critically analyze the roles and contributions of AI and human professionals in the delivery of ABA services, particularly in the context of clinical practice, educational settings, and research. Drawing on recent advancements in AI technologies, the paper evaluates both the strengths and limitations of AI-based interventions, such as machine learning, natural language processing, and robotics, in comparison to human expertise, emotional intelligence, and ethical considerations. The paper also discusses the potential for collaborative synergy between AI systems and human practitioners, proposing guidelines for integrating AI into ABA practices while maintaining the critical human element. Finally, the paper addresses ethical concerns, social implications, and future research directions necessary for a balanced approach to ABA interventions in the age of AI. A case study is presented to highlight real-world applications and outcomes. The discussion considers ethical, practical, and clinical implications of incorporating AI into ABA practices, and future directions for research in this domain are proposed.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Applied Behavior Analysis, Autism Spectrum Disorder, Ethical Considerations, Human Factors, Data-Driven Interventions*

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Author's presentation:

The author has 18 years of experience in university teaching and research in areas like: social psychology, family psychosociology, counseling of risk social groups. She represents the Chief Editor for Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies. She has recently completed postgraduate studies in Educational Interventions for Children with Disabilities and Their Families and Continuing Professional Development in Education and Counseling in Romania and is Board Certified Assistant Behavior Analyst in United States of America. ORCID ID: 0009-0000-4583-8382

The value of morality in the system of legal science and in the enhancement of social relations

Roberta PLOSCĂ

University of Craiova, Law Faculty, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The system of legal science is undoubtedly built on a system of values. It can therefore be considered that in the permanent evolution of society and the legal system, the idea of following the degree of interconnection of law with moral values is always welcome. Being subject to the rules of morality, human beings can prevent a conflict with the legal norms and this can have certain consequences in their social life. At the same time, one should approach the issue of whether, in the construction of the rules of conduct, law can receive the influence of morality and, consequently, whether we can attribute to morality the quality of a vague source of inspiration for law. Whether even at the present moment the relationship between law and morality is worthy of being valued or we can see morality as totally incompatible with law in today's society, whether there is a clear predilection of the human being towards morality or the concept of morality is easily neglected or we intentionally lose sight of the actual meaning of the term in assessing the balance of the relationships between us, all these are still as many perspectives that involve profound and conclusive discussions from which we can capture the status of this value in its relationship with the science of law.

In any case, it can be said that morality can help the understanding of the legal dimension in a superior way.

Keywords: *legal system, rule of conduct, moral value*

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Dincolo de logos, Gheorghe Dănișor, Editura Universitaria, Craiova, 2014

Author's presentation:

Roberta PLOSCĂ is Associate Professor, PhD within the Department of Private Law from the Law Faculty at University of Craiova, with 26 years of experience in university education. She graduated at the Law Faculty in 1999, PhD from 2002 (specialization: Law). She has written 18 specialized books and university manuals, published at national and international recognized editions, she had sustained about 10 nationally and internationally scientific communications, she had published about 47 articles in specialized domestic and foreign publications and she has finalized 3 grants and research contracts.

The Values of the “Succeder” Psychographic Group as Discernible in *The Sunday Times* Newspaper Review of a Hotel

Alina-Roxana Popa

The University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The paper analyses a review of The Newman, a five-star hotel in central London, which appeared in *The Sunday Times* on the 29th of January 2026, outlining the features that qualify such a newspaper article to target the primary audience of this publication, which media and marketing studies have identified as “the Succeder”. This is a psychographic group at the top of the social scale, in high-earning professions, seeking control and believing they deserve the best. The review discourse both reinforces and constructs an ethos of consumerism, in which the description of the product invites and qualifies the experience. The review does not “advertise” the hotel, but it contributes to the dissemination and creation of a story around a high-end product, which constitutes a part of the product itself. The review author reveals attributes of a one-night hotel stay, which resonate with the values that *The Times* readers seek: novelty, trendiness, liveliness and excitement, innovation, the sourcing of local items extended to historical personalities and workforce; exclusiveness, London-centricity, thrill seeking with elegant urban décor, continuity and transformation as opposed to the loss of heritage, the collaboration of luxury professionals in order to make the product more relevant, etc. The journalist Jenny Coad, who appears to be a member of the upper-class herself, offers an insight, through her experience,

into the profile of a readership that sets trends, forms opinions and partakes in the making of the story that animates the object of desire.

Keywords: *newspaper review, target audience, high-end products, luxury consumer, social class*

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Author's presentation:

Alina-Roxana POPA, PhD, is a Senior Lecturer at the University of Craiova, the Faculty of Letters, where she currently teaches ESP (English for Specific Purposes) to IT students. In the past, she also taught Pragmatics, Translation Theory, Intercultural Communication and Functional Styles. Having a PhD in advertising linguistics, she has authored one book on the language of commercial advertisements in women's magazines. She has also published two books on ESP for IT students and several articles in her area of interest: ESP methodology, online teaching, the language of advertising, of political discourse, of informative texts, or the language of propaganda in popular culture. ORCID ID: 0000-0001-9409-4789

Understanding Continuous Professional Development Needs among Teachers in Vocational and Technical Education: Evidence from a Sociological Study

Alexandrina-Mihaela Popescu

University of Craiova, Department of Teacher Training, Romania

Gabriela Motoi

University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Romania

Abstract:

The continuous professional development of teachers represents a central dimension of contemporary educational policy, particularly in contexts marked by rapid curricular transformations, technological change, and increasing pedagogical complexity. In vocational and lower-secondary education, where teachers must simultaneously address diverse student needs and align instruction with labour market expectations, identifying real training needs becomes essential for improving educational quality. This study explores the professional development needs of teachers from two vocational high schools and one urban lower-secondary school in Dolj County, aiming to construct a nuanced portrait of their perceptions, challenges, and motivations regarding continuous training. Grounded in theories of reflective practice and organizational change, the research investigates how teachers evaluate their previous participation in training, the obstacles they encounter, and the conditions that can enhance engagement in innovative learning opportunities. By integrating theoretical foundations with empirical inquiry, the study contributes to a deeper understanding of teachers' professional learning dynamics.

Keywords: *Professional Development, Teachers' Training Needs, Vocational and Technical Education; Reflective Practice; Educational Change.*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work.

Author's presentation:

Alexandrina Mihaela POPESCU is Associate Professor, PhD at University of Craiova, Director of the Department of Teacher Training. Since 2011, she has a PhD in Education Science, with thesis focusing on the conflict management in school organization. Her research agenda is focused on initial and continuous training of teachers: didactic professionalization; the conflict management in school organization; lifelong learning; optimization of the students' activities for learning – future teachers; teacher's skills profile. She is coordinator of the Research Axis Good practice in students training from the perspective of management and student class leadership – constructivist approach. She is expert in 16 national and European projects, author of over 35 articles in education sciences, author and co-author of 12 books. Also, she is Editor-in-chief of Annals of the University of Craiova. Series Psychology- Pedagogy. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2276-3941>

Gabriela MOTOI is Associate Professor, PhD., at University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Department of Sociology, Philosophy and Social Work. Her research agenda is focused on sociology of education, EU social policy, contemporary sociology, labour market policies, with a strong interdisciplinary approach that bridges sociology, public policy, and education. In 2012, he received a PhD. in Sociology, with a thesis focusing on the Educational Offer and the Labour Market Needs. In 2017, she was Postdoctoral Researcher at EHESS-Paris (France), developing research activities on the topic of youth values, attitudes and perceptions. She has published over 50 articles in academic sociology journals, and she is author and co-author at 21 sociology books. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5333-6216>

Exploring Japanese stock market volatility using symmetric and asymmetric GARCH models: A case study

Shahil Raza

Department of Commerce, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh, India

Aman Shreevastava

PG Department of Commerce & Management, Purnea University, Purnia, Bihar, India

Bharat Kumar Meher

PG Department of Commerce & Management, Purnea University, Purnia, Bihar, India

Ramona Birau

University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Stefan Margaritescu

University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Gabriela Ana Maria Lupu (Filip)

University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Mircea Laurentiu Simion

University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The main aim of this research paper is to investigate Japanese stock market volatility using symmetric and asymmetric GARCH models. The Nikkei 225 index is the Tokyo Stock Exchange index of 225 publicly owned liquid companies across industries, and the index is calculated using price-weighted-average method. It has been very effective in representing the market sentiment and macroeconomic condition of Japanese Stock market, in this context due to lack of related studies it becomes imperative to study the volatility of the Index. For this purpose, the following models, such as: GARCH, I-GARCH, T-GARCH, E-GARCH, P-GARCH, AP-GARCH (APARCH) were tested across Normal Distribution, Student's T Distribution, Generalized Error Distribution, Parametric T distribution and Parametric Generalized Error Distribution. Based on AIC, SIC and Log Likelihood APARCH at Generalized Error Distribution was chosen. The model displayed strong forecasting capability and from the analysis volatility clustering and asymmetry was evident. It was also identified that the index is sensitive to the leverage effect.

Keywords: *asymmetry, GARCH models, conditional variance, Nikkei 225 index, volatility, Tokyo Stock Exchange, leverage effect, stock market*

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Authors' presentation:

Shahil Raza -Department of Commerce, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh, India

Aman Shreevastava -PG Department of Commerce& Management, Purnea University, Purnia, Bihar, India

Bharat Kumar Meher-PG Department of Commerce& Management, Purnea University, Purnia, Bihar, India

Ramona Birau -University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Stefan Margaritescu -University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Gabriela Ana Maria Lupu (Filip) -University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Mircea Laurentiu Simion -University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Green Technologies and Sustainable Global Business Practices

D. Renukadevi

Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Sharan Kumar Shetty

Department of MBA, AJ Institute of Engineering & Technology – Mangalore, Karnataka, India

P. Vidhya

Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Ramona Birau

Doctoral School of Economic Sciences" Eugeniu Carada", University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Virgil Popescu

Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

P. Manochithra

Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

M. Devaki

Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

N. Devaram

Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Cristina Sultănoiu (Pătularu)

University of Craiova, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences "Eugeniu Carada", Craiova, Romania

Ștefan Mărgăritescu

University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

In an era marked by climate change, resource depletion, and growing environmental concerns, businesses across the globe are under increasing pressure to adopt sustainable practices. Green technologies ranging from renewable energy systems and eco-friendly manufacturing processes to sustainable supply chains and digital innovations are driving a paradigm shift in global business. This paper analyses the integration of green technologies into international business operations, explores their role in enhancing competitiveness, and examines the challenges firms encounter in transitioning to sustainable models. The discussion further highlights future directions and the importance of collaborative efforts among governments, corporations, and consumers in advancing sustainable global business practices.

Keywords: *renewable energy, international business, climate change, resource depletion, sustainable global business practices, green technologies*

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Authors' presentation:

D. Renukadevi - Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Sharan Kumar Shetty - Department of MBA, AJ Institute of Engineering & Technology – Mangalore, Karnataka, India

P. Vidhya - Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Ramona Birau - Doctoral School of Economic Sciences "Eugeniu Carada", University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Virgil Popescu - Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

P. Manochithra - Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

M. Devaki - Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

N. Devaram - Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Cristina Sultănoiu (Pătularu) - University of Craiova, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences "Eugeniu Carada", Craiova, Romania

Ștefan Mărgăritescu - University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania.

Investigating the Impact of e-Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction by Examining the Trends in Consumer Behavior towards Quick Commerce (Q-commerce)

Saidalavi K

Department of Management and Commerce, MANUU, Hyderabad, Telangana, India

Rasheed K

Department of Management, Aliah University, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

Virgil Popescu

University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

Ramona Birau

University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Roxana-Mihaela Nioata (Chireac)

University of Craiova, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences "Eugeniu Carada", Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

Purpose: The rapid growth of Quick Commerce or Q-commerce has underscored the need to understand the factors influencing customer satisfaction, particularly in the context of e-service quality. This study aims to investigate the impact of various e-service quality dimensions on customer

satisfaction within the quick commerce sector. The primary objectives of the study are to assess how efficiency, reliability, privacy/security, responsiveness, and other e-service quality dimensions influence customer satisfaction and to offer actionable insights for improving service quality in Quick Commerce.

Methodology: A quantitative research design was employed, utilizing a sample of 384 users selected through non-probability convenience sampling. Data were collected via an online structured questionnaire, which included sections on demographics, e-SERVQUAL dimensions, and customer satisfaction. The analysis was conducted using SPSS 26 and AMOS 23, with reliability assessed through Cronbach's alpha, and relationships between e-service quality dimensions and customer satisfaction were tested using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).

Findings: The findings reveal that system reliability, hygiene standards, and digital security are significant determinants of customer satisfaction in Quick Commerce. These dimensions are found to have a strong impact on customer trust, loyalty, and retention.

Originality: The study's innovation lies in its application of the SERVQUAL framework to the Quick Commerce context, an area that has not been extensively explored in existing literature. By providing a comprehensive analysis of e-service quality and its impact on customer satisfaction, this research offers valuable insights for industry practitioners aiming to enhance their operational strategies and gain a competitive edge in a growing digital market.

Keywords: *Customer Satisfaction, E-Servqual, Online Consumer Behavior, Quick Commerce, Instant Grocery Delivery Services*

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Authors' presentation:

Saidalavi K - Department of Management and Commerce, MANUU, Hyderabad, Telangana, India

Rasheed K - Department of Management, Aliah University, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

Virgil Popescu - University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

Ramona Birau - University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Roxana-Mihaela Nioata (Chireac) - University of Craiova, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences "Eugeniu Carada", Craiova, Romania

Digital Humanitarianism and the Principle of Distinction: Protecting Tech-Volunteers under International Humanitarian Law

Sarab Thamer Ahmed

*University of Thi-Qar / College of law / Department of public law ALnassiry
Thi-Qar, Iraq*

Abstract:

This research explores the legal challenges posed by the rise of "Digital Humanitarianism" in contemporary armed conflicts, specifically focusing on the "Principle of Distinction" under International Humanitarian Law (IHL). In the era of digitalized warfare, a new category of actors has emerged: tech-volunteers who provide critical humanitarian assistance through big data analysis, crisis mapping, and cyber-security support. However, their remote and intangible involvement in conflict zones creates a legal gray area regarding their protection as civilians.

The study examines the criteria for "Direct Participation in Hostilities" (DPH) as outlined by the ICRC and the Tallinn Manual 2.0, applying these standards to digital activities. It argues that the current legal framework, primarily designed for physical warfare, struggles to categorize digital acts that may inadvertently cross the "threshold of harm" or establish a "belligerent nexus." The research highlights the phenomenon of "Dual-Use Data," where humanitarian information can be exploited for military targeting, thereby stripping tech-volunteers of their civilian immunity and exposing them to military attacks or criminal prosecution.

Furthermore, the paper provides a critical analysis of the regulatory gaps in the Geneva Conventions and their Additional Protocols. It argues that the lack of a "Digital Emblem" or a formal recognition of "Cyber Neutrality" leaves digital aid workers vulnerable to being misidentified as cyber-combatants. The researcher's perspective emphasizes that "data" should be legally recognized as a "civilian object" to ensure the protection of humanitarian infrastructure.

In conclusion, the research proposes the urgent need for a "Digital Protocol" to modernize IHL. It recommends the establishment of a global digital emblem, the codification of cyber-neutrality standards, and the expansion of the definition of "relief personnel" to include technical experts. Without such legal innovations, the safety of tech-volunteers remains compromised, threatening the future of humanitarian action in a hyper-connected world

Keywords: *International Humanitarian Law (IHL), Digital Humanitarianism, Principle of Distinction, Direct Participation in Hostilities (DPH), Tech-Volunteer, Cyber Warfare, Dual-Use Data Geneva Conventions, Cyber Neutrality, Data Protection*

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Author's presentation:

Assistant Professor at the College of Law, University of Dhi Qar, Iraq. Teaches International Organizations to undergraduate students. Teaches International Humanitarian Law in English to postgraduate students. Author of the book "The Legal Status of the Unlawful Combatant in International Humanitarian Law." Author of the book "Attacks on Computer Networks in International Humanitarian Law."

Immersive experience in teaching

Daniela Scorțan

University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

Immersive learning is a learning strategy that, based on high-value technologies, provides artificial content and environments that replicate real-life scenarios. Simulating reality therefore increases student engagement and proactivity in learning. Immersive learning is more profound because the virtual environment allows us to simulate behaviors, decisions, and errors before applying them to real work. The ability to simulate reality with remarkable realism (visual, acoustic, dynamic) allows virtual reality to trick the brain into believing artificial information. We can induce perceptions, environments, and experiences by also modulating the various sensory channels. This is especially important in training and learning processes related to high-risk contexts (for example, medical and healthcare environments or construction sites). Immersive learning represents an effective solution in training and learning processes because, starting from a greater level of engagement, students develop and refine skills and techniques (know-how) in a highly stimulating environment. The effectiveness of virtual environments stems precisely from the spatial design achieved with methodologies borrowed from filmmaking, user interface design, and user experience. Spatial development enhances student immersion by acting on three levels: spatial presence (students enter another dimension); self-presence (students interact and their actions produce effects); and social presence (the virtual environment is capable of fostering interaction between participants). Combining virtual reality and training means exposing the world of education to a paradigm shift. First, in

environmental terms, training shifts from a physical to a fully immersive experience. Second, in temporal and qualitative terms, users have the opportunity to learn more independently, according to their own time and space constraints. Finally, the roles of student and teacher are transformed, with the former becoming an active participant and the latter becoming a facilitator.

Keywords: *Immersive learning, virtual environments, interaction, strategy, experience*

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Author's presentation:

Daniela Scortan defended her doctoral thesis, *A Reading starting from the draft of Zola's novel „The masterpiece”*, in 2005, at the University of Craiova. She graduated from the Faculty of Letters and History at the University of Craiova. She has a diploma in advanced studies, specialization: French literature – poetics. She teaches French as a foreign language at the Department of Modern Languages at the University of Craiova. Her areas of interest are: specialized language, translation, didactics of French as a foreign language, French literature. She is the author of 2 textbooks for economist students and 3 textbooks for distance education and around fifty specialized articles. Selection of recent articles: *Teaching practices with an interdisciplinary approach*, Revista de Științe Politice, Revue des Sciences Politiques, nr. 84, editura Universitaria Craiova, 2024, pp. 143-152. *Using*

students' different learning styles to enhance classroom interaction, Revista de Științe Politice, Revue des Sciences Politiques, nr. 72, editura Universitaria Craiova, 2021. *Quelques outils et méthodes dans l'enseignement des collocations*, volumul Literatura și alte forme de interacțiune discursivă, editura Universitaria Craiova, 2021. *Quelques observations sur l'emploi de la voix passive dans le discours juridique*, Polifonii discursive: identități literare și comunicaționale, Editura Universitaria, Craiova, 2020. *L'expression personnelle en classe de FLE: apprendre aux étudiants à mieux se connaître*, Volum omagial in memoriam Elena Petre, Editura Sitech, Craiova, 2020. *The economic speech in the French press*, Journal of Social Sciences, TEHNICA UTM, 2019.

School dropout among students: how to prevent it

Daniela Scorțan

University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

School dropout can be understood as the failure or irregular use of education and training services by school-age young people. It must be analyzed in holistic and multidimensional terms, as it cannot be traced back to a single cause (be it biological, psychological, or social), requiring a broad and multidisciplinary perspective. A key role in combating school dropout is guidance, which must be ongoing and integrated into the various subjects included in the curriculum, both as an enrichment of the curricular subjects and as a stand-alone subject. For guidance to be truly effective, it is necessary to create a shared framework of essential content for strengthening the self, understanding one's aspirations, and gaining a deeper understanding of the world of study and work, as well as the local context. This development of self-direction skills and the ability to plan actions to achieve the personal and professional development generated by guidance is crucial. To combat the phenomenon of early school leaving, promoting the well-being of young people and their active participation in their educational and social journey, it is necessary to adopt a comprehensive action based on a systemic, consistent, and ongoing approach that addresses educational challenges by investing in individuals and their living environments. Specifically, it is necessary to develop integrated educational systems involving schools, families, and the local community (local authorities, social and health services, associations, educators, and the business community). This will provide an integrated and comprehensive response to the problem through collaborative networks that adopt long-term planning (to ensure continuity in school transitions and support during critical moments) and include monitoring activities to refocus and optimize efforts over time.

Keywords: *School dropout, guidance, support, monitoring activities, aspirations.*

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Author presentation:

Daniela Scortan defended her doctoral thesis, *A Reading starting from the draft of Zola's novel „The masterpiece”*, in 2005, at the University of Craiova. She graduated from the Faculty of Letters and History at the University of Craiova. She has a diploma in advanced studies, specialization: French literature – poetics. She teaches French as a foreign language at the Department of Modern Languages at the University of Craiova. Her areas of interest are: specialized language, translation, didactics of French as a foreign language, French literature. She is the author of 2 textbooks for economist students and 3 textbooks for distance education and around fifty specialized articles. Selection of recent articles: *Teaching practices with an interdisciplinary approach*, Revista de Științe Politice, Revue des Sciences Politiques, nr. 84, editura Universitaria Craiova, 2024, pp. 143-152. *Using students'different learning styles to enhance classroom interaction*, Revista de Științe Politice, Revue des Sciences Politiques, nr. 72, editura Universitaria Craiova, 2021. *Quelques outils et méthodes dans l'enseignement des collocations*, volumul Literatura și alte forme de interacțiune discursivă, editura Universitaria Craiova, 2021. *Quelques observations sur l'emploi de la voix passive dans le discours juridique*, Polifonii discursive: identități literare și comunicaționale, Editura Universitaria, Craiova, 2020. *L'expression personnelle en classe de FLE: apprendre aux étudiants à mieux se connaître*, Volum omagial in memoriam

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The Superiority of Asymmetric Volatility Models: An Empirical Comparison of GARCH-Family Specifications for the Volatility of MSCI Mexico Index

Aman Shreevastava

*P.G. Department of Commerce and Management, Purnea University,
Purnea, Bihar, India*

Shahil Raza

*Department of Commerce, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh,
India*

Bharat Kumar Meher

*P.G. Department of Commerce and Management, Purnea University,
Purnea, Bihar, India*

Ramona Birau

*Finance and Accounting Department, "Constantin Brâncuși" University of
Târgu Jiu, Faculty of Economic Science, Tg-Jiu, Romania & University of
Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova,
Romania*

Virgil Popescu

*University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration,
Craiova, Romania*

Ștefan Mărgăritescu

*University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic
Sciences, Craiova, Romania*

Md. Wahiduz Zama

*Department of Commerce, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh,
India*

Abstract

Financial market volatility is a central component of asset pricing, hedging effectiveness, and systematic risk management. Accurate volatility forecasting is therefore a prerequisite for sound financial decision-making and regulatory compliance. This study addresses the common stylized facts observed in high-frequency financial time series, specifically volatility clustering, leptokurtosis, and the asymmetric impact of news by conducting a rigorous comparative analysis of Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (GARCH) models. The research evaluates the fitting performance of six distinct GARCH specifications, the standard GARCH(1,1), Integrated GARCH (IGARCH), Threshold GARCH (TARCH), Exponential GARCH (EGARCH), Power ARCH (PARCH), and Asymmetric Power ARCH (APARCH) models. These models were applied to a daily log return series of utilizing data spanning over a decade. Crucially, estimation

was performed under both the standard Gaussian and the Student's *t* distributional assumptions to account for non-normality.

Keywords: *MSCI Mexico Index, Asymmetric Volatility, GARCH Models, Time Series Analysis, Leverage Effect*

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Authors' presentation:

Aman Shreevastava - P.G. Department of Commerce and Management, Purnea University, Purnea, Bihar, India

Shahil Raza - Department of Commerce, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh, India

Bharat Kumar Meher - P.G. Department of Commerce and Management, Purnea University, Purnea, Bihar, India

Ramona Birau - Finance and Accounting Department, "Constantin Brâncuși" University of Târgu Jiu, Faculty of Economic Science, Tg-Jiu, Romania & University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

Virgil Popescu - University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

Ștefan Mărgăritescu - University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Md. Wahiduz Zama - Department of Commerce, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh, India

Major Financial Scams that Shook Post-Independent India: An Investigative Study for the long term period 1950-2023

Aman Shreevastava

Research Scholar, P.G. Dept. of Commerce and Management, Purnea University, Purnea, Bihar, India

Bharat Kumar Meher

Assistant Professor, P.G. Dept. of Commerce and Management, Purnea University, Purnea, Bihar, India

Sunil Kumar

Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Purnea College Under Purnea University, Purnea, Bihar, India

Ramona Birau

University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Virgil Popescu

University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

Pankaj Kumar

Assistant Professor, P.G. Department of Economics, Purnea University, Purnea, Bihar, India

Stefan Margaritescu

University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The paper deals with 13 major banking and stock market scams that have shook Indian Financial landscape in 80 years since independence. The scam considered here starts with 1956 Mundhra scam to the recent Mahadev Betting App scam of 2023. With changing times the landscape of financial scam has changed and taken new forms as evident in Adani case as well as Mahadev case. Present values of scams are also calculated using average inflation value since independence. All the scams are of different magnitude and have affected differently with different levels. One common theme observed is poor corporate governance and management practices as the core reason for financial sector failures. There was a period in between when there were series of negligence on the part of NBFC leading to troubles as in the case of PNB, IL&FS, DHFL etc. One common scam theme observed in the case of stock markets since independence was circular trading. Some cases also include poor debt management leading to extreme results.

Keywords: *Circular trading, Hawala, Financial Scam, Accounting Fraud, Algorithmic Fraud, Stock Market Scam*

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Authors' presentation:

Aman Shreevastava - Research Scholar, P.G. Dept. of Commerce and Management, Purnea University, Purnea, Bihar, India

Bharat Kumar Meher - Assistant Professor, P.G. Dept. of Commerce and Management, Purnea University, Purnea, Bihar, India

Sunil Kumar - Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Purnea College

Under Purnea University, Purnea, Bihar, India

Ramona Birau - University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Virgil Popescu - University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

Pankaj Kumar - Assistant Professor, P.G. Department of Economics, Purnea University, Purnea, Bihar, India

Stefan Margaritescu - University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

The Superiority of Asymmetric Volatility Models: An Empirical Comparison of GARCH-Family Specifications for the Volatility of MSCI Mexico Index

Aman Shreevastava

*P.G. Department of Commerce and Management, Purnea University,
Purnea, Bihar, India*

Shahil Raza

*Department of Commerce, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh
202001, India*

Bharat Kumar Meher

*P.G. Department of Commerce and Management, Purnea University,
Purnea, Bihar, India*

Ramona Birau

*Finance and Accounting Department, "Constantin Brâncuși" University of
Târgu Jiu, Faculty of Economic Science, Tg-Jiu, Romania & University of
Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova,
Romania*

Virgil Popescu

*University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration,
Craiova, Romania*

Ștefan Mărgăritescu

*University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic
Sciences, Craiova, Romania*

Md. Wahiduz Zama

*Department of Commerce, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh,
India*

Abstract:

Financial market volatility is a central component of asset pricing, hedging effectiveness, and systematic risk management. Accurate volatility forecasting is therefore a prerequisite for sound financial decision-making and regulatory compliance. This study addresses the common stylized facts observed in high-frequency financial time series, specifically volatility clustering, leptokurtosis, and the asymmetric impact of news by conducting a rigorous comparative analysis of Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (GARCH) models. The research evaluates the fitting performance of six distinct GARCH specifications, the standard GARCH(1,1), Integrated GARCH (IGARCH), Threshold GARCH (TARCH), Exponential GARCH (EGARCH), Power ARCH (PARCH), and Asymmetric Power ARCH (APARCH) models. These models were applied to a daily log return series of utilizing data spanning over a decade. Crucially, estimation was performed under both the standard Gaussian and the Student's t distributional assumptions to account for non-normality.

Keywords: *MSCI Mexico Index, Asymmetric Volatility, GARCH Models, Time Series Analysis, Leverage Effect*

Authors' Contributions:

The authors contributed equally to this work.

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Authors' presentation:

Aman Shreevastava - P.G. Department of Commerce and Management, Purnea University, Purnea, Bihar, India

Shahil Raza - Department of Commerce, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh 202001, India

Bharat Kumar Meher - P.G. Department of Commerce and Management, Purnea University, Purnea, Bihar, India

Ramona Birau - Finance and Accounting Department, "Constantin Brâncuși" University of Târgu Jiu, Faculty of Economic Science, Tg-Jiu, Romania & University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Virgil Popescu - University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

Ștefan Mărgăritescu - University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Md. Wahiduz Zama - Department of Commerce, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh, India

The Evolution of ESG Integrated Lending: Implications for Credit Allocation and Underserved Populations

Andrei SMĂRĂNDESCU

University of Craiova, Doctoral School of Economics Sciences "Eugeniu Carada", Craiova, România

Abstract:

The integration of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) criteria into financial systems is fundamentally transforming traditional credit risk assessment. While this shift successfully promotes sustainable economic practices, its direct impact on financial inclusion remains a complex and underexplored issue. This paper investigates the evolution of ESG-integrated lending, examining its implications for macroeconomic credit allocation and the financial accessibility of underserved populations. By analyzing recent market trends, the study contrasts the approaches of traditional banking institutions with agile Fintech platforms to understand how ESG metrics influence capital distribution. The analysis reveals a significant dichotomy: while traditional banks often apply ESG mandates as rigid risk-mitigation filters that can inadvertently restrict credit for marginalized demographics lacking formal "green" footprints, Fintech companies increasingly leverage alternative data to balance ESG compliance with broader financial access. Ultimately, the findings suggest that Fintech-driven models are more adept at addressing the "Social" pillar of ESG, effectively reallocating credit toward underserved groups. The research concludes that the pursuit of environmental and governance targets must not compromise social equity, advocating for a calibrated lending framework that harmonizes robust ESG objectives with the imperative of financial inclusion.

Keywords: *ESG Integration, Financial Inclusion, Fintech, Credit Allocation, Sustainability, Credit Risk Assessment*

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Author's presentation:

PhD. Student at the Doctoral School of Economic Sciences "Eugeniu Carada," University of Craiova, Romania. I have authored and co-authored multiple impactful scientific articles. My scientific contributions include papers such as "How Artificial Intelligence is Rewriting the Rules of the Game in the Financial Banking Industry" (2025) and "The Future of Work: Automation and Its Impact on Wage Inequality" (2024).

Structural Violence, Occupational Stress, and Trauma-Informed Policy in Helping Professions

Emilia-Maria Sorescu

University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

One of the major achievements of the last century and a half has been the institutionalization of helping professions, reflecting the collective assumption of responsibility for protecting vulnerable individuals, in healthcare, social work, or disaster response. Today, the concern for well-being has moved beyond its economic dimension, including the quality of life, mental health and psychological safety.

But care entails a psycho-emotional cost. Professionals who work in helping fields face risks such as burnout, vicarious trauma, compassion fatigue, and secondary traumatic stress, due to repeated exposure to others' suffering. These phenomena are often treated as individual vulnerabilities addressed through personal resilience interventions. Such an approach ignores the organizational conditions and structural constraints that may themselves operate as traumatizing factors.

Drawing on trauma psychology, occupational stress theory, and the concept of structural violence, this study proposes a dual analytical framework. First, it examines the impact of secondary trauma exposure across micro, meso, and macro levels in the Romanian social work system. Second, it distinguishes between the individualization of occupational stress and its recognition as the outcome of institutional and structural arrangements.

In this context, trauma-informed policy is conceptualized as a systemic strategy for preventing both beneficiaries' re-traumatization and professionals' secondary traumatic stress. The study argues for reframing occupational stress as an issue of public policy and institutional capacity rather than solely individual vulnerability.

Keywords: *structural violence, occupational stress, secondary traumatic stress, trauma-informed policy, social work.*

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Author's presentation:

Emilia-Maria SORESCU is Senior Lecturer, PhD., at University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, having twentyfive years experiences in higher education and in professional training of the social workers. As researcher, as expert in child protection and as trainer, she worked in over 20 European projects (2009-2026) and was short term consultant for World Bank Group (2017-2018). She is also an independent social worker, providing professional social work and social services supervision, working with vulnerable groups, communities, families and children in need, offering consultancy in the field, and she is also certified family and couple psychotherapist, and author and co-author of 18 books and chapters in book, 18 scientific articles and over 50 scientific communication at national and international conferences. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6724-6916

Reconfiguring Corporate Governance under the Impact of Hybrid and Conventional Wars

Lucian Spulbar

University of Craiova, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences "Eugeniu Carada", Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

In the post-pandemic period, the global landscape has been marked by an aggravation of armed conflicts, from the war in Ukraine to the chronic instability in the Middle East, forcing multinational corporations to abandon the paradigm of political neutrality. Through this analysis, we need to understand how corporate policies have transformed from a set of administrative rules into instruments of strategic survival and private diplomacy.

The paper explores the vulnerabilities to which economic entities caught in the middle between international sanctions, ethical consumer pressures, and the need to protect physical and human assets are exposed. We highlight the fact that traditional Business Continuity policies are insufficient in the face of modern warfare, which includes cyber and hybrid dimensions that can paralyze critical infrastructures thousands of kilometers from the front line.

Subsequently, the article investigates the adaptation mechanisms adopted by major economic actors to ensure financial sustainability. Strategies such as *friend-shoring*, radical diversification of supply chains and the implementation of rigorous occupational safety protocols for employees in affected areas are analyzed. Particular attention is paid to the dilemma of exit strategy versus maintaining a presence for humanitarian support, assessing the impact of these decisions on the long-term reputation of the brand.

The research indicate that, in the new era of unpredictability, geopolitical risk management must be natively integrated into corporate governance. Economic survival no longer depends only on market indicators, but on the organizational capacity to anticipate geopolitical mutations and to adopt flexible policies, capable of simultaneously protecting financial, human and moral capital in times of systemic crisis.

Keywords: *Business Continuity Planning – BCP, Geopolitical Risk, Corporate Governance, Conflict Zone Ethics.*

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Author's presentation:

PhD Student, Management Field, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences "Eugeniu Carada". ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6661-4166>.

The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on the Quality and Transparency of Corporate Reporting

Lucian Spulbar

University of Craiova, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences "Eugeniu Carada", Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The transition to the digital economy has generated an unprecedented volume of financial data, making traditional audit methods, based on statistical sampling, partially obsolete. We aim to investigate the disruptive impact of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies on corporate audit processes, analyzing how automation and machine learning algorithms recalibrate standards of accuracy and rigor.

It is important to understand that there is a shift from retrospective auditing to continuous auditing, an innovation that allows us to monitor transactions in real time. Specific AI capabilities are analyzed, such as natural language processing (NLP) for automated contract review and anomaly detection algorithms, capable of identifying fraud attempts or human errors that conventional methods might miss. By analyzing datasets, artificial intelligence manages to eliminate sampling risk, providing superior assurance on the integrity of financial statements, but as a tool used by the human factor.

We also try to address the challenges related to the implementation of these technologies. Particular attention is paid to the interpretability problem (the Black Box concept), where the complexity of algorithms can make it difficult to logically explain audit conclusions to regulators. The implications for human capital are also discussed, arguing that the role of the auditor is

transforming from that of data processor to that of risk interpreter and strategic consultant.

Although artificial intelligence exponentially enhances the efficiency of corporate auditing, the success of its integration depends on the creation of a new ethical and normative framework. Thus, we argue that a synergy between human professional judgment and algorithmic precision represents the sustainable future of corporate governance, ensuring increased transparency in an increasingly complex global business environment.

Keywords: *Machine Learning, Continuous Auditing, Artificial Intelligence, Anomaly Detection.*

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Author's presentation:

PhD Student, Management Field, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences "Eugeniu Carada". ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6661-4166>.

FinTech and the integration of financial markets and institutions: mapping research frontiers and impact pathways

Andrei Cristian Spulbar

University of Craiova, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences "Eugeniu Carada", Craiova, Romania

Cristian Valeriu Stanciu

University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

This study examines how the academic literature has conceptualized and assessed the influence of FinTech on the integration of financial markets and institutions. The objective is to map the field's intellectual structure, thematic evolution, and collaboration patterns in order to clarify dominant mechanisms linking digital financial innovation to market and institutional integration. The approach relies on a structured retrieval of publications from the Web of Science database, using controlled search strings combining FinTech-related terms (FinTech, digital finance, platform finance, open banking) with integration-oriented constructs (financial integration, market integration, banking integration, cross-border payments). After data cleaning and disambiguation of authors, affiliations, and keywords, the analysis synthesizes descriptive indicators and network-based evidence derived from co-authorship, co-citation, and keyword co-occurrence. The expected knowledge structure is organized around three core clusters: (i) efficiency-driven integration through reduced information and transaction frictions via digital payments, data analytics, and alternative credit scoring; (ii) institutional integration enabled by FinTech, interoperability, APIs, and open banking architectures; and (iii) governance and stability tensions reflecting regulatory harmonization, consumer protection, cyber risk, and the potential for new forms of systemic risk. A temporal thematic analysis is anticipated to show a shift from conceptual debates toward empirical designs connecting FinTech adoption to price convergence, capital mobility, and synchronization of credit cycles. The contribution lies in identifying measurement gaps—particularly cross-country comparability of integration metrics and evidence from emerging markets—and in articulating a research agenda with implications for regulatory design and regional interoperability strategies, including EU and other cross-border settings. To strengthen robustness, the study proposes burst detection to capture emerging topics and triangulation across clustering algorithms and similarity measures. Overall, the findings aim to consolidate fragmented evidence and guide future research on FinTech-enabled financial integration.

Keywords: *FinTech; Financial Integration; Market Integration; Open Banking.*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work.

Author’s presentation:

Andrei Spulbar is a dedicated PhD student specializing in finance, with a keen interest in exploring the intricate dynamics of financial markets and their impact on global economies. His research primarily focuses on the intersection of financial technology and traditional financial systems, aiming to uncover novel insights into how technological advancements can optimize financial performance and risk management. Andrei’s academic journey is fueled by a passion for quantitative analysis and econometrics, tools he expertly applies to dissect complex financial models and predict market trends. Beyond his academic pursuits, Andrei is actively engaged in the finance community, contributing to discussions and publications that address current challenges and opportunities within the sector. His work not only adds valuable knowledge to the field of finance but also aims to influence practical applications in investment banking, market analysis, and policy formulation. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-5021-9544>

Dr. Cristian Valeriu Stanciu is Associate Professor within the Department of Finance, Banks and Financial Analysis, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration at the University of Craiova, with 24 years of experience in university education and research. He became a Doctor of Economics in 2005 at the University of Craiova (specialization: International Economic Relations). He also graduated the postdoctoral studies in the Finance field, in 2013. Dr. Stanciu has published more than 66 research papers in journals and conferences; he has authored/co-authored more than 16 books and he has finalized 16 grants and research contracts. His current

research interests include financial markets, economics, quantitative finance, international monetary economy, and corporate finance. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9836-2952>

FinTech and financial stability: risk channels, resilience, and regulatory trade-offs

Andrei Cristian Spulbar

University of Craiova, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences "Eugeniu Carada", Craiova, Romania

Cristian Valeriu Stanciu

University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

This study examines the impact of FinTech on financial stability by synthesizing mechanisms through which digital innovation reshapes risk, resilience, and systemic spillovers. The framework distinguishes four channels. First, efficiency and inclusion effects may enhance stability: real-time payments, automated compliance, and data-driven underwriting can lower costs, reduce information asymmetries, and broaden access to formal finance, supporting diversification. Second, credit and market-cycle amplification may weaken stability when platform lending scales rapidly, models inherit procyclical signals, or competitive pressure compresses margins and increases risk taking. Third, interconnectedness and concentration risks rise as banks and nonbanks rely on shared infrastructures—APIs, cloud providers, and payment gateways—creating common exposures and potential single points of failure. Fourth, operational and cyber vulnerabilities become more material, including outages, model risk, data breaches, and fraud, with disruptions propagating across coupled networks. Building on these channels, the paper proposes a comparative assessment design that links FinTech adoption to macro-financial outcomes (credit growth, asset quality, liquidity conditions, and stress indicators) while accounting for regulatory capacity, market structure, and institutional quality. The contribution is an agenda for research and policy that emphasizes (i) harmonized stability metrics across jurisdictions, (ii) identification strategies to separate innovation effects from contemporaneous shocks, and (iii) proportional responses combining microprudential supervision, macroprudential tools, and oversight of critical third-party providers. Overall, the analysis argues that FinTech's net effect on stability is conditional: innovation can strengthen resilience when governance and infrastructure are robust, but it can also accelerate fragility when risk management, data controls, and supervision lag behind technological change.

Keywords: *FinTech; financial stability; systemic risk; operational & cyber risk; platform lending.*

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Acknowledgment (if any): This work was supported by a grant from the Romanian Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitalization, the project with the title „Economics and Policy Options for Climate Change Risk and Global Environmental Governance” (CF 193/28.11.2022, Funding Contract no. 760078/23.05.2023), within Romania's National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) - Pillar III, Component C9, Investment I8 (PNRR/2022/C9/MCID/I8) - Development of a program to attract highly specialised human resources from abroad in research, development and innovation activities.

Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work.

Author's presentation:

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Dr. Cristian Valeriu Stanciu is Associate Professor within the Department of Finance, Banks and Financial Analysis, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration at the University of Craiova, with 24 years of experience in university education and research. He became a Doctor of Economics in 2005 at the University of Craiova (specialization: International Economic Relations). He also graduated the postdoctoral studies in the Finance field, in 2013. Dr. Stanciu has published more than 66 research

papers in journals and conferences; he has authored/co-authored more than 16 books and he has finalized 16 grants and research contracts. His current research interests include financial markets, economics, quantitative finance, international monetary economy, and corporate finance. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9836-2952>

The Informational Ecology of Public Data in Romania

Oana Stăiculescu

University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Veronica Gheorghiuță

University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

This paper explores the informational ecology of public data in Romania from the perspective of digital governance, transparency, and data reuse. It argues that public data should not be understood merely as administrative outputs made available online, but as dynamic informational resources whose value depends on their accessibility, quality, circulation, and capacity for reuse within the public sphere. An ecological perspective makes it possible to examine not only the production and publication of public data, but also the broader relationships that shape their social relevance and institutional effectiveness. The analysis focuses on three interconnected dimensions. First, it addresses the vitality of public data, understood as their ability to remain accurate, usable, and meaningful over time. Second, it examines the processes of data recycling, namely the reinterpretation and reuse of publicly available information by institutions, researchers, media actors, and citizens. Third, it discusses the phenomenon of informational pollution, reflected in redundancy, fragmentation, inconsistent formats, poor metadata, and limited interoperability. These issues affect both the visibility and the practical utility of public data in the digital environment. The paper argues that the quality of public data ecosystems should be assessed not only by the quantity of published information, but also by the coherence, sustainability, and usability of the informational infrastructures that support them. In this sense, the informational ecology of public data offers a useful conceptual framework for understanding the opportunities and limitations of digital transformation in Romania, while also highlighting the need for more integrated, sustainable, and user-oriented data governance practices.

Keywords: *public data; informational ecology; digital governance; data reuse; informational pollution*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work.

Author's presentation:

As a Lecturer at the University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, **Oana Stăiculescu** brings a strong blend of academic expertise and applied financial experience to her teaching and professional work. With 15 years in higher education, she teaches and coordinates courses including Public Institutions Management, Economics, Public Sector Accounting, Micro/Macroeconomics, Financial Management in Public Institutions, Regional Development, Public Marketing, and Project Management, supporting students with both theoretical rigor and practical relevance. Holding a PhD in Accounting (research focused on the cost of quality as a tool for optimizing organizational performance), alongside advanced studies in audit and financial-accounting management and additional training in pedagogy and entrepreneurship, she is actively involved in professional development and capacity-building. Beyond academia, Oana has extensive hands-on experience in financial management, accounting, and consultancy, including roles such as chief accountant and operations director, and she has contributed to multiple projects as financial manager/responsible, including university and grant-supported initiatives. She is also a trainer for INPPA and the National Administration Institute, and an external evaluator for the Ministry of Energy, reflecting her sustained engagement with public-sector performance, governance, and real-world financial accountability. ORCID ID: 0000-0001-7740-2241.

Mrs. **Veronica Gheorghită** is a Lecturer, PhD, at the University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, within the Sociology and Social Work program, where she has been teaching since 2009 and has held her current position since 2019. Over the years, she has taught a wide range of courses in sociology, anthropology, and social work, including Sociology of Religion, Social Anthropology, Domestic Abuse and Violence, Diagnosis and Resolution of Social Problems, and Social Assistance for Persons with Disabilities. Holding a PhD in Sociology from the University of Craiova, with an academic background in Philosophy and Sociology, Mrs. Gheorghită has developed a strong interdisciplinary profile centered on religion, religiosity, social change, quality of life, vulnerable groups, and domestic violence. Her research activity is reflected in single-author books, co-authored volumes, articles published in national and international journals, and numerous conference presentations. She has also contributed to research and educational projects, held editorial responsibilities, and participated in international Erasmus teaching mobilities in Turkey, North Macedonia, and Bulgaria. Committed to continuous professional development, she has pursued training in research, entrepreneurship, equal opportunities, and academic teaching, while combining teaching, research, and community-oriented academic engagement. ORCID ID: 0009-0006-5642-7849

Decision Rights and Accountability in Government AI

Oana Staiculescu

University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Gabi-Daniela Gărăiman

University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

As artificial intelligence becomes increasingly integrated into public administration, its role is expanding from technical support functions to areas that affect executive judgment and governmental decision-making. This paper examines the relationship between decision rights and accountability in government AI, focusing on how authority, responsibility, and oversight are reconfigured when AI systems are involved in shaping, recommending, or informing public decisions. Drawing on perspectives from algorithmic governance and public management, the paper argues that the central challenge is not primarily technological, but institutional. The key issue is whether democratic systems can preserve clear lines of responsibility when decision processes involve complex interactions between data, algorithms, administrators, and external providers. In this context, decision rights refer to the authority to decide, approve, intervene, and ultimately assume responsibility for outcomes. Accountability, in turn, requires that these rights remain identifiable, contestable, and subject to effective oversight. The paper proposes an analytical framework for understanding government AI through the connection between AI functions, managerial controls, and

legitimacy requirements. It emphasizes that the use of AI in government must be assessed not only in terms of efficiency or innovation, but also in relation to transparency, auditability, due process, and political responsibility. When these conditions are weak, AI may blur responsibility and create accountability gaps, even where human oversight formally remains in place. The paper concludes that the governance of AI in the public sector should be based on accountability by design. This implies explicit allocation of decision rights, traceable procedures, independent auditing mechanisms, and clear remedies in cases of error, harm, or contested decisions. Such an approach is essential if government AI is to remain compatible with democratic legitimacy and administrative responsibility.

Keywords: *government AI; decision rights; accountability; algorithmic governance; public administration*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work

Author’s presentation:

As a Lecturer at the University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, Oana Stăiculescu brings a strong blend of academic expertise and applied financial experience to her teaching and professional work. With 15 years in higher education, she teaches and coordinates courses including Public Institutions

Management, Economics, Public Sector Accounting, Micro/Macroeconomics, Financial Management in Public Institutions, Regional Development, Public Marketing, and Project Management, supporting students with both theoretical rigor and practical relevance. Holding a PhD in Accounting (research focused on the cost of quality as a tool for optimizing organizational performance), alongside advanced studies in audit and financial-accounting management and additional training in pedagogy and entrepreneurship, she is actively involved in professional development and capacity-building. Beyond academia, Oana has extensive hands-on experience in financial management, accounting, and consultancy, including roles such as chief accountant and operations director, and she has contributed to multiple projects as financial manager/responsible, including university and grant-supported initiatives. She is also a trainer for INPPA and the National Administration Institute, and an external evaluator for the Ministry of Energy, reflecting her sustained engagement with public-sector performance, governance, and real-world financial accountability. ORCID ID: 0009-0006-5642-7849.

Mrs. **Gabi Daniela Gărăiman** is an Associate Professor at the University of Craiova, Faculty of Law, where she has been teaching since 2001 and coordinates key courses at the intersection of law and technology, including Legal Informatics, IT for Public Administration, and E-Administration. With strong academic and leadership experience, she also serves as Vice-Dean (2020–present; previously 2014–2016) and has been a member of the Faculty Council across multiple mandates. A PhD in Law (thesis on the complementarities between private law and computer science) and an engineer by training, Mrs. Gărăiman brings a rare interdisciplinary profile to both teaching and research. Committed to continuous professional development, she has pursued specialized training in Moodle administration and emerging themes like AI and the rule of law.

The shipping contract as a hybrid of commission and transport

Cristina Stanciu

University of Craiova, Law Faculty, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The shipping contract is that contract concluded between one party, called the principal, and another party, called the sender, by which the sender undertakes to conclude, in his own name and on behalf of the principal, a transport contract and to carry out operations ancillary to the transport, in exchange for a remuneration, called a commission. Shipment of goods is an intermediary operation, similar to commission. Although it is a variety of the commission contract, the consignment contract is not reducible to it, having its own legal features. At the same time, the shipping contract is not to be confused with the transport contract and they are autonomous in relation to each other. The different possibilities of transport between two geographical areas, the emergence of a growing number of international regulations in matters of import and export on the territory of different states, the need to ensure related operations and services to carry out the transport of goods in good conditions, storage, handling of goods, packaging, grouping and monitoring of transport in real time, customs formalities and planning of optimal routes, have led to an increase in the complexity of the activity related to transport. The volume of specific knowledge generally exceeded the usual trade knowledge and led to the division of labor in the trade branch, emerging and developing a new branch with special professional specificity: international shipping. The interposition of a forwarder (commissioner) between the customer and the carrier is intended to facilitate, from an economic and legal point of view, the movement of goods from the producer to the consumer, all the more so as the economic agent producing the goods or trading the goods usually does not have enough direct information to be able to proceed with the most suitable choice of the carrier and the means of transport. The intermediary specialized in such approaches is the one in a position to exercise convenient options, especially in situations where foreign markets are concerned.

Keywords: *shipment, commission, goods transport contract.*

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Author's presentation:

Cristina STANCIU is Associate Professor, PhD within the Department of Private Law from the Law Faculty at University of Craiova, with 25 years of experience in university education. She graduated at the Law Faculty in 1999, PhD from 2002 (specialization: Law). She also graduated the postdoctoral studies in the Law field, in 2013. She has written 18 specialized books and university manuals, published at national and international recognized editions, she had sustained about 10 nationally and internationally scientific communications, she had published about 55 articles in specialized domestic and foreign publications and she has finalized 4 grants and research contracts. ORCID ID: 0009-0008-7435-5900.

Legal protection in civil law and transport law

Cristina Stanciu

University of Craiova, Law Faculty, Craiova, Romania

Abstract

The Romanian Civil Code defines the notion of security in art. 1.377 and, according to it, the owner or the one who, based on a legal provision or a contract or even just in fact, independently exercises control and supervision over the animal or the thing and uses it in his own interest, has custody of the animal or the thing, and art. 1.376 provides, regarding liability for damage caused by things, that anyone is obliged to repair, regardless of any fault, the damage caused by the

thing under his care. The basis of legal custody consists of a right that gives the legal guardian control, direction and supervision over the work and this right can be a real right or a personal right. Regarding the persons who can have the capacity of legal custodians of things, several principles have been established in the Civil Code: the owner of the thing is presumed, until proven otherwise, to be its legal custodian; the precarious holder, if the owner of the thing transfers custody of it to him through a legal act, becomes the legal custodian of the thing; the case of a client's subordinate, who, abusing the entrusted functions, actually appropriates the power of command, control and use over the work. Regarding the situation in which the owner of the thing transfers custody of it through a legal act, in the doctrine it was considered that there is a split of legal custody, because the person to whom he transfers it - the precarious holder - will acquire the

personal right to exercise, independently, the power of direction, control and supervision over the asset. These are contracts such as: rental, loan, storage, transport. In such cases, the legal custody of the thing can be split between the owner or possessor and the precarious holder, in the sense that the legal custody of the structure of the thing remains with the owner or the possessor and the legal custody of the use or preservation of the thing is the responsibility of the precarious holder.

Keywords: *legal protection, liability, contract of carriage.*

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Author's presentation:

Cristina STANCIU is Associate Professor, PhD within the Department of Private Law from the Law Faculty at University of Craiova, with 25 years of experience in university education. She graduated at the Law Faculty in 1999, PhD from 2002 (specialization: Law). She also graduated the postdoctoral studies in the Law field, in 2013. She has written 18 specialized books and university manuals, published at national and international recognized editions, she had sustained about 10 nationally and internationally scientific communications, she had published about 55 articles in specialized domestic and foreign publications and she has finalized 4 grants and research contracts. ORCID ID: 0009-0008-7435-5900.

The Digital Assets Landscape: A Bibliometric Analysis of Intra-Market Linkages

Cristian Valeriu Stanciu

*Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova,
Romania*

Eugen Stanciu

*"Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, University of
Craiova, Romania*

Abstract:

This research aims to map the intra-market linkages within the cryptocurrency ecosystem by taking into consideration current evidence on return, volatility, liquidity and tail-risk connectedness among major digital assets. Building on Diebold-Yilmaz and related network approaches, the research shows strong time-varying spillovers in returns and volatility across large digital assets, with Bitcoin and Litecoin acting as primary transmitters while Ethereum and Ripple often receiving shocks, specifically in turbulent periods. Recent work on co-movements shows that correlations dominate dynamic spillovers for leading coins, suggesting a relatively efficient but tightly knit market. Beyond the price dynamics, liquidity-based connectedness analyses moderate but rising liquidity spillovers, revealing distinct clusters and stronger short-term integration rather than long term. In addition, quantile-based frameworks highlight that risk transmission intensifies in extreme bullish and bearish scenarios, where digital assets emerge as transmitters of shocks. The literature suggests that the digital asset environment is best understood as a multilayer network where return, volatility, liquidity and risk channels coexist, overlap but occasionally decouple. This paper positions at the intersection of these channels aiming to catalogue and visualize the connection within the digital asset markets, identifying leading assets, methodological hubs and research clusters that expose the understanding of systemic risk and information transmission. The results should. Provide a structured research map for future empirical work on digital assets networks and their implications for participants and regulators.

Keywords: *Cryptocurrency, Bitcoin, DeFi, Altcoins, Connectedness*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this article

Author's presentation:

Dr. Cristian Valeriu Stanciu is Associate Professor within the Department of Finance, Banks and Financial Analysis, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration at the University of Craiova, with 24 years of experience in university education and research. He became a Doctor of Economics in 2005 at the University of Craiova (specialization: International Economic Relations). He also graduated the postdoctoral studies in the Finance field, in 2013. Dr. Stanciu has published more than 66 research papers in journals and conferences; he has authored/co-authored more than 16 books and he has finalized 16 grants and research contracts. His current research interests include financial markets, economics, quantitative finance, international monetary economy, and corporate finance. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9836-2952.

Eugen Stanciu is a finance professional with extensive experience in financial strategy, investment management, and business transformation. Currently working in finance, managing investor relations for a digital assets hedge fund. As a PHD candidate, he focuses on capital markets synergy with digital assets and risk exposure. One of his first academic contributions was published in the Annals of the „Constantin Brâncuși” University of Târgu Jiu, Economy Series, Issue 1/2026. ORCID ID: 0009-0001-7364-4646.

Blockchain Exchange Design and Trading Instruments: A Conceptual Framework for Centralized and Decentralized Markets

Cristian Valeriu Stanciu

*Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova,
Romania*

Eugen Stanciu

*"Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, University of
Craiova, Romania*

Abstract:

This research aims to investigate the evolving structure of the blockchain trading ecosystem with a focus on centralized exchanges (CEX), decentralized exchanges (DEX) and the trading instruments they support. Drawing from recent academic literature on exchange microstructure, decentralized finance (DeFi), and digital assets markets, this study will develop a comparative framework that contrasts CEX's custodial, orderbook based model with DEX's non-custodial architectures base on automated market makers, liquidity pools and smart contracts. We will examine spot trading, margin trading and the growth of derivative instruments such as perpetual future and options showing how instrument design interacts with the exchange architecture to influence liquidity, price discovery, leverage, and risk. From a methodology perspective, this paper combines a structure literature review with a conceptual synthesis of theoretical and empirical findings. A special attention will be paid to issues of solvency, custodial risk on CEXs, smart contracts and oracle risk on DEXs, and the implications of token-based incentive mechanism and governance tokens for trader behavior and market resilience. The analysis contributes to the academic corpus with (a) organizing dispersed evidence on CEX-DEX distinctions into a framework, (b) relating exchange architecture to the specific characteristics of major trading instruments, (c) highlighting new regulatory and design issues that arise in building. Amore integrated and robust crypto-market infrastructure.

Keywords: *Centralized exchanges (CEX), Decentralized exchanges (DEX), Trading instruments, Market microstructure*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this article

Author's presentation:

Eugen Stanciu is a finance professional with extensive experience in financial strategy, investment management, and business transformation. Currently working in finance, managing investor relations for a digital assets hedge fund. As a PHD candidate, he focuses on capital markets synergy with digital assets and risk exposure. One of his first academic contributions was published in the Annals of the „Constantin Brâncuși” University of Târgu Jiu, Economy Series, Issue 1/2026. ORCID ID: 0009-0001-7364-4646.

Dr. Cristian Valeriu Stanciu is Associate Professor within the Department of Finance, Banks and Financial Analysis, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration at the University of Craiova, with 24 years of experience in university education and research. He became a Doctor of Economics in 2005 at the University of Craiova (specialization: International Economic Relations). He also graduated the postdoctoral studies in the Finance field, in 2013. Dr. Stanciu has published more than 66 research papers in journals and conferences; he has authored/co-authored more than 16 books and he has finalized 16 grants and research contracts. His current research interests include financial markets, economics, quantitative finance, international monetary economy, and corporate finance. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9836-2952

The importance of teachers in the educational system

Andreea Mihaela Stoian

University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The worldwide educational system has been changing and reshaping its structure continuously. In nowadays, education as a stand-alone word can have multiple definitions – but, if we refer to the system, then education comprises: modern buildings, trained teachers, teaching methods, receivers (those who are enrolled in different levels of education) and unlimited access to the latest technology. All of these represent the result of thousands of years in which societies evolved and decided to organise their first schools and to acknowledge the fact that the only way to transfer information to future generations is through education.

History shows that ancient civilisations set the basis of education. Archaeologists discovered that it was – almost 3000 years B.C. - on the territories of ancient *Mesopotamia* where education and schools appeared for the first time. Back then, teachers were called *scribes* and they taught reading and writing mainly to the male children from wealthy families. Later, other proofs of education appeared: old documents like *papyrus scrolls* and paintings showing pupils learning how to read and write were found in Egypt and Greece. In time, schools started to diversify their subjects and children were taught: arithmetic, philosophy, how to write official documents, music, poetry and physical training. Moving on, chronologically speaking, it was only in the 20th century when education expanded - reaching mass access, improved its teaching methods and introduced new disciplines. Teachers became the central piece of this system.

This article will explore the importance of teachers in the educational system by emphasizing their role in nowadays society. Although we are living in a period in which we are dominated by algorithm, teachers and the educational system prove the fact that they can adapt to these new challenges.

Keywords: *educational system, teachers, new technologies. evolution, challenges.*

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Author's presentation:

I am Senior Lecturer PhD., at the University of Craiova, the Faculty of Letters, department of Applied Modern Languages. I have been teaching English for Specific Purposes at the non-philological faculties from this University. I have an experience of 20 years in teaching English and in participating at different national and international conferences. A part of my work can be found on my Google Scholar profile. I have published articles related to English literature, English grammar, teaching methods and cultural history. Here are some examples: *Education, social and media communication. Professional Development and Continuous Training of English Teachers. Pronouns in English Language. Language acquisition – English nouns. Romanian Tenses versus English Tenses. Cultural history- the life and art of Constantin Brancusi. The role and purpose of English prepositions. Lumea lui William Shakespeare. The English Adjective – its importance in the syntax of sentences Refugees – a Challenge for the European Union*. I have also published three books: one is related to literature (common traits of Romanian, English and Spanish literature) and the other two are related to ESP: *English for Specific Purposes: Information Technology, Automation English for Specific Purposes: Engineering and Electromechanics*. ORCID ID: 0000-0003-4719-9179.

Multilateral Parliamentary Cooperation as a Tool for Accelerating Western Balkan Integration into the European Union

Agim Sulejmani

South East European University, Tetovo, North Macedonia

Jonuz Abdullai

South East European University, Tetovo, North Macedonia

Abstract:

Despite over two decades of EU enlargement efforts, the six Western Balkan countries face prolonged integration delays due to post-dictatorship legacies and conflicts following the Yugoslav Federation's collapse. While bilateral diplomacy dominates discourse, multilateral parliamentary cooperation remains underexplored as a catalyst for progress.

This paper argues that parliamentary diplomacy fosters internal consolidation, resolves bilateral disputes, and aligns with the Copenhagen criteria, such as political stability, market economies, and *acquis* adoption, thus mirroring goals of regional bodies like the Southeast European cooperation process, Central European Initiative, PABSEC, Adriatic-Ionian Initiative etc. These platforms enable joint membership and collaboration on human rights, rule of law, economic ties, security, and sector-specific issues like tourism and maritime transport.

Using analytical and comparative methods, the study highlights key benefits: shared EU funds, mutual interest recognition, and best-practice exchanges, which have accelerated reforms in North Macedonia in targeted areas. These mechanisms not only build trust but also expedite accession timelines.

Findings underscore parliamentary forums as vital "enablers," offering policymakers actionable strategies for Western Balkan EU paths.

Keywords: *Western Balkans, EU integration, parliamentary diplomacy, Copenhagen criteria, multilateralism, regional cooperation*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work

Author's presentation:

Agim Sulejmani, associate at the International Cooperation Department, PhD candidate at South East European University, Faculty of contemporary social science, Tetovo, North Macedonia. Working on doctoral dissertation on topic of role of parliamentary diplomacy in foreign policy of North Macedonia.

Dr Jonuz Abdullai, full professor at Faculty of contemporary social science in South East European University in Tetova, North Macedonia and Visiting Professor in Kosova. Multi-tasking socio-political professional with expertise in socio-political transition, political sociology and public policy analysis

Scientist works together with Mentor Prof. Jonuz Abdullai
"Parliamentary Diplomacy and Strategic Integration of North Macedonia"
published in VISIONS 47, Skopje
"Parliamentary cooperation of North Macedonia with Kosovo and Albania in the function of good neighborliness and European integration" presented in Shkodra , Albania, October 2026 and should be published in Social Studies, Tirana, Albania, march 2026

Organizational Support for Mental Health: Effects on Employee Wellbeing and Performance

Otilia Maria Trașcă

University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economics Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

Nowadays, the mental health of employees has emerged as a vital theme in organizational and management research literature. In this context, rapid changes in the nature of work, increased work demands, and work pressure have led to increased levels of stress, burnout, and psychological distress among employees in the workplace. In this context, there is a growing recognition of the importance of mental health support in the workplace among organizations. The main purpose of this article is to review the literature on organizational support for mental health and its effects on employees' mental health and work performance outcomes. In this context, this article will synthesize the current literature on organizational support for mental health and its effects on employees' mental health and work performance outcomes based on research literature on organizational psychology, human resource management, and work and organizational health psychology research literature. The literature suggests that organizational support for mental health can have a major impact on the overall well-being of employees by reducing stress, emotional exhaustion,

and burnout. At the same time, access to mental health support and organizational support can have a major impact on increasing the overall levels of work engagement, job satisfaction, and productivity. The literature also suggests the importance of perceived organizational support, as employees who perceive organizational support for their well-being are more likely to have a positive psychological outcome and increase their overall performance. Overall, the literature suggests that investing in mental health support for employees is not just the ethical and social responsibility of the organization, it also has the potential to improve organizational effectiveness and the well-being of employees. The article also concludes with the implications for the organization that would like to develop a comprehensive support strategy for the mental health of employees and the future research directions for this area.

Keywords: *Workplace mental health, Organizational support, Employee wellbeing, Job performance, Mental health support.*

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Author's presentation:

Otilia Maria Trașcă is an ambitious and dedicated researcher in the field of economic sciences, with a strong interest in labor market dynamics and the psychological impact of economic factors on employees. She is currently pursuing her doctoral studies at the Eugeniu Carada Doctoral School of Economic Sciences at the University of Craiova, focusing on modern organizational phenomena. Her research explores contemporary issues such as workaholism and its implications for employee productivity and well-being. She has published several scholarly articles in specialized journals, examining topics like the role of human resources departments in managing excessive workloads and the hidden costs associated with this phenomenon. Through her academic work and contributions to the field, Otilia Maria Trașcă aims to enhance the understanding of modern labor market challenges and contribute to the development of effective strategies for addressing them. ORCID ID: 0009-0008-8598-5879

The Always-On Culture: Expectations for Work Communication Beyond Working Hours

Otilia Maria Trașcă

University of Craiova, "Eugeniu Carada" Doctoral School of Economics Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Abstract:

The use of digital communication technologies has changed the way employees interact with their organization. Employees are able to stay connected with work at all times due to the use of smartphones and other digital communication technologies. This is reflected in the creation of an 'always-on' work culture. Employees feel a need to stay connected and available for work communication beyond working hours. This is a new way of interacting with work and is likely to impact employee outcomes. The aim of this article is to review the existing literature and examine the impact of work communication beyond working hours on employee outcomes. Studies on work communication beyond working hours and work-related smartphone use have found that employees feel compelled to respond quickly to work communication beyond working hours. This reduces the opportunity for employees to psychologically detach from work and is likely to increase stress and emotional exhaustion. Moreover, the literature suggests that more frequent communication during non-working hours with work-related content can lead to higher levels of work-life conflict, sleep problems, and burnout. At the same time, the idea of being constantly connected to technology can create a sense of responsibility to be connected to supervisors and colleagues as well. In this respect, the "always connected" culture can actually contribute to an organizational culture that expects

employees to be connected at all times. Overall, the article suggests that the "always connected" culture is becoming an increasing problem in modern organizations. Perhaps by developing clear communication norms and work-life boundaries, organizations can begin to mitigate some of the negative effects that can come with communication during non-working hours.

Keywords: *Always-on culture, After-hours communication, Work–life boundaries, Digital connectivity, Employee wellbeing*

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Author's presentation:

Otilia Maria Trașcă is an ambitious and dedicated researcher in the field of economic sciences, with a strong interest in labor market dynamics and the psychological impact of economic factors on employees. She is currently pursuing her doctoral studies at the Eugeniu Carada Doctoral School of Economic Sciences at the University of Craiova, focusing on modern organizational phenomena. Her research explores contemporary issues

such as workaholism and its implications for employee productivity and well-being. She has published several scholarly articles in specialized journals, examining topics like the role of human resources departments in managing excessive workloads and the hidden costs associated with this phenomenon. Through her academic work and contributions to the field, Otilia Maria Trașcă aims to enhance the understanding of modern labor market challenges and contribute to the development of effective strategies for addressing them. ORCID ID: 0009-0008-8598-5879

The Impact of AI-Generated Content on Political Discourse in Post-Communist Societies

Dumitru-Catalin Vasile

National School of Political and Administrative Studies, Bucharest, Romania

Abstract:

The rise of Artificial Intelligence is fundamentally changing how we talk about politics. Today, AI-generated content from deepfakes to automated social media campaigns has created a new digital frontier that is both exciting and deeply concerning. While these tools offer fresh ways to reach voters, they also pose serious threats to democratic stability. This is especially true in post-communist societies, where the legacy of state-controlled media and a fragile sense of institutional trust make the public particularly vulnerable to digital manipulation.

This paper explores how AI-generated content is reshaping political debate across Central and Eastern Europe. By comparing recent elections and digital trends, the study looks at how AI narratives interact with local political cultures. It pays close attention to a new "hybrid" form of disinformation: a mix of old-school propaganda techniques and high-tech algorithms designed to polarize the public.

The research finds that AI's impact depends heavily on the local environment, specifically the strength of independent media and the "digital health" of the community. In post-communist contexts, the fact that AI is cheap and easy to hide makes it dangerous; it can widen social divides and undermine transparency in public life. In conclusion, the paper argues that we need more than just simple rules for "taking down" bad content. Instead, we need a regional strategy focused on "algorithmic transparency" and better digital education. By looking at these shifts through the lens of both East and West, this study helps us understand whether new technology will ultimately help or hinder democracy in the former Eastern Bloc.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Political Discourse, Post-Communism, Digital Disinformation, Algorithmic Transparency, Democratic Resilience.*

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Author's presentation:

I am an experienced professional in artificial intelligence governance, cybersecurity, and digital transformation. I currently lead the Department for Artificial Intelligence and Emerging Technologies within Romania's Ministry of Economy, Digitalization, Entrepreneurship, and Tourism, and previously served as Advisor for Digitalization, AI, and Cybersecurity in key ministries. With over twenty years in the technology sector, I have held leadership roles at Probitas ITC, Zebra Technologies, Motorola Solutions, and Oracle, coordinating cross-regional teams and strategic partnerships focused on innovation, software development, and secure digital infrastructure. I hold an Executive MBA from Tiffin University, master's degrees in Business Administration and E-Business, and a degree in Computer Science Engineering. I am pursuing a Ph.D. at SNSPA on AI's impact on foreign and defense policy, while also studying at Romania's National Defense University and National Intelligence Academy. My work explores how AI and

emerging technologies reshape security, modern conflict, and public policy.
ORCID ID: 0009-0003-3257-4156

Exploring the Impact of Privacy, Security, and Ethical Considerations on Consumer Trust in E-Commerce

P. Vidhya

Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Sharan Kumar Shetty

Department of MBA, AJ Institute of Engineering & Technology – Mangalore, Karnataka, India

P. Jayasubramanian

Department of Commerce, Dr.N.G.P. Arts & Science College, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India

Ramona Birau

Doctoral School of Economic Sciences” Eugeniu Carada”, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Virgil Popescu

Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

N. Devaram

Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

M. Devaki

Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Gabriela Ana Maria Lupu (Filip)

University of Craiova, “Eugeniu Carada” Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Roxana-Mihaela Nioata (Chireac)

University of Craiova, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences ”Eugeniu Carada”, Craiova, Romania

D. Renukadevi

Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

P. Manochithra

Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Abstract:

This study explores the pivotal influence of privacy, security, and ethical practices on consumer trust in the e-commerce sector. As online shopping continues to expand rapidly, concerns over data breaches, unethical

practices, and opaque privacy policies have become increasingly significant. The research examines how these factors shape trust and subsequently impact consumer purchasing behavior. By analyzing quantitative data collected from online shoppers, the study employs statistical techniques to identify the primary drivers of trust and offers practical recommendations for e-commerce businesses to strengthen customer confidence and foster loyalty.

Keywords: *E-commerce, Consumer Trust, Privacy, Security, Ethical Concerns, Data Protection, Online Shopping Behavior*

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Authors' presentation:

P. Vidhya - Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science
Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Sharan Kumar Shetty - Department of MBA, AJ Institute of Engineering & Technology – Mangalore, Karnataka, India

P. Jayasubramanian - Department of Commerce, Dr.N.G.P. Arts & Science College, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India

Ramona Birau - Doctoral School of Economic Sciences" Eugeniu Carada", University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Virgil Popescu - Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

N. Devaram - Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science
Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

M. Devaki - Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science

Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Gabriela Ana Maria Lupu (Filip) - University of Craiova, “Eugeniu Carada”
Doctoral School of Economic Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Roxana-Mihaela Nioata (Chireac) - University of Craiova, Doctoral School
of Economic Sciences “Eugeniu Carada”, Craiova, Romania

D. Renukadevi - Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna
College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

P. Manochithra - Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna
College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Algorithmic Hiring and Bias: Evaluating the Accuracy, Fairness, and Ethical Implications of AI-Driven Recruitment Systems

P. Vidhya

*Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts &
Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India*

Sharan Kumar Shetty

*Department of MBA, AJ Institute of Engineering & Technology – Mangalore,
Karnataka, India*

N. Devaram

*Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts &
Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India*

Ramona Birau

*Doctoral School of Economic Sciences “Eugeniu Carada”, University of
Craiova, Craiova, Romania*

Virgil Popescu

*Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova,
Craiova, Romania*

P. Manochithra

*Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts &
Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India*

M. Devaki

*Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts &
Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India*

Stefan Margaritescu

*Doctoral School of Economic Sciences “Eugeniu Carada”, University of
Craiova, Craiova, Romania*

Roxana-Mihaela Nioata (Chireac)

*University of Craiova, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences “Eugeniu
Carada”, Craiova, Romania*

D. Renukadevi

*Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts &
Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India*

Abstract:

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly integrated into recruitment as organizations position their hiring practices as a part of their employer branding and talent marketing strategy. Algorithmic hiring systems not only influence candidate selection but also shape perceptions of fairness, inclusivity, and organizational reputation in the talent marketplace. This study explores the marketing implications of AI-driven recruitment systems, analyzing how accuracy and bias in algorithmic decision-making affect employer branding, candidate experience, and stakeholder trust. Drawing from recruitment marketing frameworks and consumer behavior theory, the research adopts a mixed-method approach—surveying job seekers, analyzing recruitment campaign data, and conducting sentiment analysis of employer reviews. Findings indicate that while AI enhances efficiency and can improve brand positioning through faster, personalized hiring processes, perceived bias or ethical lapses significantly damage organizational image and candidate loyalty. The study provides actionable insights for integrating responsible AI in recruitment marketing, highlighting the need for transparency, fairness, and ethical communication to strengthen long-term brand equity in competitive labor markets.

Keywords: *Recruitment Marketing, Employer Branding, AI in Recruitment, Algorithmic Hiring Bias, Candidate Experience*

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Authors' presentation:

P. Vidhya - Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Sharan Kumar Shetty - Department of MBA, AJ Institute of Engineering & Technology – Mangalore, Karnataka, India

N. Devaram - Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Ramona Birau - Doctoral School of Economic Sciences "Eugeniu Carada", University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Virgil Popescu - Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

P. Manochithra - Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

M. Devaki - Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Stefan Margaritescu - Doctoral School of Economic Sciences "Eugeniu Carada", University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Roxana-Mihaela Nioata (Chireac) - University of Craiova, Doctoral School of Economic Sciences "Eugeniu Carada", Craiova, Romania

D. Renukadevi - Department of Corporate Secretaryship, Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore Tamil Nadu, India

Responsibility as a Lost Value: Bioethical Consequences of Ideological Polarization

Tereza Vozárová

Faculty of Medicine, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic

Abstract:

Growing up in a post-communist country, I became sensitive to how fast ideologies change—and how slowly ethics follows. In Slovakia, we are witnessing a growing divide between liberal and conservative visions of society. Both assert their truths, but neither engages in meaningful conversation. In that space, responsibility disappears.

This paper explores how ideological polarization weakens our capacity to build shared moral frameworks. When concepts like "freedom" or "family" are reduced to slogans, their ethical substance dissolves. I argue—drawing on Levinas, Arendt and Jonas—that responsibility is not the opposite of freedom but its ethical foundation.

In post-totalitarian cultures, where ethics was once imposed, the challenge is now to build values consciously. Without restoring responsibility as a public virtue, bioethics risks becoming ideological itself—loud, but ethically empty.

Keywords: *responsibility, ideology, ethics, bioethics, post-communism, polarization, moral dialogue*

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Author's presentation:

Mgr. Tereza Vozárová, MBA is a physiotherapist and PhD student of bioethics at the First Faculty of Medicine, Charles University in Prague. Her academic interest focuses on philosophical ethics in post-communist contexts, responsibility, and human dignity. She combines clinical background with theoretical insight, aiming to build bridges between practice and reflection. ORCID ID: 0009-0000-1775-9222.

Media and Culture in Croatia in the Post-War Period (1945–1946)

Ivana-Marija Vrsaljko

University of Zadar, Department of Applied Communication Studies, Zadar, Croatia

Marijana Ražnjević Zdrilić

University of Zadar, Department of Applied Communication Studies, Zadar, Croatia

Abstract:

The media play a significant role in shaping public perception and preserving the cultural identity of every country. The period following the Second World War was turbulent, marked by profound changes in the political, cultural, and economic context. During the wartime destruction, the city of Zadar in Croatia suffered extensive damage, both in terms of its population and infrastructure. In such circumstances, the printed newspaper *Slobodna Dalmacija* played a key role in promoting and documenting cultural events, thus becoming an important messenger of the city's cultural life. The subject of this study is the media representation of cultural events in Zadar during the period from 1945 to 1946, examined through the example of the newspaper *Slobodna Dalmacija* within the context of post-war Croatia. The aim of the research is to examine the extent and manner in which cultural content was presented in the post-war press and to determine its social role in the process of rebuilding the local community. The research period covers the publication of the local newspaper *Slobodna Dalmacija* in Zadar from 1 January 1945 to 31 December 1946. The units of analysis are newspaper articles dealing with cultural events, including reports on cultural manifestations, theatre performances, musical events, exhibitions, and the activities of city libraries, museums, and galleries. The research sample comprises 65 issues of the newspaper. The study applies a descriptive method as well as quantitative and qualitative content analysis. The results indicate a pronounced presence of cultural topics in the media space,

despite the complex socio-political circumstances of the post-war period. Furthermore, the findings show that the printed medium *Slobodna Dalmacija* played an important role in promoting cultural activities, strengthening social cohesion, and preserving the cultural identity of Zadar and its surrounding area.

Keywords: *media, culture, post-war period, Croatia, content analysis*

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Acknowledgment: The work is based on the research of student Ivana-Marija Vrsaljko, which was carried out for the purpose of writing a diploma thesis under the mentorship of Marijana Ražnjević Zdrilić, associate professor.

Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work

Authors' presentation:

dr. sc. Marijana Ražnjević Zdrilić, associate professor at the Department of Tourism and Communication Sciences, University of Zadar. At the Department, I give lectures and seminars from the courses Media Literacy, Business Communication, Theory of Mass Communication and Strategic Communication. I direct my academic work and research in the field of communication sciences - media and communication. I teach students through lectures and seminars about theoretical concepts of mass communication, mutual influence of mass media and society, critical analysis of media content within the framework of media literacy and successful communication in a business and social context. I focus my research work on the study of various current topics in the field of communication sciences, including artificial intelligence.

Ivana-Marija Vrsaljko, Master of Digital Communication, completed a graduate study in Digital Communication at the University of Zadar. She is employed as an Archival Technician at the State Archives in Zadar, Croatia.

Krakow's participatory school budget as an example of civic education
Barbara Węglarz
University of the National Education Commission in Krakow, Poland
Joanna Lampa
Andrzej Frycz Modrzewski University in Krakow, Poland

Abstract:

Participatory school budget is an example of civic education implemented in Polish schools. Within this process, students submit their own ideas, develop project proposals, and participate in voting to select the initiatives they consider the most valuable for their school community. The concept of the participatory school budget emerged as an adaptation of the traditional participatory budgeting process to the needs of smaller, local communities such as schools.

Participation in this initiative enables students to co-decide on issues concerning their immediate environment. At the same time, it is intended to foster civic competencies and prepare young people for active participation in participatory budgeting processes implemented by local governments in Poland.

The aim of this paper is to present the origins and basic principles of participatory budgeting and to focus particularly on the participatory school budget as a form of civic education. Special attention is given to a case study from the Polish city of Kraków, where participatory school budget has been implemented in selected schools. The paper also discusses a national initiative of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education aimed at promoting participatory budgeting in schools.

The study is based on document analysis and critical content analysis, complemented by historical and comparative methods. The paper seeks to demonstrate how participatory school budgeting can function as a practical tool for developing civic engagement and democratic participation among students.

Keywords: *civic education, participation, participatory budget, participatory school budget*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work.

Author's presentation:

Barbara Węglarz, PhD -PhD in Political Science, MA in Political Science, MA in Russian Philology. Affiliation: University of the National Education Commission in Krakow. Research interests: administrative law, local government, direct democracy.

Joanna Lampa - fifth-year law student at Andrzej Frycz Modrzewski University in Krakow. Area of research: administrative law.

Data on SD Activity in Romania Resulting from the SOE Investigation of Jacob Lendermann

Marian Zidaru

Asociația „Casa Mării Negre”/ Black Sea House, Constanța, Romania

Stoica Lascu

The Romanian Academy of Scientists, Constanța, România

Abstract:

Jacob Lendermann arrived in Aleppo from Bucharest on April 12, 1944. Upon arrival he was interrogated by SOE and MI5 agents. From the above, it can be seen that Lendermann knows much more than an ordinary Jewish refugee, being asked how he obtained this information. He says that he did not speak to any of the above-mentioned persons, except FUSS, who provided him with all the above information, He volunteered information when questioned about the investigation into Jewish refugees. This work presents new data on the organization of the SD in Romania during World War II.

Keywords: *Jacob Lendermann, SD, SECURITY, ALEPO, ABWEHR.*

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Authors' Contributions: The authors contributed equally to this work.

Authors' presentation:

ZIDARU Marian (born 8 May 1964) is a Romanian historian. He has Associate Professor at Andrei Șaguna University Constanța and wrote 6 books as a sole author and over 110 articles and studies (especially, the history of the Romanians, including those from Dobruđa and Bessarabia). He used to teach History International Relations, Theory of International Relations, and History of Europe. Member of various societies and scientific associations. TV commentator on national history, international relations and political science. Now is retired.

LASCU Stoica (born 18 June 1951) is a Romanian historian. He has authored over a dozen books and over 380 studies and articles in journals and volumes from Romania and abroad (papers about Modern and Contemporary History of Romania, Dobruđa, Aromanians, Modern Balkan, Romanian Historiography). Former Professor at Ovidius University of Constanța – Faculty of History and Political Science). Now is retired.

Roundtable Discussion: East–West Dialogue Thirty Years On & CEPOS Research Workshop and Tutorials Series: Security, Governance and Public Policy: Community Engagement and Social Dynamics

All Day-1 Participants — Paper Presentations & Moderated Discussion
Physical Attendance

Anca Parmena Olimid, University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Romania

Citizens-Focused Governance, Security and Digital Information Integrity: An Updated Review of the Evolving Topics and Emergent Metrics

Abstract:

Objectives: This paper engages two central research objectives. The first objective aims to analyze the mechanisms and technical information security tools used in digital governance including online platforms and critical infrastructures. The second objective engages the projection of new policy perspectives in digital ecosystems.

Methods and methodology: The research methodology aims at a complex framework of methods including (a) scoping review of recent topics such as “artificial intelligence security”, “information resilience”, “platform governance”, “public accountability”, “social legitimacy”, “digital citizenship”, “information ecosystems” and (b) framework synthesis with the aim of identifying an integrated model of multi-level domain analysis configured tools-trends-determinants-metrics-policies.

Findings and discussions: The research results identify two sets of recent trends and metrics as follows: (1) the first set focuses on the dominant trends and topics recently used in scientific literature and applied research and (2) policy trends and regulatory instruments in the field of organizational responsibility, prevention and information security.

Conclusions: In conclusion, the study highlights the need for cross-sectoral research on digital governance, identifying a hybridization of concepts across the technological ecosystem and the legal regulatory spectrum of the field. In the second assessment, the study reflects recent anticipatory and user-oriented approaches.

Keywords: *citizens, governance, digital information, public accountability, social legitimacy.*

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Author's presentation:

Anca Parmena Olimid Ph.D. is Associate Professor at the University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Department of History, Political Sciences, International Relations, Political Sciences Specialization. She holds a B.A. in Law from the Faculty of Law (2003) and a B.A. in Political Sciences from the Faculty of History, Philosophy and Geography, University of Craiova (2003) and a Ph.D. in Humanities from the Faculty of History, Philosophy and Geography of the University of Craiova (2008). Her specialist subject areas are Romanian Politics since 1989, Modern and Contemporary Political Thought, the relationship between society, state and religion, Geopolitics and Geostrategy. Two of Professor Olimid's outstanding achievements is her receipt of Economic and Social Council, ECOSOC (WYA), UN Headquarters,

New York for a three months internship in 2005 and her Erasmus Scholarship for six months at the University Charles de Gaulle Lille III, France in 2001-2002. Mrs. Olimid has published widely in international databases and national political journals and is the (co)author of several books, notably, *Politics and Religion in EU and USA. Legal commentaries and social controversies* (2010), *Political and spiritual life in Modern Romanian. A Romanian Model of Church-State Relations* (2009) awarded by the Ministry of Education and Research in 2009, Romanian Politics since 1989 (2009); *Politics, Security and Participatory Governance: Key Concepts, Policies and Legislation* (2015). Editor-in-chief of *Revista de Științe Politice/Revue des Sciences Politiques*. ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7546-9845>.

Cătălina Maria Georgescu, University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Investigating Institutional Image in Security Contexts: An Imagological Framework Combining Press Monitoring and Social Media Analysis

Abstract:

Scope and Objectives: This study examines the construction and influence of the public image of an institutional actor within a contemporary security context. Its main objective is to analyze how traditional media and social media narratives shape perceptions of the actor, highlighting the interplay between press coverage and online content on social networks. The research focuses on both local and international sources to assess the actor's image and its implications for national and regional security.

Methodology: A mixed-methods approach was employed, combining traditional press monitoring with visual and social media analysis. Data sources included at least 10 news articles from multiple press outlets over a minimum 7-day period, official institutional posts and video content on Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube. Analyses included identifying the content tone, themes, symbolic elements, and narrative framing, propelled by qualitative interpretation of imagology and language.

Results and Discussion: The findings indicate that the actor's public image is shaped by a combination of positive, neutral, and negative narratives, often reflecting strategic messaging, symbolism and stereotypes. Social media content amplified certain narratives—particularly those evoking authority, heroism, or fear—while occasionally opposing press coverage. Visual elements were found to significantly influence audience perception and specific security-related narratives.

Conclusions: The study underscores the importance of integrated traditional media and social networks monitoring in understanding the public perception of institutional actors in security contexts. It demonstrates how press and social media narratives interact to construct public images, influencing both domestic and international perceptions. Effective

management of imagology emerges as a critical factor in national security strategy and public trust.

Keywords: *image, security context, imagological framework analysis, press monitoring, social media analysis.*

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Author's presentation:

Cătălina Maria Georgescu is Lecturer Ph.D. at the Faculty of Social Sciences, Political Sciences Specialization within the University of Craiova. She received her Ph.D. in 2011 from the University of Craiova, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration. She has a BA degree in Political Sciences (2006) in English Specialty from the Faculty of Political Sciences, University of Bucharest. She completed her MA degree in Political Sciences – National and Euro-Atlantic Security at the University of Craiova (2011). She is the (co-)author of 5 books and of over 60 studies and reviews published as book chapters or articles in publications indexed in international data bases. Her areas of scientific interest include the politics-administration relations, public policies, management of public organizations, European governance, security and democratization in South-Eastern Europe. Deputy Editor-in-chief at *Revista de Științe Politice/Revue des Sciences Politiques*. ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4462-4689>.

Cosmin Lucian Gherghe, University of Craiova, Faculty of Social Sciences, Craiova, Romania

Analysing the Legal Framework of Information Security and the Fight against Disinformation in Romania: The Interaction between National Security, Cyber Infrastructure, and Democratic Processes

Abstract:

This paper presents a research approach over the legal provisions on information security and disinformation. The analysis unfolds on the following directions: analysing the legal basis on defining the threats to national security in the context of disinformation, the legal framework for the creation of cyber security infrastructure and institutional framework to combat online disinformation, legal analysis on the limitation in the exercise of rights in the context of national security. The approach also follows a comparative analysis of domestic the legal framework and the EU regulations regarding cybersecurity aiming at assessing the legislative harmonisation of national legislation to European directives.

Keywords: *information security, legal framework, disinformation, cyber security infrastructure, democratic process*

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Data Inputs based on Research Topics and Online Mentions Tracking, *Revista de Științe Politice. Revue des Sciences Politiques* No. 85/2025, 43-56.

Author's presentation:

Cosmin Lucian Gherghe, Ph.D. is Associate Professor at the Political Sciences Specialization, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova. He holds a Ph.D. degree in History (2008) from the Faculty of History, Geography and Philosophy, University of Craiova and a B.A. in Political Sciences (2003) from the Faculty of History, Geography and Philosophy, University of Craiova and in Law (1999) from the Faculty of Law and Administrative Sciences, University of Craiova. He is the author of over 40 articles, studies and papers published in scientific journals or presented in national and international conferences. He is the author of "Emanoil Chinezu – Om politic, avocat și istoric", Editura Sitech, Craiova, 2009 and (co-author) "Partidele politice", Editura Sitech, Craiova, 2008. His areas of interest include political parties, constitutional law, administrative and political institutions. He is member of 3 research projects/grants and also a member of the editorial board of *Revista de Științe Politice/Revue des Sciences Politiques*. ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9131-0391>.

STUDENT RESEARCH SESSION: Applied Intelligence Analysis (A2I) Panel& EU POLICIES AND SECURITY (CEPOS Student Project Research, Quiz, Facts, Press and Legal Monitoring, Social Analysis)

CEPOS & Political Sciences specialization, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova - CEPOS 15th international student symposium
Coordinating Professors: Parmena Olimid, Cătălina Georgescu, Cosmin Gherghe. Date: launched on December 2025-March 2026

STRENGTHENING OF COMMON SECURITY AND DEFENCE POLICY (CSDP) - CASE STUDY: THE STRATEGIC COMPASS FOR SECURITY AND DEFENCE (2022)

MIRELA-GEORGIANA GHEORGHIU (MA Political Sciences, National and Euro-Atlantic Security, 1st year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova)

Abstract: In a constantly changing geopolitical context, there is a need to coordinate efforts to ensure the safety of EU citizens, of solidarity and cohesion and a unified vision to ensure the consolidation of the European Union's security and defense policy. Today, more than ever, is necessary to send a strong message to deter potential threats to European security, to encourage innovation and integration of the EU's Defence Technological and Industrial Base (EDTIB) and to adapt quickly to the new reality.

Keywords: safety, adaptability, changing geopolitical context, unified vision, strengthening of common security and defence policy (CSDP)

CYBERSECURITY, RESILIENCE SHIELD AGAINST HYBRID THREATS

THEODOR GHEORGHIU (MA Political Sciences, National and Euro-Atlantic Security, 1st year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova).

Abstract: In an increasingly digitalized world, exposed to vulnerabilities capable of jeopardizing European security, the European Union's efforts have been channeled towards protecting essential services and critical infrastructure against cyber threats, creating the necessary framework for enhancing the EU's cyber resilience, covering critical sectors and addressing risks in an integrated manner, which prevents threats from materializing and mitigate vulnerabilities in a complex geopolitical and digital context, unstable due to the intensification of attacks on critical infrastructures and hybrid actions that risk threatening European security. In this context, cyber resilience is not just a necessity, but an imperative to achieve, as it should be seen as a resilience shield against hybrid threats.

Keywords: cyber threats, critical entities, hybrid threats, mitigate vulnerabilities, cyber resilience

EU MIGRATION AND ASYLUM POLICIES

SILVESTRU-ȘERBAN PÂSLARU (MA Political Sciences, National and Euro-Atlantic Security, 1st year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova)

Abstract: Migration has been a central issue for the European countries, and over the years the European Union has faced several major migration crises. Events such as the 2015 refugee crisis, the Covid-19 pandemic, and, more recently, Russia's illegal invasion of Ukraine have tested the capacity and resilience of Member States in managing migration and asylum. These developments highlighted significant shortcomings in the existing system and accelerated the need for comprehensive reform. The New Pact on Migration and Asylum, adopted in 2024, aims to modernize and streamline current procedures, making them more effective and less time-consuming. Another key objective is to balance solidarity and responsibility by introducing more flexible mechanisms for relocation, border procedures, and returns. As the Pact becomes fully applicable this year, it will represent a crucial test for European cohesion and the EU's ability to implement a more coherent and sustainable asylum framework.

Keywords: European Union, member states, migration crises, asylum, reform, refugees, solidarity, cohesion, sustainability.

EU SECURITY POLICY IN THE EASTERN NEIGHBORHOOD (REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA, UKRAINE, GEORGIA)

RUXANDA RADU NICOLAE (MA Political Sciences, National and Euro-Atlantic Security, 2nd year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova)

Abstract: I chose this topic because I find what is happening in the field of geopolitics nowadays interesting. Geopolitics is a field that is constantly changing in the countries on the European continent such as the Republic of Moldova, Ukraine, Georgia, and also on a global level. Currently, heavy, bloody battles are taking place on Ukrainian territory, with many deaths, especially among young people, involving the Russian army which seeks to impose its power and the ideologies coming from the Russian state capital, Moscow. The danger of the war spreading beyond the borders of the Ukrainian state is so great that countries not under NATO protection fear becoming the target of a future attack. Thus, the European Union has come to the aid of countries that wish to maintain their territorial integrity and state independence, such as the Republic of Moldova, Ukraine, and Georgia, through military equipment. The Eastern Partnership is an important

demonstration of the assistance provided by the European Union against the expansionist ambitions of other states.

Keywords: EU security policy, geopolitics, war, NATO, aid, Eastern Partnership.

EU CYBERSECURITY STRATEGY 2020–2025

DANIEL-PETRUȚ BĂȘĂȘTEANU (MA Political Sciences, National and Euro-Atlantic Security, 1st year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova, Romania)

Abstract: The rapid digital transformation of European societies has increased both the opportunities and the vulnerabilities within the digital space. Cyberattacks targeting public institutions, private companies, and critical infrastructure have become more frequent and sophisticated. In this context, the European Union adopted the EU Cybersecurity Strategy for the Digital Decade (2020–2025), aiming to strengthen Europe's resilience against cyber threats and to ensure a secure digital environment for citizens and businesses. The strategy focuses on three main pillars: resilience, technological sovereignty, and global leadership in cybersecurity. First, the EU aims to strengthen the resilience of critical infrastructures, public administrations, and private sectors by improving cooperation between Member States and enhancing incident response capabilities. Institutions such as the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) play a key role in coordinating cybersecurity policies and supporting national authorities. Second, the strategy promotes technological development and digital sovereignty by investing in advanced cybersecurity technologies, innovation, and research. The EU encourages the development of secure digital infrastructures, including 5G networks, cloud services, and artificial intelligence systems, while reducing dependency on external technological providers. Finally, the EU Cybersecurity Strategy emphasizes international cooperation and global leadership. The European Union seeks to promote international norms and responsible behavior in cyberspace while strengthening partnerships with NATO and other strategic partners to counter cyber threats and hybrid attacks. In conclusion, the EU Cybersecurity Strategy 2020–2025 represents a comprehensive framework designed to protect European digital space, enhance resilience against cyber threats, and ensure a secure and trustworthy digital future for the European Union.

MIGRATION AND THE EU ASYLUM POLICY

SPERIATU-MIRESCU ROBERT-CRISTIAN (National and Euro-Atlantic Security, 2nd year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova)

Abstract: The present paper analyses the European Union's approach to migration and asylum, focusing on the balance between security concerns and the protection of fundamental rights. In recent years, migration has increasingly been framed as a security challenge, prompting the EU to strengthen its legislative and institutional framework in order to manage migratory flows more effectively. The research examines key EU regulations, particularly Regulation (EU) 2021/1147 establishing the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund and Regulation (EU) 2024/1359 addressing situations of crisis and force majeure in the field of migration and asylum. In addition, the paper incorporates an analysis of media discourse from the period 2024–2025, drawing on articles published by Euronews, Amnesty International, and the Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. This analysis reveals growing concerns regarding the securitization of migration policies and their potential impact on fundamental rights, particularly in relation to data protection, detention practices, and cooperation with third countries. The paper concludes that while the European Union seeks to establish a coherent and effective migration and asylum system, significant challenges remain in ensuring that security measures do not undermine the core values and human rights principles on which the EU is founded.

Keywords: European Union, Migration, Asylum, Security, Fundamental Rights, Solidarity.

THE UE-NATO PARTNERSHIP IN MANAGING HYBRID THREATS

DUMITRU-RADU GURAN (MA Political Sciences, National and Euro-Atlantic Security, 2nd year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova)

Abstract: The partnership between the European Union and NATO is essential for managing modern hybrid threats. Hybrid threats combine military and non-military means, such as disinformation, cyberattacks, and economic pressure. Cooperation intensified after 2016, when the two organizations signed joint declarations. The main goal is to increase the resilience of member states and protect critical infrastructure. The EU contributes through civilian, economic, and legislative instruments. NATO provides military expertise, defense capabilities, and rapid response mechanisms. Information sharing between the two organizations allows early identification of risks. They also organize joint exercises to prepare against hybrid attacks. Cooperation also targets combating propaganda and strengthening cybersecurity. This partnership strengthens Euro-Atlantic security and the ability to respond to new types of threats.

Keywords: Hybrid threats, Critical infrastructure, Security, Resilience, NATO, European Union.

THE EU CYBERSECURITY STRATEGY 2020–2025: A FRAMEWORK FOR DIGITAL SECURITY

LIXANDRA MARIA-ADELA (MA Political Sciences, National and Euro-Atlantic Security, 1st year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova)

Abstract: The rapid digital transformation of European societies has significantly increased both opportunities and vulnerabilities in the cyber domain. In response to the growing number of cyberattacks, hybrid threats and risks targeting critical infrastructures, the European Union adopted the Cybersecurity Strategy for the Digital Decade (2020–2025). The strategy represents a comprehensive framework aimed at strengthening the EU's digital resilience, ensuring technological sovereignty and enhancing cooperation among Member States. This paper analyses the main pillars of the EU Cybersecurity Strategy, focusing on resilience, operational capacity and global leadership in cyberspace. Particular attention is paid to the protection of critical infrastructures, the development of a coordinated cyber crisis response mechanism and the consolidation of partnerships at international level. The study also examines the institutional architecture supporting the implementation of the strategy and the interaction between cybersecurity and broader security and defense policies. The analysis highlights both the progress achieved and the structural challenges that continue to affect the coherence and effectiveness of European cybersecurity governance. The paper concludes that the EU Cybersecurity Strategy 2020–2025 represents a significant step towards a more secure and autonomous digital Europe, while emphasizing the need for sustained investment, coordination and strategic adaptability.

Keywords: European Union, cybersecurity strategy, digital resilience, critical infrastructure, strategic autonomy.

COUNTERING DISINFORMATION AND HYBRID THREATS IN THE

CIUPITU GABRIELA-CRINA (BA Political Sciences, 2nd year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova)

This report explores the critical security challenges posed by disinformation and hybrid threats within the European Union. In an era of rapid digitalization, information has evolved into a strategic tool used for both public awareness and malicious manipulation, aimed at undermining democratic processes and institutional trust. Hybrid threats are defined as coordinated actions combining military and non-military means—such as cyberattacks and economic pressure—to exploit political and social vulnerabilities without triggering conventional armed conflict. The document identifies a diverse range of actors involved in these activities, including

hostile states, extremist groups, and non-state entities like automated bot networks. These actors often operate in a coordinated manner to amplify manipulative narratives. To counter these risks, the EU has established a robust legal framework, notably the Digital Services Act (DSA) and the Code of Practice on Disinformation, which emphasize platform transparency and content moderation. Key institutional players, such as the European Commission, the European External Action Service (EEAS), and the European Parliament, collaborate to monitor hostile narratives and strengthen informational resilience. Furthermore, the report highlights the importance of media literacy as a primary defense, empowering citizens to critically evaluate sources. Despite these efforts, the evolution of artificial intelligence and the lack of global regulatory uniformity present ongoing challenges to maintaining the balance between security and the fundamental right to freedom of expression.

Keywords: Disinformation, Hybrid Threats, European Union, Digital Services Act, Cybersecurity, Media Literacy, Strategic Compass

EUROPEAN HEALTH SECURITY AFTER COVID-19: THE ROLE OF HERA AND ECDC

SAVIN ALEXANDRU GABRIEL (BA Political Sciences, 2nd year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova)

The COVID-19 pandemic represented an unprecedented challenge for the European Union, testing not only the resilience of national healthcare systems but also the limits of European coordination in times of crisis. The initial phase of the pandemic revealed significant structural vulnerabilities, including shortages of medical equipment, fragmented decision-making processes, and limited strategic reserves of essential medicines. These shortcomings generated important debates regarding the need to strengthen the EU's competences in the field of health security and crisis management. In response to these challenges, the European Union initiated a process of institutional consolidation aimed at building a stronger and more integrated European Health Union. A key development in this process was the creation of the Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority (HERA), whose primary objective is to anticipate cross-border health threats, support research and innovation, secure the production and stockpiling of medical countermeasures, and ensure rapid access to vaccines and treatments during emergencies. HERA represents an important step toward increasing the EU's strategic autonomy in the pharmaceutical and biomedical sectors. At the same time, the mandate of the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) has been significantly reinforced. The agency now benefits from expanded powers in epidemiological surveillance, data collection, risk assessment, and coordination of responses among Member States. By improving monitoring systems and providing scientific

guidance, the ECDC contributes to a more coherent and evidence-based European response to health crises. This paper analyzes the post-pandemic transformation of European health security governance, focusing on the complementary roles of HERA and ECDC within the broader framework of the European Health Union. It evaluates the effectiveness of these reforms, the remaining challenges related to sovereignty and coordination between national and supranational levels, and the long-term implications for European integration. Ultimately, the study argues that the consolidation of EU health security mechanisms represents not only a functional necessity but also a significant step in deepening political integration in response to transnational crises.

Keywords: European Union, health security, COVID-19, HERA, ECDC, European Health Union, crisis management, European integration.

EU SECURITY POLICY IN THE MEDITERRANEAN AND THE MIDDLE EAST

ANA MARIA CORNELIA SIRBU (MA Political Sciences, National and Euro-Atlantic Security, 1st year, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Craiova)

Abstract: E.U. security policy in the Mediterranean and Middle East has evolved in 2026 toward active strategic autonomy, integrating military presence with normative rigor. Through operations ASPIDES and IRINI, the Union exercises its role as a guarantor of freedom of navigation, protecting vital trade routes against asymmetric threats and arms proliferation. This power projection is coupled with coercive legal instruments, such as Regulation (EU) 2026/271, aimed at degrading the technological capabilities (UAV) of destabilizing actors. Furthermore, the 2025 Pact for the Mediterranean redefines the region as a common space of resilience, where the security of critical undersea and energy infrastructure becomes a shared strategic priority. Essentially, the EU is shifting from reactive crisis management to an integrated approach, employing technological sanctions, strategic dialogue with Gulf states, and naval missions to secure this essential geopolitical corridor between Europe and Asia.

Keywords: European Union, naval missions, Mediterranean, Middle East, strategic priority.

After Conference.

Manuscript Submission

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For chapters in edited books

Goodin, R. E. (2011). The State of the Discipline, the Discipline of the State. In Goodin, R. E. (editor), *The Oxford Handbook of Political Science*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 19-39.

For journal articles

Georgescu, C. M. (2013a). Qualitative Analysis on the Institutionalisation of the Ethics and Integrity Standard within the Romanian Public Administration. *Revista de Științe Politice*, (37), 320-326.

Georgescu, C. M. (2013b). Patterns of Local Self-Government and Governance: A Comparative Analysis Regarding the Democratic Organization of Thirteen Central and Eastern European Administrations (I). *Revista de Științe Politice*, (39), 49-58.

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Tables and figures are introduced in the text. The title appears above each table.

E.g.:

Table 1. The results of the parliamentary elections (May 2014)

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